

NASA Interplanetary Mission (NIM) Database

A Survey of System Attributes for NIM Launched Between 1989 and 2023

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ABSTRACT

The database consists of a survey of NASA Interplanetary Missions (NIMs) launched between May 1989 and October 2023. Mission data includes system-level attributes in support of advanced system-level modeling. The attributes include elements of the program, schedule, cost, and technical design. Cost silos include three inflation formats: Then\$ representing realized expenses in the Year of recording, NASA's New Start Inflation Index (NSII) adjusted expenses, and Personal Consumption Expenditures Price Index (PCEPI) adjusted expenses. Inflated values are adjusted to fiscal Year 2022 equivalent dollars with an index of 1.00 applied forward to adjust to 2023 and 2024 equivalent expenditures. The NIM database serves as a reference for future research and cost analytics in NASA's system-level analysis of the NIM.

CCS CONCEPTS

• General and reference → Data • Computing methodologies → Modeling and simulation

KEYWORDS

Satellite, Space Mission, Interplanetary Space Mission, Satellite Attributes, Space Mission System Parameters

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1 Introduction

The database consists of a survey of NASA Interplanetary Missions (NIMs) launched between May 1989 and October 2023. Mission data includes system-level attributes in support of advanced system-level modeling. The attributes include elements of the program, schedule, cost, and technical design. Cost silos include three inflation formats: Then\$ representing realized expenses in the Year of recording, NASA's New Start Inflation Index (NSII) adjusted expenses, and Personal Consumption Expenditures Price Index (PCEPI) adjusted expenses. Inflated values are adjusted to fiscal Year 2022 equivalent dollars with an index of 1.00 applied forward to adjust to 2023 and 2024 equivalent expenditures. The

NIM database serves as a reference for future research and cost analytics in NASA's system-level analysis of the Interplanetary Mission.

2 NASA Interplanetary Missions

2.1 Database

The NIM database includes published mission design data for 33 NASA missions and 35 spacecraft. Data sources include published NASA Budget Requests from 1984 through 2024, the NSSDCA database, and other technical references. NASA Budget Requests provide the attributes of proposed mission costs and schedules, as well as an accounting of realized expenses for the two years before the budget request. For example, the NASA Year 2002 Budget Request document includes the Year 2000 realized expenses.

The database's 35 interplanetary missions were launched between 1984 and 2023. For inclusion within the database, the mission achieved Phase E operation status. System risk encompasses attributes such as mission success or failure, budget versus realized cost comparison for total mission cost, design schedule time to launch, and mission operational life.

Between 1961 and 2024, NASA launched seventy-six interplanetary satellite missions. Of those missions, 38 were launched before 1978, and 38 were launched or planned for launch after 1989.

The NIM database elements (missions) include a variety of space mission types and primary destinations:

- Mission Types: Orbiter, Fly By, Lander, Sample Return, Defense Test, Impact, Test Flight
- Primary Mission Destination: Lunar, Venus, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Asteroid, Comet, Solar Wind, Pluto

This database represents a comprehensive, published record of system attributes for NASA interplanetary space missions. NIM construction includes data silos, as shown in Figure 1, which encompass elements of cost, schedule, technical design, and program components. A mission datasheet summarizes the

attributes of each NIM element. This database represents the culmination of dozens of source documents. The appendix presents detailed data for each mission.

2.2 Data Contents

The NIM database includes the data element attributes, organized by component:

Mission Identification

- Mission name (Mission)
- COSPAR ID (COSPAR)
- NASA program (Initiative)
- Destination planet or body (Destination)
- Success – success, failure, operational (Success)
- Type of mission (Type)
- Delivery launch vehicle (Launch Vehicle)

Program Schedule (Plan)

- Proposed design schedule (months) (PDS)
- Proposed mission operation schedule (years) (PMS)
- Realized design schedule (reported) (months) (RDS)
- Realized mission operation schedule (reported) (years) (RMS)
- Calculated design schedule (calculated from dates: [launch – phase A]/30) (months) (CDS)
- Calculated mission operation schedule ([EoM – launch]/365) (years) (CMS)

Milestone Date

- Feasibility – initial concept date (Feasibility)
 - Mission concept review
- Funding – Phase A, selection, contract award (Funding)
 - Authorization to proceed or primary contract award.
- PDR – Phase B (PDR)
 - Preliminary Design Review
- CDR – critical design review/authorization to proceed (CDR)
 - Final/Critical Design Review
- Launch – (Phase D) deployment/launch (Launch)
 - Transport/ Launch Integration/Encapsulation
 - Flight Readiness Review
- Arrival On-station – post-launch and pre-operations (cruise/transfer) (On-Station)
 - Transfer/Operations readiness review.
- Operations – begin science (Science)
- Extend Mission – end of planned science (Extend)
- End-of-Mission – end of science, disposal, loss of contact (EoM)
- Start Year – mission recognized as a budget line item (StartY)
- Launch Year – mission launch Year (LaunchY)

Cost (\$M) (xxCx)

- Then Year \$ - actual budget or realized expenses - reported as \$M in the year that the costs were incurred (xxCT)

- Proposed mission cost – budget request (PMCT)
- Current mission cost – current, latest, or final cost (CMCT)
- Total mission cost – realized for development, launch, and operations (TMCT)
- Total development cost – realized for Phase A through launch (TDCT)
- Total launch cost – realized (TLCT)
- Total planned operations cost – realized for post-launch through extended operations of End-of-Mission if no extension (TOCT)
- Total extended operations cost – realized for extended operations through End-of-Mission (TECT)
- NASA New Start Inflation Index (NSII) adjusted – inflated costs to \$M fiscal Year 2022 value based on the NSII inflation rates (xxCN)
 - Adjusted total mission cost – realized for development, launch, and operations (TMCN)
 - Adjusted total development cost – realized for Phase A through launch (TDCN)
 - Adjusted total launch cost – realized (TLCN)
 - Adjusted total planned operations cost – realized for post-launch through extended operations of End-of-Mission if no extension (TOCN)
 - Adjusted total extended operations cost – realized for extended operations through End-of-Mission (TECN)
- Personal Consumption Expenditures Price Index (PCEPI) adjusted – inflated costs to \$M fiscal Year 2022 value based on the PCEPI inflation rates
 - Adjusted total mission cost – realized for development, launch, and operations (TMCP)
 - Adjusted total development cost – realized for Phase A through launch (TDCP)
 - Adjusted total launch cost – realized (TLCP)
 - Adjusted total planned operations cost – realized for post-launch through extended operations of End-of-Mission if no extension (TOCP)
 - Adjusted total extended operations cost – realized for extended operations through End-of-Mission (TECP)

Technical design – mass (kgs)

- Launch mass of spacecraft (fueled) (kgs) (LM) (LM)
- Fuel load mass (kgs) (Fuel)
- Apogee Kick Motor mass (kgs) (AKM)
- Ballast (kgs) (Ball)
- Spacecraft Dry mass – bus and payload (kgs) (SCdry)
- Space Vehicle bus mass (kgs) (SVbus)
- Space Vehicle payload instrument mass (kgs) (SVpay)
- Probe mass – separated systems/ instruments from the Space Vehicle during operations (kgs) (Probe)

- Cruise stage mass – for lander/rover missions, does not land (kgs) (Cruise)
- Lander mass – for lander/rover missions, re-entry, and landing (kgs) (Lander)
- Aeroshield – for re-entry missions (kgs) (Aero)

Technical design – mission payload

- Objectives – the number of independent objectives listed for the mission (Obj)
- Instruments – the number of discrete instruments within the Space Vehicle payload (Ins)
- Instrument mass – the reported payload mass or sum of instrument component masses (kgs) (InsMass)
- Instrument power – the reported payload average power (assumes duty cycling and mission phase operation) or the sum of instrument component average power (worst case sum) (watts) (InsPwr)

Technical design - spacecraft architecture

- Deployments – the number of independent component deployments (a measure of complexity) (Deploy)
- Bus volume – the volume of the stowed Space Vehicle (cubic meters) (BV)
- Power Source – solar array/Radioactive Thermal Generator (RTG) (SA)
- Solar array type – body, fixed, or articulated, and the number of arrays
- Spacecraft power (watts)
 - BoL power – beginning of life power at 1 Au (watts) (BoLP)
 - BoM power – beginning of mission power reported at-station, aphelion power for non-circularized or transfer orbits (watts) (BoMPwr)
 - BoS power – beginning of science mission power reported on-station, aphelion power for initial science orbit (watts) (BoSPwr)
- Solar array area – the deployed area of the solar array (assuming 90% cell density) or reported solar cell area (meters squared) (SAA)
- Solar array type – quantity of wings and articulation, fixed, or body mounted (SAT)

realization that the mid-1980s represented an engineering revolution specific to the satellite industry. The introduction of workspace computation and associated computer-aided engineering resources, processes, and practices significantly altered the space mission engineering process. Innovation realization encompassed mission-level through component-level design, manufacture, integration, and testing. Technological advances fostered a global shift from design by test and physical-based engineering to an alternative design through analysis and simulation. Computer-based applications made traditional processes faster, more efficient, and repeatable. The collaboration between personal computers and wide area networks (WANs) enabled alternative assessments, process standardization, a deeper understanding, and greater flexibility in evaluating, realizing, and operating space-based missions. Computer-aided design (CAD), computer-aided manufacturing (CAM), and computer-aided analysis (CAA) provided improved abilities to perform complex analytical tasks repeatedly and conveniently, thereby evolving the engineering process.

Figure 1: NIM Data Silos

2.3 Data Pruning

The purpose of the NIM database is to serve as a quality, reliable data source for system-level data in the development and demonstration of artificial intelligence (AI) predictor performance, specifically the Classified Regression (CR) algorithm. Data pruning of the NASA interplanetary mission catalog limited the NIM to post-1989 launched missions. From the 1970s through the mid-1980s, NASA did not invest in interplanetary missions. This absence resulted from funding limitations and prioritized commitments to the International Space Station (ISS) and Space Shuttle programs. The decision to prune the catalog is based on the

2.4 Cost

The accounting practice and reporting details are significant to the cost data collected and represented in the NIM database. The cost elements of the NIM are thorough, consistent, and comprehensive accounts of the full life cycle costs recorded in NASA's annual budget requests. Cost segmentation is consistent with NASA's budget practice for reported costs, which bifurcated at the program phase transitions of development, launch, and operation. For most cost elements, the realized cost report is generated two years after the Year the cost was incurred. When omissions of realized costs

exist or reporting includes summed mission expenditures, the prior proposed allocation provides the basis for the allocation distribution of the reported values.

NASA budget requests submitted to Congress are the source of cost data for the periods 1959–1997 and 2002–present (as of 2024).[4] Each budget document lists expenditures for the two fiscal Years prior and projects budget requests for the four budget Years into the future.

The Planetary Society publishes a list and associated links to each NASA budget document available for download. From 1997 to 2002, NASA budget requests did not include detailed mission-level expenses and request details. Missing data augmentation utilizes the planning and performance reporting from preceding and post-budget requests documents to reconstruct annual expenditures. Supplemental costs from alternative documents, including press kits, program summaries, NASA and JPL document archives, and other historical records, complete the cost data.

The NIM cost data consists of three accounting formats:

- *Then* – \$ Accumulated from the NASA Budget Request documents and alternate references as required. The NASA Budget Requests report expenditure and project requests in Then-Year Dollars (*Then* – \$) for the Year incurred. The *Then* – \$ Records are unadjusted, representing a constant inflation factor of 1.0 for all years.
- The NASA New Start Inflation Index (NSII) is the standard for forward projecting costs in Year-incurred dollars and normalizing prior expenditures to current cost forecasting. [1]
- Personal Consumption Expenditures Price Index (PCEPI) is a commonly utilized inflation index for cost normalization. The Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA) reports the index. The PCEPI is the preferred measure of inflation used by the Federal Reserve. This index is comparable to the Bureau of Labor Statistics' Consumer Price Index for Urban Consumers. [2]

Each index reports an adjusted value for the associated Year. Index normalization resulted in a consistent \$1.00 cost in 2022, in Year Dollars for all indices. Cost projections for 2023 and 2024 expenditures assign an inflation factor of 1.00. In addition to the NSII and PCEPI inflation indices, the assessment included the Consumer Price Index (CPI), the Consumer Price Index Less Food and Energy (CPILFESL), and the Standard & Poor's 500 Index (S&P 500).

Figures 2 and 3 represent the comparison of the inflation indices. Figure 2 illustrates the index performance considering forward pricing from a 1961 baseline for each model (\$1 in 1961 projects to Then-Year dollars to 2022). Figure 3 applies a reverse pricing

model based on \$100 in 2022 and projects back to 1961 for “equivalent dollars” for each model.

Each index exhibits a unique curve. T-tests compare each of the indices’ models for correlation. The results indicate that the NSII is statistically significant compared to the alternative indices. The non-NSII indices are correlated and not statistically significant. The PCEPI index represents all non-NSII indices considered. The NASA NSII represents an outlier to other established inflation indices. Comparatively, the NSII undervalues (1969-2007) and overvalues (2011-present) contributions. Table 1 lists the inflation index value and associated multiplier (Model 2022) by model year.

Figure 2: NSII Comparison with Alternate Inflation Indices (forward priced)

Figure 3: NSII Comparison with Alternate Inflation Indices (reverse priced)

2.5 Schedule

Schedule data includes information gathered from proposed or funding plans, realized activities, launch records, public information releases, and news articles (operational milestones and events). The data includes details and incorporates data consistency among NIM elements. The time of performance, reported in months or years as realized values, relies on reported milestone dates and conversion to attribute consistent reporting norms:

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development in months, launch as a non-time-dependent event, and operations in years.

- The development schedule defines the time difference between the launch date (launch manifests and news releases) and contract initiation/award data (NASA budgets and KDP documents).
- The launch schedule is the launch date.
- Cruise represents the time lapse between the operational status date, from operational plans and news releases, and the launch date.
- Primary operation is the time between mission event dates (failure, planned mission operations, notification/approval of extended operations, or end of life) and operational status date.
- Extended operation is the time between 4/17/2025 (the date established for Version 1.0) or the End of the Mission (press releases) and the notification/approval of the extended operations date (NASA budgets, press releases).

2.6 Technical Design

Technical design data includes mass, power, payload, and mission design details. Industry documentation provided the source for technical data: NASA and JPL archives, press releases, NASA open-source databases and records, Jane’s biannual publications [3], and alternative sources. A rating system from most dependable to least dependable defines the proximity of each source to NASA. The NIM database includes higher-rated source data. The prioritization of sources, from most to least dependable, is as follows: NASA, NASA affiliates, NASA contractors, alternative technical sources, and news sources.

2.7 Program

The program data consists of non-numerical mission information: mission purpose, mission destination, program source, and prime contractor. The non-numerical program data included in the NIM is limited and presented in the Appendix.

Other information included program designation, COSPAR number, mission success and status, failure information, and launch vehicle.

3 NIM Database

The NIM database contents are in Table 2 by section:

- Section 1 – Mission definition - Tables 2a and 2b
- Section 2 – Schedule - Tables 2b through 2d
- Section 3 – Cost - Tables 3e through 3g
- Section 4 – Technical - Tables 2g through 2j

Table 1: Inflation Index Values

Year	NNSI Year	NSSI 2022	CPI	CPI Model 2022	PCEPI	PCEPI 2022	CPI/FESL	CPI/FESL 2022	S&P 500 /I	S&P 500 /I 2022
1959	1959	14.965	29.20	10.024	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	585.18	8.482
1960	1960	14.348	29.60	9.889	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	604.28	8.214
1961	1961	13.903	29.90	9.789	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	611.45	8.118
1962	1962	13.368	30.30	9.660	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	702.46	7.066
1963	1963	12.916	30.60	9.565	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	652.97	7.602
1964	1964	12.360	31.00	9.442	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	754.87	6.575
1965	1965	11.953	31.50	9.292	10.00	7.020	10.00	8.991	842.18	5.894
1966	1966	11.277	32.50	9.006	10.25	6.847	10.25	8.772	895.37	5.544
1967	1967	10.750	33.40	8.763	10.51	6.679	10.60	8.479	783.17	6.338
1968	1968	10.199	34.80	8.411	10.92	6.427	11.10	8.102	850.37	5.837
1969	1969	9.649	36.70	7.975	11.41	6.150	11.74	7.661	874.19	5.678
1970	1970	9.026	38.80	7.544	11.95	5.876	12.47	7.210	728.95	6.809
1971	1971	8.491	40.50	7.227	12.45	5.636	13.05	6.887	716.70	6.926
1972	1972	8.034	41.80	7.002	12.88	5.450	13.45	6.682	766.86	6.473
1973	1973	7.600	44.40	6.592	13.57	5.172	13.92	6.458	848.00	5.853
1974	1974	7.090	49.30	5.937	14.99	4.684	15.08	5.963	629.27	7.888
1975	1975	6.399	53.80	5.441	16.24	4.324	16.47	5.459	424.93	11.681
1976	1976	5.870	56.90	5.144	17.13	4.099	17.55	5.123	531.53	9.338
1977	1976 TQ	5.750	60.60	4.830	18.24	3.849	18.65	4.822	541.37	9.169
1978	1977	5.299	65.20	4.489	19.51	3.598	20.00	4.495	440.58	11.266
1979	1978	4.916	72.60	4.032	21.24	3.305	21.95	4.096	445.42	11.144
1980	1979	4.489	82.40	3.552	23.53	2.983	24.68	3.643	434.92	11.413
1981	1980	4.055	90.90	3.220	25.64	2.738	27.27	3.297	466.43	10.642
1982	1981	3.683	96.50	3.033	27.06	2.594	29.28	3.070	379.53	13.078
1983	1982	3.417	99.60	2.939	28.21	2.488	30.43	2.955	450.18	11.026
1984	1983	3.211	103.90	2.817	29.28	2.398	31.99	2.811	498.23	9.963
1985	1984	3.047	107.60	2.720	30.30	2.317	33.39	2.693	496.27	10.002
1986	1985	2.947	109.60	2.671	30.96	2.267	34.74	2.588	579.60	8.564
1987	1986	2.861	113.60	2.577	31.91	2.200	36.10	2.490	725.73	6.839
1988	1987	2.748	118.30	2.474	33.16	2.117	37.71	2.384	660.59	7.514
1989	1988	2.610	124.00	2.360	34.61	2.028	39.40	2.282	719.06	6.903
1990	1989	2.490	130.70	2.239	36.13	1.943	41.38	2.173	814.19	6.096
1991	1990	2.383	136.20	2.149	37.34	1.880	43.42	2.071	737.82	6.727
1992	1991	2.300	140.30	2.086	38.33	1.831	45.01	1.998	919.26	5.400
1993	1992	2.187	144.50	2.026	39.29	1.787	46.50	1.934	931.22	5.330
1994	1993	2.098	148.20	1.975	40.11	1.750	47.81	1.881	987.10	5.028
1995	1994	2.035	152.40	1.921	40.95	1.714	49.25	1.825	944.46	5.256
1996	1995	1.984	156.90	1.866	41.83	1.678	50.58	1.778	1214.15	4.088
1997	1996	1.935	160.50	1.824	42.55	1.650	51.78	1.736	1469.39	3.378
1998	1997	1.909	163.00	1.796	42.89	1.637	52.97	1.697	1818.87	2.729
1999	1998	1.862	166.60	1.757	43.52	1.613	54.07	1.663	2319.00	2.140
2000	1999	1.818	172.20	1.700	44.62	1.573	55.38	1.623	2576.78	1.926
2001	2000	1.747	177.10	1.653	45.51	1.542	56.86	1.581	2327.31	2.133
2002	2001	1.686	179.90	1.627	46.11	1.522	58.18	1.545	1964.36	2.527
2003	2002	1.640	184.00	1.591	47.08	1.491	59.03	1.523	1504.29	3.300
2004	2003	1.605	188.90	1.549	48.25	1.455	60.07	1.497	1865.78	2.660
2005	2004	1.552	195.30	1.499	49.64	1.414	61.36	1.465	1890.19	2.626
2006	2005	1.505	201.60	1.452	51.04	1.375	62.91	1.429	1967.48	2.523
2007	2006	1.459	207.30	1.412	52.34	1.341	64.38	1.397	2146.69	2.312
2008	2007	1.405	215.30	1.359	53.89	1.303	65.85	1.365	1992.95	2.491
2009	2008	1.357	214.50	1.365	53.74	1.306	66.98	1.342	1250.79	3.968
2010	2009	1.332	218.10	1.342	54.71	1.283	67.62	1.330	1582.07	3.137
2011	2010	1.314	224.90	1.301	56.09	1.252	68.74	1.308	1777.01	2.793
2012	2011	1.293	229.60	1.275	57.14	1.229	70.19	1.281	1750.68	2.835
2013	2012	1.279	233.00	1.256	57.91	1.212	71.43	1.259	1961.45	2.531
2014	2013	1.260	236.70	1.237	58.79	1.194	72.68	1.237	2377.00	2.088
2015	2014	1.236	237.00	1.235	58.92	1.191	74.01	1.215	2647.83	1.875
2016	2015	1.211	240.00	1.220	59.51	1.180	75.64	1.189	2470.84	2.009
2017	2016	1.197	245.10	1.194	60.59	1.158	77.03	1.167	2858.52	1.736
2018	2017	1.172	251.10	1.166	61.89	1.134	78.68	1.143	3434.07	1.445
2019	2018	1.143	255.70	1.145	62.81	1.118	80.41	1.118	3160.51	1.571
2020	2019	1.121	258.80	1.131	63.50	1.105	81.78	1.099	3877.22	1.280
2021	2020	1.097	271.00	1.080	66.06	1.063	84.70	1.061	4425.02	1.122
2022	2021	1.057	292.70	1.000	70.20	1.000	89.91	1.000	4963.62	1.000

Table 2a: NIM Database (Section 1 – Mission Definition)

Mission	COSPAR	Initiative	Destination	Success	Type	Launch Vehicle
2001 Mars Odyssey	2001-013A	Mars Surveyor	Mars	Operational	Orbiter	Delta 7925
Cassini	1997-061A	na	Saturn	Success	Orbiter	Titan 4
Contour	2002-034A	Discovery 6	Comet	Failure - LV	Flyby	Delta 7425
Dart	2021-110A	Planetary Def	Asteroid	Success	Impact	Falcon 9
Dawn	2007-043A	Discovery 9	Asteroid	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7925
Deep Impact	2005-001A	Discovery 8	Comet	Success	Rendezvous	Delta 7925
Deep Space 1	1998-061A	New Millennium	Comet	Success	Flyby	Delta 7326
Galileo	1989-084B	na	Jupiter	Success	Orbiter	STS 34
Genesis	2001-034A	Discovery 5	L1	Success	Sample Return	Delta 7326
Grail-A	2011-046A	Discovery 11A	Lunar	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7920
Grail-B	2011-046B	Discovery 11B	Lunar	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7920
Insight	2018-042A	Discovery 12	Mars	Success	Lander	Atlas 5
Juno	2011-040A	New Frontiers 2	Jupiter	Success	Orbiter	Atlas 5
Ladee	2013-047A	na	Lunar	Success	Orbiter	Minotaur V
Lucy	2021-093A	Discovery 13	Jupiter	Operational	Flyby	Atlas 5
Lunar Prospector	1998-001A	Discovery 3	Lunar	Success	Orbiter	Athena 2
M2020 - Perseverance	2020-052A	na	Mars	Operational	Rover	Atlas 5
Magellan	1989-033B	na	Venus	Success	Orbiter	STS
Mars Climate Orbiter	1998-073A	MPLMCO 1 of 2	Mars	Failure	Orbiter	Delta 7425
Mars Global Surveyor	1996-062A	na	Mars	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7925
Mars Observer	1992-063A	na	Mars	Failure	Orbiter	Titan 3
Mars Pathfinder	1996-068A	Discovery 2	Mars	Success	Rover	Delta 7925
Mars Polar Lander	1999-001A	MPLMCO 2 of 2	Mars	Failure	Lander	Delta 7425
Mars Recon Orbiter	2005-029A	na	Mars	Success	Orbiter	Atlas 5
MAVEN	2013-063A	Scout 2	Mars	Operational	Orbiter	Atlas 5
MERA - Spirit	2003-027A	na	Mars	Success	Rover	Delta 7925
MERB - Opportunity	2003-032A	na	Mars	Success	Rover	Delta 7925H
Messenger	2004-030A	Discovery 7	Mercury	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7925
MSL - Curiosity	2011-070A	Flagship	Mars	Operational	Rover	Atlas 5
NEAR Shoemaker	1996-008A	Discovery 1	Asteroid	Success	Orbiter	Delta 7925
New Horizons	2006-001A	New Frontiers 1	Pluto	Operational	Flyby	Atlas 5
Osiris-Rex	2016-055A	New Frontiers 3	Asteroid	Operational	Sample Return	Atlas 5
Phoenix	2007-034A	Scout 1	Mars	Success	Lander	Delta 7925
Psyche	2023-157A	Discovery 14	Asteroid Belt	Operational	Orbiter	Falcon Heavy
Stardust	1999-003A	Discovery 4	Comet	Success	Sample Return	Delta 7426

Table 2c: NIM Database (Section 2 – Schedule Part 2)

Mission	Feasibility	Funding	PDR	CDR	Launch	On-Station
2001 Mars Odyssey	2/1/1997	11/6/1997	10/1/1998	4/1/1999	4/7/2001	10/24/2001
Cassini	9/1/1990	6/1/1991	6/1/1994	8/1/1995	10/15/1997	7/1/2004
Contour	10/1/1997	2/1/1999	1/20/2000	12/1/2000	7/3/2002	7/3/2002
Dart	9/1/2016	3/1/2017	4/1/2018	4/1/2019	11/24/2021	9/26/2022
Dawn	na	9/1/2002	10/1/2003	5/1/2004	9/27/2007	7/16/2011
Deep Impact	7/1/1999	5/1/2000	3/1/2001	1/1/2002	1/12/2005	7/4/2005
Deep Space 1	na	10/1/1995	na	na	10/24/1998	7/29/1999
Galileo	na	10/1/1977	na	na	10/18/1989	12/8/1995
Genesis	10/20/1997	12/1/1997	7/1/1998	7/1/1999	8/5/2001	11/16/2001
Grail-A	10/30/2006	1/15/2008	11/11/2008	11/12/2009	9/10/2011	12/11/2011
Grail-B	10/30/2006	1/15/2008	11/11/2008	11/12/2009	9/10/2011	12/11/2011
Insight	na	8/1/2012	8/1/2013	5/1/2014	5/5/2018	11/26/2018
Juno	7/1/2004	5/1/2005	5/1/2008	4/1/2009	5/8/2011	7/6/2016
Ladee	3/1/2008	4/1/2008	8/23/2010	5/20/2011	9/7/2013	10/6/2013
Lucy	9/15/2015	1/4/2017	10/20/2018	10/21/2019	10/16/2021	4/20/2025
Lunar Prospector	2/28/1995	2/28/1995	4/1/1995	10/1/1995	1/6/1998	1/11/1998
M2020 - Perseverance	8/7/2013	11/1/2014	2/3/2016	3/1/2017	7/20/2020	2/18/2021
Magellan	1/1/1984	1/1/1984	na	na	5/4/1989	8/10/1990
Mars Climate Orbiter	4/1/1994	11/1/1995	3/1/1996	1/1/1997	12/11/1998	9/23/1999
Mars Global Surveyor	2/1/1994	10/1/1994	na	2/1/1996	11/7/1996	9/12/1997
Mars Observer	10/1/1984	9/1/1988	9/1/1988	10/1/1990	9/25/1992	8/21/1993
Mars Pathfinder	10/1/1993	10/1/1993	12/1/1993	9/1/1994	12/4/1996	7/4/1997
Mars Polar Lander	2/7/1994	3/17/1995	na	1/4/1997	1/3/1999	12/3/1999
Mars Recon Orbiter	11/1/2000	10/3/2001	7/1/2002	7/1/2003	8/12/2005	3/10/2006
MAVEN	1/1/2007	9/15/2008	7/1/2010	7/15/2011	11/18/2013	9/22/2014
MERA - Spirit	5/1/2000	5/1/2000	2/1/2001	12/11/2001	6/10/2003	1/4/2004
MERB - Opportunity	5/1/2000	5/1/2000	2/1/2001	12/11/2001	7/8/2003	1/21/2004
Messenger	3/1/1996	1/1/2000	5/24/2001	3/22/2002	8/3/2004	3/18/2011
MSL - Curiosity	10/28/2003	12/1/2005	6/20/2006	6/1/2007	11/26/2011	7/6/2012
NEAR Shoemaker	11/1/1993	1/1/1994	4/1/1994	11/1/1994	2/17/1996	2/14/2000
New Horizons	6/1/2001	11/29/2001	3/1/2003	10/1/2003	1/19/2006	7/14/2015
Osiris-Rex	5/11/2024	5/1/2012	3/1/2013	4/1/2014	9/8/2016	12/3/2018
Phoenix	5/16/2003	8/4/2003	2/1/2005	9/1/2005	8/4/2007	5/25/2008
Psyche	6/1/2017	5/1/2018	3/1/2019	4/20/2024	10/13/2023	8/1/2029
Stardust	1/1/1996	10/1/1996	9/1/1996	6/1/1997	2/7/1999	1/2/2004

Table 2b: NIM Database (Section 2 – Schedule Part 1)

Mission	Launch Vehicle	PDS	PMS	RDS	CDS	RMS	CMS
2001 Mars Odyssey	Delta 7925	40.0	2.51	41.0	41.6	24.04	23.50
Cassini	Titan 4	67.0	11.00	85.0	77.6	19.93	13.22
Contour	Delta 7425	34.0	6.00	35.0	41.6	0	0.00
Dart	Falcon 9	50.0	0.92	56.0	57.6	0.84	0.00
Dawn	Delta 7925	44.0	10.17	60.0	61.7	11.10	7.30
Deep Impact	Delta 7925	39.0	1.58	50.0	57.2	8.58	8.11
Deep Space 1	Delta 7326	39.0	0.92	39.0	37.3	3.15	2.39
Galileo	STS 34	51.0	8.08	125.0	146.7	13.93	7.79
Genesis	Delta 7326	37.0	2.58	46.0	44.8	3.10	2.81
Grail-A	Delta 7920	44.0	0.74	46.0	44.5	1.27	1.02
Grail-B	Delta 7920	44.0	0.74	46.0	44.5	1.27	1.02
Insight	Atlas 5	43.0	1.99	69.0	70.1	4.62	4.05
Juno	Atlas 5	46.0	6.00	72.0	73.3	13.95	8.79
Ladee	Minotaur V	56.0	0.44	68.0	66.2	0.61	0.53
Lucy	Atlas 5	58.0	11.50	58.0	58.2	3.50	-0.01
Lunar Prospector	Athena 2	30.0	1.00	34.0	34.8	1.56	1.55
M2020 - Perseverance	Atlas 5	68.0	1.88	68.0	69.6	4.75	4.16
Magellan	STS	52.0	1.00	60.0	65.0	5.44	4.18
Mars Climate Orbiter	Delta 7425	37.0	2.13	37.0	37.9	0.78	0.00
Mars Global Surveyor	Delta 7925	26.0	5.72	25.0	25.6	9.99	9.15
Mars Observer	Titan 3	60.0	3.40	60.0	49.5	0.90	0.00
Mars Pathfinder	Delta 7925	36.0	0.58	38.0	38.7	0.81	0.23
Mars Polar Lander	Delta 7425	46.0	1.17	46.0	46.3	0.92	0.00
Mars Recon Orbiter	Atlas 5	45.0	5.40	46.0	47.0	18.61	18.03
MAVEN	Atlas 5	62.0	9.00	62.0	63.0	10.33	9.49
MERA - Spirit	Delta 7925	34.0	0.25	34.0	37.8	6.79	6.22
MERB - Opportunity	Delta 7925H	34.0	0.25	35.0	38.8	14.93	14.39
Messenger	Delta 7925	51.0	8.00	57.0	55.9	10.75	4.12
MSL - Curiosity	Atlas 5	46.0	2.51	71.0	72.9	12.32	11.70
NEAR Shoemaker	Delta 7925	27.0	1.00	25.5	25.9	5.04	1.04
New Horizons	Atlas 5	na	15.00	na	50.4	18.17	8.68
Osiris-Rex	Atlas 5	52.0	7.00	52.0	53.0	7.53	5.29
Phoenix	Delta 7925	43.0	1.17	43.0	48.7	1.29	0.48
Psyche	Falcon Heavy	48.0	7.42	61.0	66.4	0.43	0.38
Stardust	Delta 7426	37.0	7.00	37.0	28.6	12.13	7.23

Table 2d: NIM Database (Section 2 – Schedule Part 3)

Mission	Science	Extend	EoM	StartY	LaunchY
2001 Mars Odyssey	2/19/2002	8/24/2004	4/17/2025	1998	2001
Cassini	7/1/2004	7/1/2008	9/15/2017	1985	1992
Contour	7/3/2002	7/3/2002	7/3/2002	1998	2002
Dart	9/26/2022	9/26/2022	9/26/2022	2016	2021
Dawn	na	6/1/2016	11/1/2018	2002	2007
Deep Impact	7/4/2005	7/4/2005	8/11/2013	1999	2005
Deep Space 1	na	9/18/1999	12/18/2001	1996	1998
Galileo	na	12/1/1997	9/21/2003	1978	1989
Genesis	12/5/2001	9/8/2004	9/8/2004	1997	2001
Grail-A	3/7/2012	5/29/2012	12/17/2012	2007	2011
Grail-B	3/7/2012	5/29/2012	12/17/2012	2007	2011
Insight	11/26/2018	11/24/2020	12/15/2022	2011	2018
Juno	7/6/2016	6/30/2017	4/17/2025	2001	2006
Ladee	11/21/2013	3/1/2014	4/18/2014	2008	2013
Lucy	10/16/2027	10/16/2033	4/17/2025	2016	2021
Lunar Prospector	1/15/1998	1/1/1999	7/31/1999	1996	1998
M2020 - Perseverance	2/18/2021	1/6/2023	4/17/2025	2013	2020
Magellan	9/15/1990	5/16/1991	10/12/1994	1984	1989
Mars Climate Orbiter	9/23/1999	9/23/1999	9/23/1999	1996	1999
Mars Global Surveyor	9/23/1998	2/1/2002	11/2/2006	1994	1996
Mars Observer	8/21/1993	8/21/1993	8/21/1993	1985	1992
Mars Pathfinder	na	8/4/1997	9/27/1997	1993	1996
Mars Polar Lander	12/3/1999	12/3/1999	12/3/1999	1996	1999
Mars Recon Orbiter	9/1/2006	12/10/2010	3/17/2024	1996	1999
MAVEN	10/1/2015	1/1/2020	3/17/2024	2007	2013
MERA - Spirit	4/3/2004	4/3/2004	3/22/2010	2000	2003
MERB - Opportunity	4/20/2004	4/20/2004	6/10/2018	2000	2003
Messenger	4/4/2011	3/1/2012	4/30/2015	1999	2004
MSL - Curiosity	8/22/2012	7/10/2014	3/17/2024	2002	2011
NEAR Shoemaker	2/14/2000	2/12/2001	2/28/2001	1994	1996
New Horizons	7/14/2015	3/1/2017	3/17/2024	2001	2006
Osiris-Rex	10/10/2020	9/24/2023	3/17/2024	2011	2016
Phoenix	5/26/2008	8/24/2008	11/16/2008	2003	2007
Psyche	8/1/2029	6/1/2031	3/17/2024	2016	2023
Stardust	1/15/2004	2/14/2011	3/24/2011	1996	1999

Table 2e: NIM Database (Section 3 – Cost Part 1)

Mission	PMCT	CMCT	PBDS	FBDS	TMCT	TDCT	TLCT	TOCT
2001 Mars Odyssey	267.2	366.1	33	34	680.2	366.2	53.9	48.5
Cassini	1436.4	1375.9	92	110	3206.8	1408.5	398.4	678
Contour	69.1	96.8	38	40	145.8	96.8	49	0
Dart	219	258.3	31	43	332	240.6	68.8	22.6
Dawn	202.8	287.1	37	53	505.6	282.9	91.3	108
Deep Impact	194.1	252	44	63	352.5	230.9	57.6	15
Deep Space 1	73.3	99.3	33	43	180.6	114.2	45.4	7.3
Galileo	410.099	1639	43	136	1783.1	902.3	323.9	468.5
Genesis	126.1	162.9	32	46	264	163	48.7	52.3
Grail-A	213.5	224.35	44	44	243.65	147.95	76.4	9.65
Grail-B	213.5	224.35	44	44	243.65	147.95	76.4	9.65
Insight	425	633.1	na	na	822.8	596.4	163.4	36.7
Juno	700	1114.1	51	51	1304.5	726.2	190.4	167.8
Ladée	262.9	279.2	26	38	279.2	204.3	58.7	11
Lucy	990	999.2	57	57	999.2	523.1	149.4	326.7
Lunar Prospector	61.3	61.7	30	34	63.9	30.6	26	5.1
M2020 - Perseverance	2351	2715.6	68	69	2890.6	2232.2	230.4	253
Magellan	294.6	698.2	52	64	864.8	463.2	235	93.7
Mars Climate Orbiter	183.6	183.25	39	39	147.95	94.5	45.3	8.15
Mars Global Surveyor	140.2	130.7	31	34	303	130.7	52.6	74.9
Mars Observer	458.6	511.2	60	60	825.5	511.2	293.1	21.2
Mars Pathfinder	150	174.2	38	49	258.8	199.2	47.1	10.2
Mars Polar Lander	2351	183.25	na	na	147.95	94.5	45.3	8.15
Mars Recon Orbiter	334.4	450	43	47	1072.2	419.2	90	169.5
MAVEN	567.2	551.1	62	62	771.2	382.4	168.7	26.4
MERA - Spirit	328.6	399	34	34	483.3	321.5	50.6	26.9
MERB - Opportunity	328.6	399	34	34	595.6	321.5	50.6	26.9
Messenger	326.2	390	46	57	457.8	216.2	69	104.8
MSL - Curiosity	1068.5	2337.1	45	70	3046	2142.4	194.7	176.9
NEAR Shoemaker	249.4	230.8	29	29	230.8	124.9	44	61.9
New Horizons	594.9	781.4	44	44	889.7	347.7	218	215.7
Osiris-Rex	865.9	775.1	52	52	1125.3	591.6	183.5	246.9
Phoenix	325	412.8	41	41	417	318.2	86.2	8.4
Psyche	925	1108.1	48	61	1108.1	844.5	112.7	150.9
Stardust	117.8	126.4	35	39	236.4	126.4	40.8	32.1

Table 2g: NIM Database (Section 3 – Cost Part 3/Technical Part 1)

Mission	TLOP	TOCP	TEOP	LM	Fuel	AKM	Ball	SDry
2001 Mars Odyssey	86.3	72.1	249.7	758	348.7	na	33	376.3
Cassini	678.7	1021.5	894.5	5712	3132	na	na	2581
Contour	75.9	0	na	775	70	377	na	328
Dart	74.6	22.7	na	610	86.5	na	na	560
Dawn	125.7	133.3	27.1	1217.7	470.6	na	na	747.1
Deep Impact	86.8	21.4	64	1020	na	na	na	1042
Deep Space 1	74.7	11.7	21.5	486.3	112.6	na	na	373.7
Galileo	716.8	826.2	136.8	2380	925	na	166	1289
Genesis	78.1	76.3	na	636	142	na	na	494
Grail-A	97.8	11.8	11.8	306	108	na	na	198
Grail-B	97.8	11.8	11.8	306	108	na	na	198
Insight	192	40.9	27.2	721	67	na	46	608
Juno	243.8	200.2	206.1	3625	2032	na	na	1593
Ladée	71.6	13.3	6.2	375.5	134.8	na	na	240.7
Lucy	163.6	326.7	na	1550	729	na	na	821
Lunar Prospector	43.4	8.4	3.5	296.4	137.7	na	na	158.7
M2020 - Perseverance	257.8	263	165	3839	1400	na	na	na
Magellan	501.1	181.6	132.7	3449	22414	na	na	1035
Mars Climate Orbiter	74.6	13.05	na	629	291	na	na	338
Mars Global Surveyor	88.9	119.6	65.6	1030.5	360.5	na	3.7	666.3
Mars Observer	576.2	38.6	na	2573	1346	na	199	1028
Mars Pathfinder	80.5	16.8	3.8	895	100	na	248	na
Mars Polar Lander	74.6	13.05	na	583	64	na	na	na
Mars Recon Orbiter	129.1	226.2	448.2	2180	1149	na	0	1031
MAVEN	207.3	31.5	186.8	2454	1645	na	na	809
MERA - Spirit	77.5	39	114.3	1063	45	na	na	na
MERB - Opportunity	77.5	39	248.2	1063	45	na	na	na
Messenger	104.2	137	82	1108	607.8	na	na	485.2
MSL - Curiosity	244.1	215.1	589.8	3839	539	na	na	3300
NEAR Shoemaker	76.2	98.8	na	818	318	na	na	487
New Horizons	357.1	309.8	132.1	585	77	na	na	508
Osiris-Rex	217.6	269.4	103.3	1955	1095	na	na	860
Phoenix	117.1	11	5.5	664	67	na	na	na
Psyche	112.7	150.9	na	2800	1064	na	na	1400
Stardust	66.9	48.2	48.4	385	85	na	na	300

Table 2f: NIM Database (Section 3 – Cost Part 2)

Mission	TECT	TMCN	TDCN	TLCN	TOCN	TECN	TMP	TDGP
2001 Mars Odyssey	211.6	1116.2	677	99.7	78.8	260.7	994.4	586.3
Cassini	721.9	5916.8	3019.5	809.3	1149.4	938.6	5079.8	2484.1
Contour	na	258.1	172	86.1	0	na	226.7	150.8
Dart	na	374.8	274.8	76.3	23.7	na	365.2	267.9
Dawn	23.4	749.7	444.7	137.4	139.7	27.9	690.7	404.6
Deep Impact	49	578.3	390.5	96.1	23.5	68.2	521.6	349.4
Deep Space 1	13.7	346.6	221.2	87.3	13.5	24.6	296.6	188.7
Galileo	88.4	5323.7	3218.2	946	1005.1	154.4	3983.5	2303.7
Genesis	475.2	300.5	90.4	84.3	na	414.4	260	
Grail-A	9.65	327.2	200.4	101.95	12.4	12.4	312.25	190.85
Grail-B	9.65	327.2	200.4	101.95	12.4	12.4	312.25	190.85
Insight	26.3	1015.1	745.8	199.3	41.6	28.4	973	712.9
Juno	220.1	1669.8	995.9	254.1	208	211.8	1594	943.9
Ladée	5.2	365.8	269.8	75.5	14	6.5	348.7	257.6
Lucy	na	1089.6	594.1	167.4	328.1	na	1069.5	579.2
Lunar Prospector	2.2	125.2	60.2	51.1	9.8	4.1	106.3	51
M2020 - Perseverance	165	3338.1	2635.5	263.9	273.7	165	3244.5	2558.7
Magellan	72.9	2390.8	1343.8	649.8	232	165.2	1845.6	1030.2
Mars Climate Orbiter	na	285.6	183.25	87.3	15.05	na	243.85	156.2
Mars Global Surveyor	44.8	579.6	263.9	105.2	138.2	72.3	496.6	222.5
Mars Observer	na	2092.7	1309.3	736.2	47.2	na	1636	1021.2
Mars Pathfinder	2.3	527.6	407.8	95.7	19.7	4.4	443.6	342.5
Mars Polar Lander	na	285.6	183.25	87.3	15.05	na	243.85	156.2
Mars Recon Orbiter	393.5	1531.4	681.6	142.1	243.8	463.9	1421.6	618.1
MAVEN	193.7	942.5	499.5	218.1	33	191.9	901.2	475.6
MERA - Spirit	84.3	800.5	547.2	86.8	43	123.5	720.7	489.9
MERB - Opportunity	196.6	940.1	547.2	86.8	43	263.1	854.6	489.9
Messenger	67.8	710.3	363.3	115.2	145.7	86.1	649.6	326.4
MSL - Curiosity	532	4197.7	3068.5	255.7	266.7	606.8	3902.8	2853.8
NEAR Shoemaker	na	462.8	257.9	90.9	114	na	391.2	216.2
New Horizons	108.3	1472.6	676.2	416.8	241.7	137.9	1375.3	576.3
Osiris-Rex	103.3	1350.7	747.5	224.5	275.4	103.3	1302.5	712.2
Phoenix	4.2	630.1	484.8	127.7	11.8	5.8	576.4	442.8
Psyche	na	1202.7	935.9	115.9	150.9	na	1176.1	912.5
Stardust	37.1	427.6	244	78	54	51.6	371.8	208.3

Table 2h: NIM Database (Section 4 – Technical Part 2)

Mission	SVbus	Svpay	Probe	Cruise	Lander	Aero	Obj	Ins
2001 Mars Odyssey	331.8	44.5	na	na	na	na	6	3
Cassini	2150	343	348	na	na	na	8	12
Contour	267.6	60.4	na	na	na	na	6	4
Dart	500	23.5	na	na	na	na	4	1
Dawn	700.7	46.4	na	na	na	na	5	3
Deep Impact	580	90	372	na	na	na	4	3
Deep Space 1	355.5	18.2	na	na	na	na	4	3
Galileo	1180	84.07	339	na	na	na	9	12
Genesis	289	12.26	192.74	na	na	na	4	3
Grail-A	132.6	65.4	na	na	na	na	6	2
Grail-B	132.6	65.4	na	na	na	na	6	2
Insight	na	48.3	60	79	309.7	189	5	3
Juno	1438.14	154.86	na	na	na	na	5	10
Ladée	191.1	49.7	na	na	na	na	4	4
Lucy	759.34	61.66	na	na	na	na	4	4
Lunar Prospector	135	23.7	na	na	na	na	6	5
M2020 - Perseverance	na	1052	na	539	575	440	5	8
Magellan	na	15.2	na	na	na	na	4	1
Mars Climate Orbiter	294	44	na	na	na	na	6	2
Mars Global Surveyor	590	76.3	na	na	na	na	8	6
Mars Observer	862	139.9	na	na	na	na	6	8
Mars Pathfinder	na	16	154	218	159	4	6	3
Mars Polar Lander	na	7	na	82	290	140	5	3
Mars Recon Orbiter	892	139	na	na	na	na	5	7
MAVEN	737.5	71.5	na	na	na	na	5	8
MERA - Spirit	na	190	na	193	348	287	7	7
MERB - Opportunity	na	190	na	193	348	287	7	7
Messenger	442.8	42.4	na	na	na	na	6	7
MSL - Curiosity	3032	899	na	536	2016	480	8	10
NEAR Shoemaker	430	56.25	na	na	na	na	3	6
New Horizons	478	30	na	na	na	na	8	7
Osiris-Rex	750	110	na	na	na	na	5	6
Phoenix	na	59	na	82	284	172	4	6
Psyche	1330	70	na	na	na	na	5	3
Stardust	254	24	0	na	na	na	3	5

Table 2i: NIM Database (Section 4 – Technical Part 3)

Mission	InsMass	InsPwr	Deploy	BV	SA	BoLP	BoMPwr	BoSPwr
2001 Mars Odyssey	44.5	58	2	9.7	SA	1500	na	750
Cassini	236	228	4	85.4	RTG	900	na	630
Contour	60.4	100	0	5.7	SA	670	na	na
Dart	14	5	1	8.9	SA	6600	na	na
Dawn	46.4	95	3	3.59	SA	10300	1300	na
Deep Impact	90	92	2	12.5	SA	750	620	na
Deep Space 1	18.2	21.9	2	8.9	SA	2500	na	na
Galileo	112.1	87.4	4	112.1	RTG	570	493	410
Genesis	12.26	9.5	4	9.2	SA	265	na	na
Grail-A	65	191.2	2	1	SA	700	na	na
Grail-B	65	191.2	2	1	SA	700	na	na
Insight	48.3	118	3	2.06	SA	1800	700	600
Juno	154.86	124.4	4	33.65	SA	14000	500	400
Ladée	49.7	195	0	7.69	SA	295	295	260
Lucy	61.66	70	3	11.0	SA	26400	na	504
Lunar Prospector	23.7	17	3	1.7	SA	200	186	na
M2020 - Perseverance	50.675	435.7	5	17.82	RTG	110	na	na
Magellan	15.2	210	2	106	SA	625	1200	na
Mars Climate Orbiter	44	45	1	6.72	SA	1000	500	na
Mars Global Surveyor	76.3	76.6	4	2.32	SA	1980	940	660
Mars Observer	139.9	107.7	4	3.46	SA	3400	1408	1147
Mars Pathfinder	23	4.5	4	0.0936	SA	30	16	na
Mars Polar Lander	290	25	4	11.9	SA	672	336	200
Mars Recon Orbiter	139	189	3	9.68	SA	6000	3000	2000
MAVEN	71.5	90	3	10.58	SA	3400	1700	1135
MERA - Spirit	190	20	3	5.52	SA	300	140	na
MERB - Opportunity	190	20	3	5.52	SA	300	140	na
Messenger	42.4	67.5	3	3.28	SA	370	450	na
MSL - Curiosity	899	125	7	17.82	RTG	125	125	na
NEAR Shoemaker	56.25	53.1	4	1.7	SA	1800	400	na
New Horizons	30.4	28.2	0	1.96	RTG	240	200	176
Osiris-Rex	110	121.6	3	26.112	SA	3000	1226	na
Phoenix	59	53	3	1.75	SA	600	334	na
Psyche	70	46.2	4	25.87	SA	19200	2400	na
Stardust	24.16	34.8	5	0.7	SA	800	170	na

Table 2j: NIM Database (Section 4 - Technical Part 4)

Mission	SA	SAT
2001 Mars Odyssey	7.4	2-axis Gimbal
Cassini	na	na
Contour	12.81	Body
Dart	22	Roll Out
Dawn	36.4	2 articulated
Deep Impact	7.2	Fixed
Deep Space 1	14.4	2 articulated
Galileo	na	na
Genesis	3.4	2 fixed
Grail-A	7.2	Fixed
Grail-B	7.2	Fixed
Insight	6.3	Fixed
Juno	60.4	3-articulated
Ladée	7.103	Body
Lucy	83.66	2 fixed
Lunar Prospector	5.2	body
M2020 - Perseverance	na	na
Magellan	12.6	2 articulated
Mars Climate Orbiter	11	2-axis Gimbal
Mars Global Surveyor	13.3	2 articulated
Mars Observer	25.9	2-axis Gimbal
Mars Pathfinder	0.22	body
Mars Polar Lander	2.9	body
Mars Recon Orbiter	20	2 articulated
MAVEN	12	2 fixed
MERA - Spirit	1.51	2 fixed
MERB - Opportunity	1.51	2 fixed
Messenger	5.0	2 articulated
MSL - Curiosity	na	na
NEAR Shoemaker	8.64	4 fixed
New Horizons	na	na
Osiris-Rex	8.5	2 fixed
Phoenix	4.16	2 fixed
Psyche	75	2 articulated
Stardust	6.6	Fixed

Appendix Contents

The data used to populate Table 2 in the Appendix is by mission.

The Appendix includes an alphabetical listing of NIM: summary, details, NASA budget cost references, and a list of references for each element mission.

References – General to All Missions 9

NASA Interplanetary Mission (NIM) Database 9

 2001 Mars Odyssey 9

 Cassini 10

 Contour 14

 Dart (Double Asteroid Redirection Test) 16

 Dawn 17

 Deep Impact 19

 Deep Space 1 20

 Galileo 22

 Genesis 24

 Grail – A/B 26

 Insight 28

 Juno 30

 Ladée 32

 Lucy 34

 Lunar Prospector 35

 Mars 2020 (Perseverance) 37

 Magellan 39

 Mars Climate Orbiter 42

 Mars Exploration Rovers 43

 Mars Global Surveyor 46

 Mars Observer 48

 Mars Pathfinder 50

 Mars Polar Lander 52

 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 54

 Mars Science Laboratory 56

 Maven 60

 Messenger 61

 Near 63

 New Horizons 64

 Osiris Rex 66

 Phoenix 68

 Psyche 70

 Stardust 71

Data Dictionary 74

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The author would like to thank those responsible at **The Planetary Society** for their efforts with *The Planetary Exploration Budget Database*. Their cost data provided a valuable cross-reference for the information collected and the data in this database. The Planetary Society archives provided comprehensive and unrestricted access to NASA budget documentation from 1961 through 2024. This resource was crucial to the cost collection effort.

Main page link: <https://www.planetary.org/>
 Database link: <https://www.planetary.org/space-policy/planetary-exploration-budget-database>
 Budget link: <https://www.planetary.org/space-policy/every-nasa-budget-request>
 Support Membership link: <https://www.planetary.org/membership?level=Visionary&src=homejoin>

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[3] Bond, Peter R. (2011) *Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012, 27th ed.* Jane’s Information Group, Alexandria, Va.

[4] The Planet Society. Every NASA Budget Request, from 1961 to Now. <https://www.planetary.org/space-policy/every-nasa-budget-request> .

Appendix Missions

2001 Mars Odyssey

Mission Attributes		2001 Mars Odyssey	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition		Cost	
COSPAR	2001-013A	Start	1998
Program	Mars Surveyor	Launch	2001
Destination	Mars	Budget \$	267.2
Success	Operational	Realized \$	366.1
Type	Orbiter	Budget Schedule	33
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925	Realized Schedule	34
Schedule		Then \$	\$ 680.20
Initial Design Duration (months)	40.0	Development	\$ 366.20
Realized Design Duration (months)	41.0	Launch	\$ 53.90
Calculated Design Duration (months)	41.6	Operations	-
Initial Mission Life (years)	2.5	Primary	\$ 48.50
Realized Mission Life (years)	23.5	Extended	\$ 211.60
Extended Mission Life (years)	20.1	NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,116.20
Phase A - Award	11/6/1997	Development	\$ 677.00
PDR	10/1/1998	Launch	\$ 99.70
CDR	4/1/1999	Operations	-
Launch	4/7/2001	Primary	\$ 78.80
On Station	10/24/2001	Extended	\$ 260.70
Extend Mission	8/24/2004	PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 994.40
End Mission	9/13/2024	Development	\$ 586.30
Technical Scope		Launch	\$ 86.30
Launch Mass	758	Operations	-
Fuel	348.7	Primary	\$ 72.10
S/V Dry	376.3	Extended	\$ 249.70
S/V Bus	331.8	Payload	
S/V Payload	44.5	Instruments	3
Probe/Rover	-	Mass (kg)	44.5
Cruise	-	Power (W, ave)	58
Lander	-	RTG or S/A	S/A
Aeroshield +	-	S/A Power	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	9.7	BoL 1 Au	1500
Objectives	6	Perihelion	-
Deployments	2	Aphelion	750
		S/A Area (m2)	7.4
		S/A Type	2-axis Gimbal
		Blank	-

2001 Mars Odyssey

- Formerly Mars Global Mapper
 - Formerly Mars Surveyor 2001 Project: a) orbiter, b) lander
 - Mission life: 1-year cruise and 3-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
 - Extension: The mission was extended three times, 3rd extension was 10/1/2008 (through 2015), and it is currently operational (date 3/17/2024 in the database)
 - Status: Currently Operational
 - Operations (4 years) – 5.8+14.0+10.5+9.9+10.0 ($\frac{10}{12}$) (end of October) = 48.53
 - Extended Operations – Nov 1, 2005 – end of 2024 = 261.1 - 48.53 = 212.57
 - Instruments
 - MARIE (3.3 kg, 7.0 W)
 - THEMIS (11.2 kg, 19 W)
 - GRS (30.3 kg, 32 W)
 - Bus Volume: 2.2 x 1.7 x 2.6 m³
 - Deployments: 2
 - Solar array x 2
 - Objectives:
 - Determine the abundance of hydrogen (1)
 - Globally map the elements that make up the surface (2)
 - Acquire high-resolution thermal infrared images of surface minerals (3)
 - Provide information about the structure of the Martian surface (4) and
 - Record the radiation environment in low Mars orbit (5)
 - Communication relay (+1)
 - Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin
- From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012
- Control: 3-axis stabilized
 - Space: 5.7 m
 - Launch mass: 725 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 33 kg
 - Fuel: 348.7 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 331.8 kg
 - Payload: 44.5 kg
 - Structure: 81.7 kg
 - C&DH: 11.1
 - Thermal: 20.3
 - ACS: 23.4
 - Propulsion: 49.7
 - Communications: 23.9 kg
 - Power (+ ballast, remaining mass): 44.2
 - S/A Area: 7.4 m²
 - Power (1 Au): 1500 W
 - Power (station): 750 W

- Science
 - THEMIS: Thermal Emission Imaging System
 - GRS: Gamma Ray Spectrometer
 - MARIE: Martian Radiation Environment Experiment

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-41)

BASIS OF FY 2000 FUNDING REQUIREMENT

	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000
	(Thousands of Dollars)		
MARS SURVEYOR PROGRAM			
98 Orbiter and Lander.....	79,600	22,000	--
01 Orbiter and Lander.....	71,200	150,700	126,800
Mars Network.....	--	--	4,100
Micromissions.....	--	--	5,000
Future Missions.....	57,100	55,700	114,800
ELV (Non-acid).....	142,700	148,200	140,400
Total.....	187,600	228,400	250,700

*Total cost information is provided in the Special Issues section

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-39)

BASIS OF FY 2001 FUNDING REQUIREMENT

	FY 1999	FY 2000	FY 2001
	(Thousands of Dollars)		
MARS SURVEYOR PROGRAM			
1998 Orbiter and Lander.....	16,858	--	34,200
2001 Orbiter and Lander.....	162,204	117,000	35,000
Mars Telecom Network and Science Micromissions.....	--	6,000	297,500
Future Missions.....	48,538	125,400	257,500
Total.....	227,700	248,400	326,700

*Total cost information is provided in the Special Issues section

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

2001 Mars Odyssey

The Mars 2001 Odyssey science objective is to determine the elemental and mineral composition of the surface, learn about the landforms, and measure the potential radiation hazards for future human exploration. The 2001 Mars Odyssey Orbiter is scheduled for launch in April 2001, will arrive at Mars in October 2001, and will begin the mapping orbit 45 to 90 days after orbit capture.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	244.2	80.5	52.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	366.1
LAUNCH SUPPORT	41.7	19.7	5.9	--	--	--	--	--	--	67.3
MISSION OPERATIONS	--	5.8	14.1	10.4	10.1	3.8	--	--	--	44.2
DATA ANALYSIS	--	3.0	9.0	9.6	9.9	6.8	--	--	--	38.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	--	--	THD	THD	THD	THD	--	--	--	--
TOTAL	285.9	109.2	47.1	23.1	20.0	20.0	10.6	--	--	515.9

NASA Budget requests are consistent with PEBD data.

2001 Mars Odyssey References

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Cassini

Mission Attributes		Cassini		
Last Updated		9/13/2024		
Definition		Cost		
COSPAR	1997-061A	Start	1985	
Program		Launch	1992	
Destination	Saturn	Budget \$	1436.4	
Success	Success	Realized \$	1375.9	
Type	Orbiter	Budget Schedule	92	
Launch Vehicle	Titan 4	Realized Schedule	110	
		Then \$	\$ 3,206.80	
		Development	\$ 1,408.50	
		Launch	\$ 398.40	
		Operations	-	
		Primary	\$ 678.00	
		Extended	\$ 721.90	
		NSII 2023\$	\$ 5,916.80	
		Development	\$ 3,019.50	
		Launch	\$ 809.30	
		Operations	-	
		Primary	\$ 1,149.40	
		Extended	\$ 938.60	
		PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 5,079.80	
		Development	\$ 2,484.10	
		Launch	\$ 679.70	
		Operations	-	
		Primary	\$ 1,021.50	
		Extended	\$ 894.50	
Schedule		Technical Scope		
Initial Design Duration (months)	67.0	Launch Mass	5712	
Realized Design Duration (months)	85.0	Fuel	3132	
Calculated Design Duration (months)	77.6	S/V Dry	2581	
Initial Mission Life (years)	11.0	S/V Bus	2150	
Realized Mission Life (years)	19.9	S/V Payload	343	
Extended Mission Life (years)	9.2	Probe/Rover	-	
Phase A - Award	6/1/1991	Cruise	-	
PDR	6/1/1994	Lander	-	
CDR	6/1/1995	Aeroshield +	-	
Launch	10/15/1997	Bus Volume (m ³)	85.4	
On Station	7/1/2004	Objectives	8	
Extend Mission	7/1/2008	Deployments	4	
End Mission	9/15/2017	Payload	Instruments	12
			Mass (kg)	236
			Power (W, ave)	228
			RTG or S/A	RTG
			S/A Power	-
			BoL 1 Au	900
			Perihelion	-
			Aphelion	630
			S/A Area (m ²)	-
			S/A Type	-
			Blank	-

Cassini

- JPL (Cassini) / ESA (Huygens)
- Originally planned as a second Mariner Mark II
- Budget cuts, the cancellation of CRAF, and the rescope of the project necessitated a specialized design.
- Mission life: 7-year cruise and 4-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
- Extension: Mission extended two times, 1st extension Equinox was 7/1/2008 (through 9/2010), 2nd Solstice Mission (date 2/2010 through May 2017)
- Status: Successful
- Instruments (351 kgs, 228-314 W mode dependent) - NSSDCA
 - CIRS (39.24 kg, 26.4 W, 6 kbps)
 - CDA (16.36 kg, 11.4 W, 0.524 kbps)
 - MAG (3.0 kg, 3.1 W, 3.6 kbps)
 - ISS (57.83 kgs, 30 W, 115.2 kbps)
 - INMS (6.0 kgs, 15 W, 1 kbps)
 - MIMI (21.57 kgs, 14 W, 7 kbps)
 - CAPS (12.5 kgs, 14.5 W, 8 kbps)
 - RPWS (6.8 kgs, 7 W, 0.9 kbps)
 - RSS (6.3 kgs)
 - RADAR (18 kgs, 50 W, 175 kbps)
 - UVIS (8 kgs, 6.5 W, 4 kbps)
 - VIMS (40.5kgs – Jane’s)
- Bus Volume: 6.8 x 4.0 dia m³
- Deployments: 4

- 1-Huygens,
 - 3-RTG booms
 - Objectives:
 - Determine the 3-dimensional structure and dynamic behavior of the rings (1)
 - Determine the composition of the satellite surfaces and geological history (2)
 - Determine the nature and origin of the dark material on Lepatus (3)
 - Measure the 3-dimensional structure and dynamics of the magnetosphere (4)
 - Study the dynamic behavior of Saturn's atmosphere at cloud level (5)
 - Study the time variability of Titan's clouds and hazes (6) and
 - Characterize Titan's surface on a regional scale (7)
 - Delivery Huygens (+1)
 - Manufacturer: JPL
- From Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012
- 3-axis stabilized
 - 1992 – Funding change, the CRAF mission component canceled, Cassini launch rescheduled from 1996 to 1997 launch for redesign
 - Launch mass: 5770 kg (weights vary from source to source: 5655, 5712)
 - Fuel: 3132 kg
 - Probe: 348 kg
 - LV Adapter: 165 kg
 - S/V: 2125 kg
 - Space Vehicle:
 - Payload:
 - Structure:
 - C&DH:
 - Thermal:
 - ACS:
 - Propulsion:
 - Communications:
 - Power (+ ballast, remaining mass):
 - S/A Area: $0.0 m^2$
 - Power (1 Au): 885 W BoL (3 RTGs, no batteries)
 - Power (EoM): 638 W
 - Science
 - CAPS: Cassini Plasma Spectrometer
 - VIMS: Visual Infra-Red Mapping Spectrometer
 - ISS: Imaging Science Subsystem
 - RADAR:
 - INMS – Ion Neutral Mass Spectrometer
 - CDA: Cosmic Dust Analyzer
 - RPWS: Radio and Plasma Wave Science
 - UVIS: Ultraviolet Imaging Spectrograph
 - MIMI: Magnetospheric Imaging Instrument
 - MAG: Dual Technique Magnetometer

- RSS: Radio Science Subsystem
- CIRS: Composite Infra-Red Spectrometer
- Huygens: Battery powered, 6 instruments.
- Mass: 348.3 kg
 - Attachment Structure: 30 kg
 - Probe: 318.3
 - Deceleration System: 79.0 kg
 - Scientific Instruments: 48 kg
 - Operated for 2 hours after landing (Gunter)
 - 5 LiSO₂ batteries – 1660 Whr – 250 W for 3-hour mission
- Schedule (Maston)
 - 1986 ESA Cassini Phase A
 - 1987-1988 NASA Mariner Mark II
 - 1989 CRAF/Cassini approved by Congress.
 - 1992 Funding cap implemented – CRAF cancelled, Cassini launch rescheduled from 1996 to 1997.
 - 4/21/1997 Cassini ships

The NASA budget requests for Cassini span from 1992 through 2023 to estimate the program's costs.

As a note: Cassini mission operations were significant >\$60M per year, including 1999-2004 (cruise phase).

The PEDB information is consistent with the NASA budgets. Several modifications are incorporated based on the interpretation of conflicting budget data. For most entries, the actual data is from the second subsequent budget for that year (1990 cost data included in the 1992 budget as actual).

The adjustments to the data entered are:

- 1997 – introduces +\$16.4 for tracking and data support: +\$3.96M added for Years 1990-1993: Budget 1997 lists \$15.8 Prior applied evenly to each of the 4 preceding years.
- 1997 – introduces \$16.8M for civil service compensation for 1990-1994, applied equally to each of the 5 preceding years: \$3.36M
- 1998 – clarifies civil service compensation for 1990-1995 as \$29.8 or -\$0.7M. This applies to 1990 to adjust the line entry to \$2.7M.
- 2009 – operations for 2007 listed by PEDB as \$81.2M. Cassini transitioned from its primary mission to the first extended mission on July 1, 2007. Mission operation costs for 2007 were allocated equally, \$40.6M, to both primary and extended mission operations.
- Mission operations costs from 2002 to 2015 are incomplete. The budgets for 1997 through 1999 forecasted operations costs through 2005. These costs are

absent from subsequent budget requests and lumped within either outer planet cost line items or in the general NASA satellite operations cost structures (up to 21 operating satellites). Costs for 2004-2010, excluding the PEDB assumption for 2007, were not obtainable from the presented information.

- The JPL End of Mission Press Release states that Cassini's mission operations were \$1.4B. Assuming this statement is accurate, the resulting non-2004-2006 and 2008-2010 mission operations totaled \$940.4M. The balance of \$459.6M was distributed equally between the Years 2004-2006 and 2008-2010, for \$76.6M per year and a total operations cost of \$1.4B.
- 1993 – The Centaur Upper Stage (US) cost line item moved to the Titan IV cost accounting. This resulted in a slip in the Cassini launch schedule to shift the Centaur costs away from the Cassini mission and save the Cassini program cost (removed from the annual Cassini development cost). NASA's cost accounting is generic.

These represent the highlights of the Cassini mission cost justifications and allocations. Cassini includes a detailed summary of the costs that justify the PEDB line items.

NASA 1992 Budget Request (p. RD 5-1)

	1990 Actual	1991 Budget		1992 Budget Estimate	Page Number
		Estimate	Estimate		
Galileo development.....	17,127	--	--	--	
Hegellan.....	--	--	--	--	
Ulysses.....	14,252	3,300	3,034	--	RD 5-4
Mars observer.....	98,922	68,900	78,528	54,400	RD 5-6
Mars balloon relay.....	4,400	2,000	1,497	1,200	RD 5-6
Comet rendezvous asteroid flyby/cassini.....	29,319	146,000	145,000	328,000	RD 5-8
Mission operations and data analysis.....	155,956	173,500	161,175	150,500	RD 5-10
Research and analysis.....	70,672	82,500	67,866	93,200	RD 5-12
Total.....	390,848	485,200	457,100	627,300	

NASA 1993 Budget Request (p. RD 5-7)

	1991 Actual	1992 Budget		1993 Budget Estimate
		Estimate	Estimate	
Spacecraft.....	91,300	209,920	134,000	122,700
Experiments.....	46,800	104,960	68,500	76,800
Ground operations.....	9,200	13,120	8,200	10,500
Total.....	147,300	328,000	210,700	210,000
Launch vehicle.....	(2,400)	(97,100)	(13,300)	(9,300)

NASA 1994 Budget Request (p. RD 4-9)

	1992 Actual	1993 Budget		1994 Budget Estimate
		Estimate	Estimate	
Spacecraft.....	134,000	122,700	122,700	168,500
Experiments.....	68,500	76,800	76,800	81,500
Ground operations.....	9,200	10,200	5,423	16,600
Total.....	210,700	210,000	204,923	266,600
Launch vehicle.....	(20,100)	(9,300)	(5,278)	(82,300)

NASA 1995 Budget Request (p. SAT 1.2-7)

CASSINI	OPMENT	FY 95 PRESIDENT'S BUDGET											
		FY 90	FY 91	FY 92	FY 93	FY 94	FY 95	FY 96	FY 97	FY 98	FY 99	TOTAL	
29.5	143.0	210.7	205.0	266.6	255.0	191.5	107.3	13.8	1422.4				
APA	0.7	9.3	10.2	15.0	11.5	0.0	6.5	13.2	1.0	34.2			
TAXES	28.8	133.7	200.5	190.0	238.3	249.0	175.6	90.7	12.7	1203.3			
TOTAL JPL	1.2	18.9	80.8	18.5	13.9	14.9	18.0	2.0		144.1			
CARRY FORWARD													
GAZVOWER													
TOTAL OBLIGATIONS	27.5	151.1	192.8	208.1	242.9	245.0	173.5	106.7	15.7	1280.3			
PROJECT MANAGEMENT	1.6	4.1	6.0	5.6	6.0	6.4	6.9	7.4	0.9	44.8			
PROJECT ENGINEERING	1.6	4.9	4.8	5.4	4.4	4.6	3.4	3.7	0.4	31.2			
SCIENCE	1.1	3.3	4.1	3.2	3.9	4.7	4.8	4.2	0.8	29.9			
INSTRUMENTS	5.9	27.8	39.5	55.9	64.9	75.1	47.1	14.7	2.7	207.4			
SPACECRAFT/SERVICE	16.0	34.7	82.7	107.9	115.5	103.2	64.4	40.5	4.4	610.3			
GROUND SYSTEM	0.8	2.4	4.7	7.5	15.8	23.6	20.1	31.3	3.4	117.6			
RTG	0.5	18.9	20.0	22.3	23.2	12.2	8.5	4.6	0.6	116.6			
RTG					0.4	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.1	1.9			
RTG						8.8	14.6	10.2	2.2	37.4			
UNALLOCATED CONTINGENCY					(23.1)	(87.2)	(48.0)	(17.6)		(185.9)			
TOTAL RESERVES (APACONTINGENCY)					43.4	81.8	66.7	33.6	2.5	227.5			395.1
% RESERVES					19%	30%	48%	30%	20%				
MANPOWER		1074		605	593	513	429	332	45	3591			

(p. SAT 6-2a)

CASSINI - TITAN IV/CENTAUR COST GROWTH (Dollars in Millions)

	Prior	FY93	FY94	FY95	FY96	FY97	FY98	Total
FY 1994 President's Budget	27.7	5.3	82.3	86.1	100.1	88.7	26.9	417.1
FY 1995 President's Budget	27.7	5.3	85.4	91.3	102.7	120.6	41.4	475.4
Net Change			4.1	5.2	2.6	31.9	14.5	58.3

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-18)

	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	588.2	266.6	255.0	191.5	107.3	13.8				1,422.4
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS						49.3	56.4	56.3	593.0	755.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	33.0	86.4	78.1	98.9	115.3	40.0				451.7
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	15.8	.6	3.2	3.6	4.2	4.5	9.0	13.2		54.1
TOTAL	637.0	353.6	336.3	294.0	226.8	107.6	65.4	69.5	593.0	2,683.2

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

	PRIOR	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	854.8	255.0	191.5	106.7	13.7					1,421.7
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					48.4	55.0	56.6	53.5		751.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	119.4	81.0	89.1	100.3	39.5					429.1
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	16.4	3.2	2.0	2.6	5.3	9.0	6.0	8.0		52.5
TOTAL EXCLUDING CIVIL SERVICE COSTS (\$M)	990.6	339.2	282.6	209.6	106.7	64.8	61.0	64.6	636.2	2,664.3

(ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE FTEs)	(282)	(107)	(89)	(31)
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M)	16.8	7.6	4.9	2.3

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	1,109.8	191.5	89.6	9.0						1,399.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				38.1	55.8	55.0	56.6	63.8	466.7	736.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	206.1	88.2	95.2	39.6						429.1
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	19.6	1.8	3.0	4.7	8.8	6.2	4.5	5.0		53.6
TOTAL EXCLUDING CIVIL SERVICE COSTS (\$M)	1,335.5	281.5	187.8	91.4	64.6	61.2	61.1	68.8	466.7	2,618.6

(ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE FTEs)	(389)	(84)	(24)	(3)	(3)	(3)	(3)	(3)
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M)	23.7	6.1	1.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	1301.3	74.6								1375.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS		15.0	38.1	55.8	55.0	53.6	60.8	70.7	396.0	1375.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT		294.3	92.7	17.1						404.1
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		21.4	3.0	4.7	8.8	6.2	4.5	5.0	5.0	49.1
TOTAL EXCLUDING CIVIL SERVICE COSTS (\$M)	1617.0	185.3	59.9	64.6	61.2	58.1	65.8	75.7	396.0	2583.6

(ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE FTEs)	(473)	(30)	(6)	(6)	(6)	(6)	(6)	(6)
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M)	29.8	2.3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-46)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into "Other Mission Operations" – 1999 Budget Request planning.

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-43)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into “Other Mission Operations” – 1999 Budget Request planning.

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-44)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into “Other Mission Operations” – 1999 Budget Request planning.

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. unknown)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into “Other Mission Operations” – 1999 Budget Request planning.

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-16)

BUDGET				
Budget Authority (\$M)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget	118.9	310.0	309.9	
Stardust	3.5	4.6	5.3	
Genesis	0.0	7.2	8.2	
Contour	1.5	2.4		
Galileo				
DS-1	0.3			
Messenger			3.0	
Deep Impact			6.9	
Dawn				
Cassini	30.7	31.5	30.3	
DSN expansion	22.0	15.3	0.7	
DSMS	65.9	249.6	265.6	
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget	+0.8	+0.0	-3.4	Reason for Change:
Stardust			+0.3	
Genesis	-0.2		+2.0	growth
Contour			-2.0	spacecraft lost
Messenger			+0.1	full cost
Deep Impact			+0.1	full cost
Dawn				new mission selection
Cassini	+1.0		+1.0	full cost
DSN expansion	+7.0			
DSMS	-1.0		-5.0	includes transfer to Optical Comm

 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
 Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
 FY 2002 and FY 2003 are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 2-18)

BUDGET				
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRESBJD	298.9	308.2	277.0	
Stardust	4.7	5.3		
Genesis	8.1	8.2		
Messenger		3.0		
Deep Impact		6.9		
Cassini	31.3	30.1	16.3	
DSN expansion	15.2	0.7		
DSMS	239.6	254.0	260.7	

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. ESA 2-18)

- No reference – 2005 Budget Request planning

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p. SAE SMD 1-3)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into “Solar System Research” – 2005 Budget Request planning; \$119.5M for Cassini, Messenger, and New Horizons operations.

NASA 2008 Budget Request (SMD-179)

- Cassini mission operations lumped into “Planetary Science Research” – estimate for 2006.

NASA 2009 Budget Request (Sci-159)

FY 2009 Budget Request							
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2007 Actual	FY 2008 Enacted	FY 2009	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	1,215.6	1,247.3	1,334.2	1,410.1	1,537.3	1,570.0	1,608.7
Planetary Science Research	181.9	242.1	270.8	315.8	355.6	373.2	382.6
Discovery	128.3	153.0	247.0	258.3	256.0	326.1	140.5
New Frontiers	106.6	132.2	263.9	250.3	232.3	227.7	236.9
Mars Exploration	634.9	553.5	386.5	299.6	344.5	341.1	413.8
Outer Planets	79.0	81.9	101.1	216.7	279.4	230.6	362.0
Technology	84.8	84.8	64.9	69.3	69.6	71.3	73.0
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	1,411.2	1,395.8	1,676.9	1,720.3	1,738.3	1,748.2	=
Planetary Science Research	278.8	370.5	402.9	416.2	428.5	402.9	=
Discovery	179.9	184.9	320.7	370.2	355.2	341.1	=
New Frontiers	158.1	147.3	296.0	277.5	267.9	274.5	=
Mars Exploration	721.1	625.7	594.8	592.5	624.0	666.5	=
Technology	73.4	67.6	62.6	63.9	62.7	64.2	=
Total Change from FY 2008 Request	-195.7	-148.4	-342.6	-310.2	-200.9	-178.2	1,608.7

NASA 2010 Budget Request (SCI-145)

FY 2010 Budget Request							
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2008 Actual	FY 2009 Enacted	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	1,312.6	1,325.6	1,346.2	1,500.6	1,577.7	1,600.0	1,633.2
Planetary Science Research	183.1	162.1	161.7	193.5	240.2	232.6	254.2
Lunar Quest Program	41.3	105.0	103.6	142.6	138.6	145.5	118.7
Discovery	136.4	247.0	213.2	234.6	256.8	256.5	264.3
New Frontiers	115.1	263.9	264.1	239.9	294.2	239.8	249.6
Mars Exploration	709.3	381.6	416.1	494.5	405.5	514.3	536.7
Outer Planets	62.2	101.1	98.6	97.1	140.3	117.7	118.5
Technology	65.2	64.9	89.0	98.4	102.1	93.5	91.4

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET – 64)

FY 2011 Budget Request							
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2009 Actual	FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	104.8	98.6	103.5	157.9	152.0	144.0	155.8
Outer Planets	104.8	98.6	103.5	157.9	152.0	144.0	155.8
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	101.1	98.6	97.1	140.3	117.7	118.5	--
Outer Planets	101.1	98.6	97.1	140.3	117.7	118.5	--
Changes from FY 2010 Request	3.7	0.0	6.4	17.6	34.2	25.5	--

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

FY 2012 Budget Request							
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2010	Ann CR, FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	100.6	-	120.8	80.5	82.2	84.1	88.5
Outer Planets	100.6	-	120.8	80.5	82.2	84.1	88.5

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-56)

FY 2013 BUDGET							
Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2011	Estimate FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	91.9	122.1	84.0	80.8	78.8	76.2	76.3
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-38.1				
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-31.2%				

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-50)

FY 2014 Budget							
Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	122.1	--	79.0	45.6	24.4	26.4	26.4
Change from FY 2012	--	--	-43.1				
Percentage change from FY 2012	--	--	-35.3 %				

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-47)

OUTER PLANETS

FY 2015 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2013	Enacted FY 2014	Request FY 2015	FY 2016	Notional		
					FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019
Outer Planets Future Mission	69.7	80.0	15.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	147.8	159.0	95.7	82.2	84.5	27.8	9.1
Change from FY 2014			-63.3				
Percentage change from FY 2014			39.8%				

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-45)

FY 2016 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2014	Enacted FY 2015	Request FY 2016	FY 2017	Notional		
					FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	5.3	--	18.9	20.5	12.9	4.1	2.0
Jupiter Europa	80.0	100.0	30.0	30.0	50.0	75.0	100.0
Outer Planets Research	15.5	--	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cassini	51.6	--	58.8	58.7	10.2	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	152.4	--	116.2	117.7	81.6	87.6	110.5

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-55)

OUTER PLANETS AND OCEAN WORLDS

FY 2017 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2015	Enacted FY 2016	Request FY 2017	FY 2018	Notional		
					FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	7.4	--	20.5	17.4	4.1	2.0	2.3
Jupiter Europa	100.0	175.0	49.6	24.2	65.2	117.5	236.5
Outer Planets Research	8.5	--	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cassini	68.1	--	58.7	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	184.0	--	137.3	56.0	77.8	128.0	247.3

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-68)

FY 2018 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2016	Enacted FY 2017	Request FY 2018	FY 2019	Notional		
					FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	18.7	--	18.5	6.6	5.1	5.3	5.1
Outer Planets Research	8.5	--	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cassini	58.8	--	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	86.0	--	32.9	15.1	13.6	13.8	13.6

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-85)

FY 2019 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2017	CR FY 2018	Request FY 2019	FY 2020	Notional		
					FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	22.9	--	10.3	5.1	5.3	5.1	6.0
Outer Planets Research	7.5	--	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cassini	54.1	--	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	84.5	--	20.9	13.6	13.8	13.6	14.5

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-85)

FY 2020 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2018	Enacted FY 2019	Request FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024
Icy Satellites Surface Technology	35.0	--	2.2	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	18.5	--	5.1	5.3	5.1	3.4	0.7
Outer Planets Research	8.5	--	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
Cassini	19.2	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	81.2	--	15.8	18.8	18.6	16.9	14.2

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-93)

FY 2021 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2019	Enacted FY 2020	Request FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025
Icy Satellites Surface Technology	35.0	--	0.0	5.8	2.8	2.5	2.5
JUICE - Jupiter Icy Moons Explorer	15.6	--	2.7	4.8	3.4	0.8	0.8
Outer Planets Research	6.7	--	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3
Cassini	3.9	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	61.2	--	10.9	18.9	14.5	11.5	11.7

Cassini References

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Matson, D.L., Spilker, L.J. & Lebreton, JP. *The Cassini/Huygens Mission to the Saturnian System*. Space Science Reviews 104, 1–58 (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1023609211620>

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Contour

Mission Attributes	
Contour	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2002-034A
Program	Discovery 6
Destination	Comet
Success	Failure - LV
Type	Flyby
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7425
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	34.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	35.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	41.6
Initial Mission Life (years)	6.0
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.0
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.0
Phase A - Award	2/1/1999
PDR	1/20/2000
CDR	12/1/2000
Launch	7/3/2002
On Station	7/3/2002
Extend Mission	7/3/2002
End Mission	7/3/2002
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	775
Fuel	70
S/V Dry	328
S/V Bus	267.6
S/V Payload	60.4
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m³)	5.7
Objectives	6
Deployments	0
Cost	
Start	1998
Launch	2002
Budget \$	69.1
Realized \$	96.8
Budget Schedule	38
Realized Schedule	40
Then \$	\$ 145.80
Development	\$ 96.80
Launch	\$ 49.00
Operations	-
Primary	\$ -
Extended	-
NSII 2023\$	\$ 258.10
Development	\$ 172.00
Launch	\$ 86.10
Operations	-
Primary	\$ -
Extended	-
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 226.70
Development	\$ 150.80
Launch	\$ 75.90
Operations	-
Primary	\$ -
Extended	-
Payload	
Instruments	4
Mass (kg)	60.4
Power (W, ave)	100
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	670
Perihelion	-
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m2)	12.8
S/A Type	Body
Blank	-

Contour

- Spacecraft lost during transition from EEO to cruise immediately following SRM command.
- Discovery 6
- Mission life: 6-year prime mission to fly by three comet nuclei: Encke in 2003, Schwassmann-Wachmann-3 in 2006, and a'Arrest in 2008.
- Extension: none
- Status: Failed during launch operations. 45 days after launch, the Star-30BP kick motor fired for an interplanetary trajectory and loss of contact.
 - Operations (0 years) – 45 days in parking orbit
- Instruments
 - CRISP (27.7 kg, 45 W)
 - CIDA (10.5 kg, 13 W)
 - NGIMS (13.5 kg, 47 W)
 - CFI (9.7 kg, 10 W)
- Bus Volume: octagonal prism 0.81 side length x 1.49 height $m^3 = 4.72m^3$
- Deployments: 0
- Objectives:
 - Image parts of the nucleus at resolutions of 4 meters per pixel
 - Determine the nucleus size, shape, rotation state, and albedo/color heterogeneity.
 - Map composition of the nucleus surface and coma through spectroscopy
 - Obtain detailed composition measurements of gas and dust in the near-nucleus environment.
 - Access level of outgassing through imaging, spectroscopy, and gas and dust measurements
 - Asses the diversity of comets
- Manufacturer: Johns Hopkins University – Applied Physics Laboratory

The mission omitted from Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

Chiu includes Contour’s master schedule.

- Control: dual mode, spin-stabilized (parking orbit and cruise), 3-axis stabilized (comet)
- Launch mass: 775 kg (Delta II launch manifest is 1005 kg to EEO – Earth elliptical orbit)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): tbd kg
 - Fuel: 70.0 kg
 - Star 30 SRM: 377 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 267.6 kg
 - Payload: 60.4 kg
 - Alternate sources: Delta II manifest – 1005 kg Launch mass; Panneton – total mass 970, including 500kg SRM, 80 kg Hydrazine, 390 kg S/V dry.
- S/A Area: 8 panels $0.81 \times 1.49 m^2 + 1$ octagonal panel 0.81 side length $m^2 = 9.65 + 3.16 m^2$
- Power (1 Au): 670

• Science

- CRISP: Contour Remote Imager/Spectrograph
- CIDA: Comet Impact Dust Analyzer
- NGIMS: Neutral Gas and Ion Mass Spectrometer
- CFI: Contour Forward Imager

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-47) provides full program cost accounting. The NASA 2004 budget reflects -\$2.0M for planned operations costs for 2004. Does not address civil servant and data analysis entries budgeted in 2003.

CONTOUR Life Cycle Cost Data:	Fiscal							ETC	Total
	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	FY 06	FY 07		
Pre-development	9.2								9.2
Development	35.2	41.6	10.8						87.6
Launch services	16.9	20.6	11.5						49.0
Operations				2.4	2.0	0.4	1.6		6.4
Data Analysis				1.5	1.5	1.4	1.8		6.2
[Est. Civil Servant FTE]		10	9	6	6	3	3		

Key Milestones:	FY 2002 Budget		FY 2003 Budget		Comment
	Date	Date	Date	Date	
Complete environmental testing	FY 02		4/02		
Launch	7/02		7/02		On schedule

SAT 1-47

Contour References

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E. Reynolds, M. Chiu, R. Farquhar, and D. Dunham, *The CONTOUR Discovery Mission*, 1999 IEEE Aerospace Conference. Proceedings (Cat. No.99TH8403), Snowmass, CO, USA, 1999, pp. 11-18, vol.2, doi: 10.1109/AERO.1999.793137.

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Dart

Mission Attributes		Dart	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition			
COSPAR	2021-110A		
Program	Planetary Def		
Destination	Asteroid		
Success	Success		
Type	Impact		
Launch Vehicle	Falcon 9		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	50.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	56.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	57.6		
Initial Mission Life (years)	0.9		
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.8		
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.0		
Phase A - Award	3/1/2017		
PDR	4/1/2018		
CDR	4/1/2019		
Launch	11/24/2021		
On Station	9/26/2022		
Extend Mission	9/26/2022		
End Mission	9/26/2022		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass		Payload	
Fuel	610	Instruments	1
S/V Drv	86.5	Mass (kg)	14
S/V Bus	560	Power (W, ave)	5
S/V Payload	500	RTG or S/A	S/A
Probe/Rover	23.5	S/A Power	-
Cruise	-	BoL 1 Au	6600
Lander	-	Perihelion	-
Aeroshield +	-	Aphelion	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	8.9	S/A Area (m ²)	22.0
Objectives	4	S/A Type	Roll Out
Deployments	1	Blank	-

- Launch mass: 610 kg (Falcon 9 v1.2 (Block 5))
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 0 kg
 - Fuel: 86.5 kg (unaccounted mass from launch, LICIA deployment, and impact mass)
 - Space Vehicle: 500. kg
 - Payload: 23.5 kg
- S/A Area: 22 m²
- Power (1 Au): 6600 W
- Science
 - DRACO: Didymos Reconnaissance and Asteroid Camera for OpNav
 - LICIA CubeSat: Light Italian CubeSat for Imaging of Asteroids

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-6): The FY 2017 request includes \$6.1M for the Asteroid Impact and Deflection Assessment (AIDA), all of which is allocated to DART.

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-14): prior formulation \$22.5M (pre-2019: 2017-\$6.1 and 2018-\$16.4).

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-13): prior formulation \$40.6M (pre-2020: 2017-\$6.1, 2018-\$16.4, and 2019-\$18.1). prior implementation \$22.9 (pre-2020: 2019-\$22.9).

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-14)

FY 2022 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Request	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	BTC	Total
	Prior	Enacted								
Formulation	40.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	40.6
Development/Implementation	120.9	72.4	65.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	258.3
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	1.4	11.1	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.5
2021 MPAR LCC Estimate	161.5	72.4	66.4	11.1	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	315.4
Total Budget	161.5	72.4	66.4	11.1	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	315.4
Change from FY 2021				-55.3						
Percentage change from FY 2021				-83.3%						

(p. PS-17)

Development Cost Details

NASA confirmed DART to proceed into implementation in August 2018. The NEXT-C electric propulsion technology demonstration system is funded by the Discovery Future project and is not included in the development cost of this mission.

Element	Base Year Development Cost Estimate (\$M)	Current Year Development Cost Estimate (\$M)	Change from Base Year Estimate (\$M)
TOTAL:	258.3	258.3	0
Aircraft/Spacecraft	71.7	104.1	+32.4
Payloads	5.3	6.3	+1.0
Systems I&T	16.4	19.4	+3.0
Launch Vehicle	41.0	68.8	+27.8
Ground Systems	5.7	6.8	+1.1
Science/Technology	3.2	3.8	+0.6
Other Direct Project Costs	114.9	49.2	-65.7

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-14)

FY 2023 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Request	Request	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	FY 2027
	FY 2021	FY 2022						
Double Asteroid Redirection Test	75.5	16.7	4.5	4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Near Earth Object Observations	51.3	42.2	43.3	43.3	41.5	41.5	42.5	47.7
Total Budget	126.8	58.9	47.8	47.8	41.5	41.5	42.5	47.7
Change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-11.1	-11.1				
Percent change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-23.2%	-23.2%				

Dart

- Mission life: Cruise to impact (1 year) from 2019 NASA budget: Dec 2020 to Oct 2022.
- Extension: none (impact)
- Status: Completed
 - Operations – cruise Nov 24, 2021, to impact Sep 26, 2022
- Instruments
 - DRACO (9.55 kg, 5 W)
 - LICIA CubeSat (14 kg, 0 W – self-powered)
- Bus Volume: 2.6 x 1.8 x 1.9 m³ with propulsion & payload. Core is 1.14 x 1.24 x 1.32m³
- Deployments: 3
 - LICIA
 - Solar array x 2 (roll out)
- Objectives:
 - Perform a full-scale demonstration of the spacecraft kinetic impact technique for deflection of an asteroid, (1)
 - Measure the resultant asteroid deflection, (2)
 - Study hypervelocity collision effects on an asteroid (3)
 - Deploy LICIA. (+1)
- Manufacturer: Johns Hopkins University – Applied Physics Laboratory (JHU-APL)

Not available in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized

Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) References

Krebs, Gunter D. **DART**. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/dart_apl.htm .

NASA. **Double Asteroid Redirection Test**. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2021-110A> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

NASA. **LICIACube**. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2021-110C> , downloaded Mar 5, 2024.

NASA. **NASA Awards Launch Services Contract for Asteroid Redirect Test Mission**. Apr 11, 2019. <https://www.nasa.gov/news-release/nasa-awards-launch-services-contract-for-asteroid-redirect-test-mission/> , viewed Mar 22, 2024.

Adams, Elena et. al. **Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) Mission**. Oct 1, 2023. APL_COMM-23-04772. NTRS Document ID 20230015804. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20230015804/downloads/DART%20Final%20Technical%20Report.pdf> , downloaded Mar 22, 2024.

Dawn

Mission Attributes		Dawn																																																	
Last Updated		9/13/2024																																																	
Definition		<table border="1"> <tr><td>COSPAR</td><td>2007-043A</td></tr> <tr><td>Program</td><td>Discovery 9</td></tr> <tr><td>Destination</td><td>Asteroid</td></tr> <tr><td>Success</td><td>Success</td></tr> <tr><td>Type</td><td>Orbiter</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch Vehicle</td><td>Delta 7925</td></tr> </table>		COSPAR	2007-043A	Program	Discovery 9	Destination	Asteroid	Success	Success	Type	Orbiter	Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925																																				
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Dawn

- Mission life: cruise and prime mission (Primary mission: 8 years 9 months)
- Extension: extended
- Status: Successful
 - Operations (11 years 5 months)
 - Extended Operations – June 2016 – 11/1/2018
- Instruments
 - Framing Camera (10 kg, 24 W)
 - GRaND (10.5 kg, 9 W)
 - Mag (3.05 kg, 3 W)
 - VIR (MS) (9.3 kg, 17.6 W)
 - Radio Science (part of bus communications)
- Bus Volume: 1.64 x 1.27 x 1.77 m³ = 3.59 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Mag boom
- Objectives:
 - Internal structure, density, and homogeneity of two complementary protoplanets, (1)
 - Determine shape, size, composition, and mass, (2)
 - Surface morphology, cratering, magnetism, (3)
 - Determine thermal history and size of core (4)
 - Understand the role of water in controlling asteroid evolution, (5) and
 - Explore the current paradigm of Vesta as the howardite, eucrite, and diogenite (HED) parent body and determine if meteorites come from Ceres – provide geological context for HEDs (6)
- Manufacturer: JPL / Orbital Sciences

From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Original launch May 27, 2006. Due to financial shortfalls and technical problems (ion thrusters), the project was delayed by more than 1 year.
- Delta II Heavy 2925H-9.5 with Star 48 upper stage into heliocentric orbit
- Control: 3-axis stabilized (assumed due to deployed solar arrays)
- Design life: 10 years.
- Launch mass: 1217.7 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest – 1218 kg)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 33 kg
 - Fuel (xenon): 425 kg
 - Fuel (hydrazine): 45.6 kg
 - Space Vehicle: kg
- S/A Area: two 2.3 x 8.3 m² solar arrays
- Power (1 Au): 10.3 kW
- Power (3 Au - station): 1.3 kW EoL
- Science
 - Framing Camera: Framing Camera
 - GRaND: Gamma Ray and Neutron Spectrometer

- Mag: Magnetometer
- VIR: Visual and Infrared Imaging Spectrometer
- Radio Science

Dawn at Vesta Press Kit

Program: Cost: \$466 million total, including \$373 million to build and launch the spacecraft and \$93 million for 10 years of operations and data analysis.

Dawn Launch Press Kit

Program: Cost: \$357.5 million total (not including launch vehicle), consisting of \$281.7 million spacecraft development and \$75.8 million mission operations.

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-11)

TECHNICAL COMMITMENT		
The baseline for this technical commitment will be set at Confirmation Review.		
Technical Specifications	FY04 President's Budget	Change from Baseline
Payload:	The five instruments are a Framing Camera, Mapping Spectrometer, Gamma Ray/Neutron Spectrometer, Laser Altimeter, and Magnetometer.	--
Launch Vehicle:	Delta 2025H	--
Cruise:	3 NSTAR Xenon (Xe) thrusters, one at a time. Maximum fuel mass: 288 kg to Vesta and 89 kg to Ceres	--
Vesta:	Orbit at 700 and 120 km alt., 11 months	--
Ceres:	Orbit at 890 and 140 km alt., 11 months	--
Schedule	FY04 President's Budget	Change from Baseline
Start of Formulation	Sep 02	--
Preliminary Design Review	Aug 03	--
Critical Design Review	Apr 04	--
Launch	May 06	--
Vesta Encounter	Jul 10	--
Ceres Encounter	Aug 14	--
End of Mission & Data Archiving	Jul 16	--

(p. SAE 2-12)

BUDGET/LIFE CYCLE COST											
Total budget authority represents the Life Cycle Cost (LCC).											
Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	Prior	FY02	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget	0.0	1.0	30.3	125.6	83.5	40.0	0.2	0.0	89.8	280.2	Baseline to be established at Aug 03
Development	0.0	1.0	30.3	125.6	83.5	39.9				286.8	Confirmation Review; project not yet in implementation.
Operations										44.9	
Data Analysis				0.0	1.0	1.1	1.3			44.7	
Changes since FY 03 Pres.											
Budget	+0.0	+1.0	+30.3	+125.6	+83.5	+40.0	+0.2	+0.0	+89.8	+390.2	Reason for Change:
Development	+0.0	+1.0	+30.3	+125.6	+83.5	+39.9				+286.8	Mission selection
Operations										+44.9	
Data Analysis					+1.0	+1.1	+1.3			+44.7	
FY 2003 President's Budget (LCC)										+47.1	Mission selected after 03 Bud.
Initial Baseline (LCC)										TBD	(see above)

 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
 Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
 FY 2002, FY 2003, Prior and BTC are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget (p. ESA 2-12) 2003 Dev Costs - \$36.3

NASA 2006 Budget (p. SAE 2-2) 2004 Dev Costs - \$126.5

NASA 2007 Budget (p. SMD 2-11) 2005 Dev Costs - \$85.9

NASA 2008 Budget (p. SMD-156) 2008 Ops Costs - \$7.8, 2009 Ops Costs - \$7.6, 2010 Ops Costs - \$8.1

Development Cost Details

Element	Base Year Development Cost Estimate (\$M)	Current Year Development Cost Estimate (\$M)	Delta
Total:	273.5	263.4	-10.1
Aircraft/Spacecraft	143.7	117.3	-26.4
ELV	87.5	65.0	-22.5
Mission Operations	12.7	14.6	1.9
Other	20.4	55.2	34.8
Payload	8.7	7.3	-1.4
Science/Technology	0.5	4.0	3.5

NASA 2013 Budget (p. PS-23) 2011 Ops Costs - \$14.8

NASA 2014 Budget (p. PS-23) 2012 Ops Costs - \$14.3

NASA 2015 Budget (p. PS-20) 2013 Ops Costs - \$23.3

NASA 2016 Budget (p. PS-19) 2014 Ops Costs - \$1.5

NASA 2017 Budget (p. PS-22) 2015 Ops Costs - \$17.2

NASA 2018 Budget (p. PS-30) 2016 Ops Costs - \$22.2

NASA 2019 Budget (p. PS-48) 2017 Ops Costs - \$1.0

NASA 2020 Budget (p. PS-48) 2018 Ops Costs - \$11.1

NASA 2021 Budget (p. PS-49) 2019 Ops Costs - \$0.2

Dawn References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Dawn (Discovery 9)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/dawn.htm.

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NASA. *Dawn at Vesta – Press Kit*. Jul 2011. <https://science.nasa.gov/resource/dawn-at-vesta-press-kit/>, downloaded Mar 22, 2024.

Deep Impact

Mission Attributes Deep Impact	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2005-001A
Program	Discovery 8
Destination	Comet
Success	Success
Type	Rendezvous
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	39.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	50.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	57.2
Initial Mission Life (years)	1.6
Realized Mission Life (years)	8.6
Extended Mission Life (years)	8.1
Phase A - Award	5/1/2000
PDR	3/1/2001
CDR	1/1/2002
Launch	1/12/2005
On Station	7/4/2005
Extend Mission	7/4/2005
End Mission	8/11/2013
Cost	
Start	1999
Launch	2005
Budget \$	194.1
Realized \$	252
Budget Schedule	44
Realized Schedule	63
Then \$	\$ 352.50
Development	\$ 230.90
Launch	\$ 57.60
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 15.00
Extended	\$ 49.00
NSII 2023\$	\$ 578.30
Development	\$ 390.50
Launch	\$ 96.10
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 23.50
Extended	\$ 68.20
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 521.60
Development	\$ 349.40
Launch	\$ 86.80
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 21.40
Extended	\$ 64.00
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	1020
Fuel	-
S/V Dry	1042
S/V Bus	580
S/V Payload	90
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	12.5
Objectives	4
Deployments	2
Payload	
Instruments	3
Mass (kg)	90
Power (W, ave)	92
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	750
Perihelion	620
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m ²)	7.2
S/A Type	Fixed
Blank	-

hitting the surface of the nucleus at high velocity., (1)

- Determine properties of the surface layers such as density, porosity, strength, and composition from the resultant crater and its formation., (2)
- Study the relationship between the surface layers of a cometary nucleus and the change of finding pristine materials of the interior by comparison of the interior of the crater with the pre-impact surface (3) and
- Improve our understanding of the evolution of cometary nuclei, particularly their approach to dormancy, by comparing the interior and surface (4).
- Manufacturer: Orbital Sciences and Ball Aerospace (payload)

From Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 650 kg (Delta II launch manifest: 1400 kg)
 - Ballast/Adapter (unaccounted mass): 49 kg
 - Fuel: 86 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 515 kg
 - Payload: 90 kg
 - Impactor: 372 kg
 - Dead weight: 113
- S/A Area: fixed wing (7.2 m² – source NSSDCA)
- Power (1 Au): 750 W (Epoxi Encounter Fact Sheet: Nov 2, 2010)
- Power (station): 620 W (NSSDCA)
- Science
 - HRI: High Resolution Imager
 - MRI: Medium Resolution Imager
 - ITS: Impact Targeting Sensor

Deep Impact

- Planning and mission Design: JPL Nov 1999 – May 2001
- Total cost: \$333M including launch.
- Mission life: 18-month cruise and impact (2004 NASA Budget: launch 1/05, Encounter 7/05)
- Extension: extended two times, 1st extension was 7/3/2005 (through 2011), 2nd extension was identified 7/3/2007; communications lost Aug 11, 2013, en route to another target (believed to be out of fuel)
- Status: Completed
 - Operations (18 months) –
 - Extended Operations – July 4, 20025 through Aug 11, 2013
- Instruments
 - HRI (unknown)
 - MRI (unknown)
 - ITS (unknown)
- Bus Volume: 3.2 x 1.7 x 2.3 m³
- Deployments: 2
 - Impactor
 - High-gain antenna gimbal
- Objectives:
 - Dramatically increase the knowledge of key properties of a cometary nucleus and, for the first time, directly assess the interior of a cometary nucleus using a massive Impactor

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
LUNAR PROSPECTOR	63.9	1.4								65.3
NEAR	202.2	13.2	10.0	1.5	3.0	3.0	1.5			234.4
STARBUST	170.7	4.3	4.6	4.3	5.6	6.8	5.6	6.6		208.5
GENESIS	127.3	62.3	32.3	6.9	7.4	2.8	2.1	1.5	0.3	242.9
CONTOURNIR	9.2	32.2	53.9	26.5	3.9	3.5	1.8	3.4		154.4
DEEP IMPACT	1.5	22.7	72.7	84.2	55.6	21.0	9.6	2.1		288.4
MESSENGER	1.7	9.6	52.0	97.4	64.7	35.2	7.0	6.9	51.7	326.2
FUTURE MISSIONS		3.5	4.9	9.0	60.2	202.3	266.1	273.1	Continuing	
TOTAL EXCLUDING CIVIL SERVICE COSTS (\$M)	169.2	234.3	229.8	230.4	274.6	295.7	293.6			
ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE PRISM	(21)	(18)	(22)	(28)	(33)	(37)	(39)			
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M)		2.1	1.4	1.9	2.7	5.3	8.0	8.2		

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-49)

Science Objectives:

- Dramatically improve the knowledge of key properties of cometary nuclei
- Measure the composition of the interior of the comet
- Improve our understanding of the evolution of cometary nuclei

Deep Impact Life Cycle Cost Data:

	Prior	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	FY 06	FY 07	BTC	Total
ATD	24.2	72.7	85.2	59.1	21.0	11.1	2.0			275.3
Development	24.1	15.5								39.6
Launch Services		49.9	62.7	36.3	7.7					156.6
Operations	0.1	7.3	22.5	22.8		4.9				57.6
Data Analysis					6.8	8.2	0.3			15.3
					1.6	2.9	1.7			6.2

Key Milestones:

	FY 2002 Budget Date	FY 2003 Budget Date	Comment
PDR	2/01	2/01	Held week of 2/26/01
CDR	1/02	1/02	On schedule
Launch	1/04	1/04	On schedule

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-9)

TECHNICAL COMMITMENT		
The baseline for this technical commitment was made in 5/01 and is detailed in Appendix 8 of the Discovery Program Plan.		
Technical Specifications	FY04 President's Budget	Change from Baseline
Mission requirement	Fly to comet Tempel 1	--
Payload	High Resolution Imager (HRI), Medium Resolution Imager (MRI) and Impactor Target Sensor (ITS)	--
Launch Vehicle	Delta II	--
Launch Mass	1,000 kg	--
Prime antenna diameter	1 meter (parabolic)	--
Communications bandwidths	x-band for flyby spacecraft (uplink command and downlink telemetry) and s-band for impactor communication to/from the flyby spacecraft	--
Max Data Rate	175 kbps	--
Max solar array power	620 W at encounter	--

Schedule		
	FY04 President's Budget	Change from Baseline
Start of Formulation	Nov-99	--
Start of Implementation	Jun-01	--
Critical Design Review	Jan-02	--
Launch	Jan-04	--
Earth/Moon Flyby	Jan-05	--
Encounter	Jul-05	--
End of Mission	Aug-06	--
End of DA/Archive	Apr-06	--

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 2-4)

BUDGET				
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	Change	FY 2005 Comments
Solar System Exploration	1,039.1	1,315.9	-128.9	1,187.0 --
Development	308.3	292.4	-82.7	209.7 --
MESSENGER	86.7	37.8	-37.8	--
Deep Impact	57.7	12.9	-3.4	9.5 --
Dawn	36.3	124.9	-40.5	84.4 --
Small Development Projects	3.9	--	--	--
New Horizons (Pluto)	123.6	116.8	-1.0	115.8 --
Operations	298.9	308.2	-31.2	277.0 --
Research	258.5	323.7	+42.9	366.6 --
Technology and Advanced Concepts	173.5	391.6	-57.9	333.7 --

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

(p. ESA 2-8)

Schedule	FY 2005 President's Budget	Change from Baseline
Start of Formulation	Nov-99	--
Start of Implementation	Jun-01	--
Critical Design Review	Jan-02	--
Launch	Jan-04 (launch delayed to Dec-04)	--
Encounter	Jul-05	--
End of DA/Archive	Apr-06	--
End of Mission	Aug-05	--

(p. ESA 2-10) The total budget through BTC (before 2006) is listed as \$286.6.

Not listed as a line item from 2006 through 2012.

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-25) OM and DA \$5.3

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-23) OM and DA \$4.0

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-20) OM and DA \$3.0

Deep Impact References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Deep Impact / EPOXI (Discovery 7)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/deep_impact.htm.

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NASA. (2010) *Epoxi Comet Encounter Fact Sheet*. Nov 2, 2010. <https://epoxi.astro.umd.edu/7press/kits.shtml>, downloaded Mar 23, 2024.

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NASA. (2005) *Deep Impact/EPOXI*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2005-001A>, NSSDCA/COSPAR ID: 2005-001A, viewed Mar 23, 2024.

Mr. Monte Henderson, Mr. William Blume, *Deep Impact – A Review of the World's Pioneering Hypervelocity Impact Mission*, Procedia Engineering, Volume 103, 2015, Pages 165-172, ISSN 1877-7058, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.04.023>.

University of Maryland. *Deep Impact – Technology – Flyby Spacecraft*. <https://deepimpact.astro.umd.edu/tech/flyby.html>, viewed Mar 24, 2024.

Deep Space 1

Mission Attributes																																																			
Deep Space 1																																																			
Last Updated	9/13/2024																																																		
Definition	<table border="1"> <tr><td>COSPAR</td><td>1998-061 A</td></tr> <tr><td>Program</td><td>New Millennium</td></tr> <tr><td>Destination</td><td>Comet</td></tr> <tr><td>Success</td><td>Success</td></tr> <tr><td>Type</td><td>Flyby</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch Vehicle</td><td>Delta 7326</td></tr> </table>			COSPAR	1998-061 A	Program	New Millennium	Destination	Comet	Success	Success	Type	Flyby	Launch Vehicle	Delta 7326																																				
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Deep Space 1

- New Millennium Series – 1995, Office of Space Science established New Millennium Projects
- Goals included Development Areas of:

This material is the property of Colorado State University

- Autonomy
- Communications
- Microelectronics and modular architecture
- Multifunctional systems
- Later added: science instruments and microsystems, electronic systems, and mechanical systems
- The primary purpose is to demonstrate innovative technologies and architecture.
- Range of Small Projects: \$50-100M projects with shared launches to Medium Projects: \$100-150M system-level projects
- Mission life: 11 months (Technology Validation Report)
- Extension: extended 1 time from Sep 18, 1999, through Dec 18, 2001
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - MICAS (12.0 kg, 10.0 W) - Rodgers
 - PEPE (5.6 kg, 9.6 W) - Rayman
 - IPS/IDS (3.7 kg, 2.3 W) - Rayman
- Bus Volume: 2.5 x 2.1 x 1.7 m³ - DS1 Asteroid Flyby Press Kit (96 x 112 x 79 hexagonal subframe core)
- Deployments: 2
 - Solar array x 2
- Objectives:
 - Determine asteroid composition, (1)
 - Understand Braille’s spectral signatures, (2)
 - Determine if Braille contains any “prebiotic” materials, (3) and
 - Understand the asteroid’s morphology, (4) – DS1 Asteroid Flyby Press Kit

From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Manufacturer: JPL, Spectrum Astro (primary power system + Xe thrusters)
- DS1 was planned as a technology demonstrator (12 technologies, 2 of which were instruments) focused on solar electric propulsion and operated as a comet/asteroid flyby.
- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 486.3 kg (Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 121 kg
 - Fuel: 25 kg hydrazine + 58 kg Xenon
 - Space Vehicle: 365kg
 - Payload: 125 kg – advanced technologies
- S/A Area: 7.4 m²- Gunter (two 152 x 533 cm solar concentrator arrays – 16.2 m² – includes concentrators)
- Power (1 Au): 2500 W
- Power (station):
- Science
 - MICAS: Miniature Integrated Camera Spectrometer
 - PEPE: Plasma Experiment for Planetary Exploration

- IPS/IDS: Ion Propulsion System/Ion Diagnostic Subsystem

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-29)

Deep Space 1

Deep Space 1 was selected in FY 1996 as the first New Millennium Program mission. The technology to be validated will include solar electric propulsion, an advanced solar array, autonomous primary navigation, 3-D stack flight computer, and miniature imaging camera spectrometer. Spectrum Astro was selected in FY 1996 to integrate the spacecraft. DS 1 is expected to launch in July, 1998 on a Med-Lite-class Delta launch vehicle. The supplemental technology development line below contains funding for crosscutting technology development efforts previously managed by the Office of Space Access and Technology.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		26.3	28.9	18.1						73.3
SUPPLEMENTAL TECH DEV		7.2	6.1	1.6						14.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					3.6	2.1				5.7
LAUNCH SUPPORT		3.7	5.1	31.9						40.7
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT			0.1	0.2	0.1					0.4
TOTAL		37.2	40.2	51.8	3.7	2.1				135.0

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-30)

Deep Space 1

Deep Space 1 was selected in FY 1996 as the first New Millennium Program mission. The technology to be validated will include solar electric propulsion, an advanced solar array, autonomous primary navigation, and miniature imaging camera spectrometer. Spectrum Astro was selected in FY 1996 to integrate the spacecraft. DS 1 is expected to launch in July, 1998 on a Med-Lite-class Delta launch vehicle. The supplemental technology development line below contains funding for crosscutting technology development efforts previously managed by the Office of Space Access and Technology.

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	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		26.3	28.9	18.1						73.3
SUPPLEMENTAL TECH DEV		7.2	6.1	1.6						14.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					4.2	2.6				6.8
LAUNCH SUPPORT		7.7	5.0	31.9						44.6
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT			0.1	0.2	0.1					0.4
TOTAL		41.2	40.1	51.8	4.3	2.6				140.0

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SI-29)

Deep Space 1

Deep Space 1 was selected in FY 1996 as the first New Millennium Program mission. DS 1 launched in October, 1998 on a Med-Lite-class Delta launch vehicle. All technologies completed their validation by the end of FY 1999 and included solar electric propulsion, an advanced solar array, autonomous primary navigation, and a miniature imaging camera spectrometer. Given the opportunity to explore further, the DS 1 mission has been extended to validate twelve advanced technologies via an asteroid flyby and comet flyby. The supplemental technology development line below contains funding for crosscutting technology development efforts previously managed by the Office of Space Access and Technology.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		95.2	4.1							99.3
SUPPLEMENTAL TECH DEV (included in Dev)		114.0								114.0
MISSION OPERATIONS			8.1	3.0	4.2					15.3
DATA ANALYSIS			1.5	1.9	1.6	0.6				5.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT		45.4								45.4
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		0.3	0.1							0.4
TOTAL		140.9	13.8	4.9	5.8	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	166.0

Deep Space 1 (DS 1) References

- Krebs, Gunter D. *DS1 (Deep Space 1)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/ds-1.htm .
- NASA. *Deep Space 1*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1998-061A> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.
- NASA. (1999) *Deep Space 1 Asteroid Flyby – Press Kit*. Jul 1999. https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/press_kits/ds1asteroid.pdf , downloaded Mar 11, 2024.

Galileo

Mission Attributes Galileo	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR Program	1989-084B
Destination	Jupiter
Success	Success
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	STS 34
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	51.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	125.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	146.7
Initial Mission Life (years)	8.1
Realized Mission Life (years)	13.9
Extended Mission Life (years)	5.8
Phase A - Award	10/1/1977
PDR	
CDR	
Launch	10/18/1989
On Station	12/8/1995
Extend Mission	12/1/1997
End Mission	9/21/2003
Cost	
Start	1978
Launch	1989
Budget \$	410.099
Realized \$	1639
Budget Schedule	43
Realized Schedule	136
Then \$	\$ 1,783.10
Development	\$ 902.30
Launch	\$ 323.90
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 468.50
Extended	\$ 88.40
NSII 2023\$	\$ 5,323.70
Development	\$ 3,218.20
Launch	\$ 946.00
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 1,005.10
Extended	\$ 154.40
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 3,983.50
Development	\$ 2,303.70
Launch	\$ 716.80
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 826.20
Extended	\$ 136.80
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	2380
Fuel	925
S/V Dry	1289
S/V Bus	1180
S/V Payload	84.07
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	112.1
Objectives	9
Deployments	4
Payload	
Instruments	12
Mass (kg)	112.1
Power (W, ave)	87.4
RTG or S/A	RTG
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	570
Perihelion	493
Aphelion	410
S/A Area (m ²)	-
S/A Type	-
Blank	-

Galileo

- Original Plan: Start of project 1978, launch January 1982, EoM 1987.
- Delayed launch: 7 years with 10-year EoM delay (3 years added to mission)
- Original estimated cost: \$410.1M
- Estimate 1987 cost: \$1362.5 M – increase due to shuttle launch delays, changes to the upper stage, and the Challenger accident.
- Original mission cruise: 2 years, revised cruise: 4 years VEEGA trajectory transfer – extends cruise from 24 to 72 months (+4 years) – used Mars to shorten this (I think)
- Original Operations: 22 months of Jupiter and 4 satellites
- Delays: expanded the scope of scientific investigations
 - The shuttle was delayed from 1982 to 1984.
 - Delay split the mission into two spacecraft: a primary (40-month cruise) and a probe (28-month cruise) mission, to coincide with arrival.
 - 1981 – due to cost increases, the three-stage IUS was replaced with Centaur – returned the mission to a single space vehicle
 - 1982 NASA cancelled the Centaur upper stage and replaced it with a two-stage IUS –

resulting in VEEGA launch trajectory transfer.

- In 1982, Congress directed NASA to use the Centaur upper stage in late 1982.
- 1986 Challenger accident (January), NASA cancels the liquid stage Centaur for safety reasons, returning to the IUS (safer option).
- The design features a dual-spin mechanism: one fixed and one rotating section.
- JPL is considered the most complex mission to date.
- Mission life: 8 years 1 month
- Extension: extended three times
- Status: Successful
 - Operations prime: 12/8/1995 - Dec 1997: EoM 9/21/2003 (deorbited – out of fuel)
- Instruments (17: 12 Space Vehicle, 7 Probe)
 - IDS ()
 - DDS (4.2 kg, 5.4 W)
 - EPD (10.5 kg, 10.1 W)
 - HIC (8.33 kg, 2.8 W)
 - MAG (7.0 kg, 3.9 W)
 - NIMS (18.8 kg, 12 W)
 - PPR (5.2 kg, 3.8 W)
 - PLS (13.2 kg, 10.7 W)
 - PWS (7.14 kg, 9.8 W)
 - RS ()
 - SSI (28 kg, 23 W)
 - UVS/EUVS (9.7 kg, 5.9 W)
- Bus Volume: 6.15 x 9.0 x 4.6 m³
- Deployments: 4
 - Probe
 - HGA (failed to open completely)
 - 2 booms (MAG and RTG)
- Objectives:
 - Investigate the circulation and dynamics of the Jovian atmosphere, (1)
 - Characterize the structure of the atmosphere, (2)
 - Characterize the morphology, geology, and physical state of the Galilean satellites, (3)
 - Investigate the composition and distribution of surface minerals of GS, (4)
 - Determine the gravitational and magnetic fields and dynamic properties of GS, (5)
 - Study the atmospheres, ionospheres, and extended gas clouds of GS, (6)
 - Study the interaction of the Jovian magnetosphere with the GS, (7) and
 - Characterize the vector magnetic field and energy spectra, composition, and angular distribution of energetic particles and plasma. (8)
 - Deliver probe and relay data. (+1)
- Manufacturer: JPL
- Launch mass: 2562 kg (STS launch – 2380 NSSDCA)

- Ballast (unaccounted mass): 166 kg (STS cradle)
- Fuel: 925 kg
- Space Vehicle: 1180 kg
 - Payload: 112.07 kg
 - Probe: 339 kg
 - Instruments: 112.07 kg
- Power: RTG (provided by DoE)
- Power (1 Au): 570 W (BoL)
- Power (station): 493 W – 410 W (EoM)
- Science
 - IDS: Composition of the Jovian Atmosphere
 - DDS: Dust Detection System
 - EPD: Energetic Particles Detector
 - HIC: Heavy Ion Counter
 - MAG: Magnetometer
 - NIMS: Near Infrared Mapping Spectrometer
 - PPR: Photopolarimeter-Radiometer
 - PLS: Plasma Detector
 - PWS: Plasma Wave Spectrometer
 - RS: Radio Science: Celestial Mechanics
 - SSI: Solid-State Imaging
 - UVS/EUVS: Ultraviolet Spectrometer and Extreme Ultraviolet Spectrometer

NASA Budget Requests	Spacecraft	Experiments	Ground Ops	STS Ops
1980 (p. RD 5-4) 1978 actual	\$11.660	\$7.590	\$1.700	\$0.900
1981 (p. RD 5-5) 1979 actual	\$54.083	\$18.714	\$5.903	\$2.400
1982 (p. RD 5-5) 1980 actual	\$89.222	\$19.390	\$7.488	\$8.300
1983 (p. RD 5-5) 1981 actual	\$47.700	\$8.800	\$6.600	\$2.400
1984 (p. RD 5-4) 1982 actual	\$90.500	\$13.500	\$11.700	\$8.200
1985 (p. RD 5-4) 1983 actual	\$67.524	\$8.612	\$15.464	\$12.600
1986 (p. RD 5-5) 1984 actual	\$50.578	\$9.375	\$19.547	\$37.200
1987 (p. RD 5-7) 1985 actual	\$27.745	\$10.275	\$20.780	\$36.600
1988 (p. RD 5-5) 1986 actual	\$34.175	\$14.215	\$15.810	\$10.900
1989 (p. RD 5-5) 1987 actual	\$45.715	\$11.383	\$14.102	\$11.800
1990 (p. RD 5-5) 1988 actuals	\$31.377	\$9.078	\$11.445	\$31.200
1991 (p. RD 5-5) 1989 actuals	\$34.880	\$13.670	\$24.850	\$85.500
1992 (RD 5-1) 1990 actuals	\$17.127			

Upper Stage
NASA 1989 Budget Request (p. RD 2-9)

A:\SFACND.DOC										
FY 89 CONGRESSIONAL BUDGET BACKUP										
UPPER STAGES PROGRAM CONTENT										
DETAIL PROGRAM CONTENT										
NDA	PRIOR	FY87	FY88	FY89	FY90	FY91	FY92	FY93	FY 88 CONG TOTAL	FY 89 CONG TOTAL
FY89 CONGRESSIONAL	830.9	160.5	159.7	106.6	68.6	68.3	42.8	2.0		
CHANGE APPROP. INTEG.		(4.4)	(0.2)	(0.3)						
CHANGE		(4.6)	(0.5)	(0.6)						
FY89 CONGRESSIONAL	826.5	156.1	159.2	106.0	74.8	64.0	47.7	68.9	1,025.8	1,497.5
DOTAE	558.3	111.2	116.0	81.7	51.5	51.0	32.7	58.2	440.8	440.8
OPERATIONS	516.3	144.8	138.3	122.5	74.3	51.0	32.7	58.2	1,081.8	998.9
IUS	167.2	93.6	124.3	114.0	52.0	26.1	30.7	37.8	679.0	585.3
TDRS C 6/88			0.2	1.6					1.8	1.8
TDRS D 2/89			38.8	9.0					48.3	47.3
TDRS E/F 10/89			28.2	35.5	28.2	17.5			122.6	124.8
TDRS G 10/89			8.0	15.4	24.2	20.1	9.7	3.8	101.2	25.2
GALILEO 10/89			9.2	6.4	24.2	20.1	9.7	3.8	82.4	70.4
MAGELLAN 4/89			8.0	15.4	24.2	20.1	9.7	3.8	172.1	115.2
ULYSSES 10/90			11.4	2.9	30.4	38.0	21.0	6.3	117.0	95.2
OTHER			75.8	35.4	24.6	5.2	2.8	1.4	158.6	115.0
MOD KIT FOR PLANETARY B/U			(8.3)	(0.2)	(0.2)					
TDRS			18.0	44.0	4.5	17.9	14.2	8.7	115.5	98.6
MARS OBSERVER 8/92			12.3	22.1	4.5	17.9	14.2	8.7	86.9	63.5
MOD KIT INCL ABOVE			(4.3)	(0.0)	(0.0)	(0.0)			(19.9)	
ACTS CLUSTER			5.7	21.9	(0.0)	(12.8)	(8.9)	(3.6)	27.6	7.0
PAM			13.7	.2	.3	.2	.2	.2	15.2	66.2
SPIP			10.2	7.1	9.8	8.0	8.0	9.0	70.0	24.1
CENTAUR			207.2						207.2	222.7

NASA 1991 Budget Request (p. RD 2-8)

UPPER STAGES PROGRAM CONTENT									
Launch Vehicle Date Prior									
Total	FY89	FY90	FY91	BTC	EAC				
Development	3.3	0.4							
Operations	128.3	84.2	91.3						
IUS	80.0	35.9	45.4						
TDRS-E & F	1/914								
TDRS-D	12/92	86.2	1.3	4.5	22.5	14.8	129.3		
Galileo	9/89	39.8	16.2	19.0	0.9		72.9		
Magellan	4/89	36.2	31.3	0.7			68.4		
Ulysses	10/90	54.2	26.3	7.7	14.4		102.6		
Titan-to-STS Mod Kit		1.0	2.9	4.0	3.0		10.9		
Other IUS		1.7	1.1	3.0	12.0				
TDRS		66.4	34.6	38.4	27.3	17.1	184.5	At Congressional Cap	
Mars Observer	9/92	38.9	16.4	20.1	18.1	9.2	112.2		
ACTS	9/92	27.1	18.4	9.3	9.2	7.9	71.9		
Centauro					6.3	136.7			
CRAF	8/95				6.3	64.1	70.4		
Cassini	4/96					72.6	72.6		
SPIP		13.5	9.0	12.3					

Mission Operations

NASA Budget Requests	Operations Actual	Previous Year	Request Year
1992 (p. RD 5-10) 1990 actual	\$37.315	\$44.200	\$57.700
1993 (p. RD 5-10) 1991 actual	\$48.074	\$57.700	\$63.000
1994 (p. RD 5-10) 1992 actual	\$57.000	\$59.429	\$57.600
1995 (p. RD 5-10) 1993 actual	\$59.429	\$59.900	\$70.700
1996 (p. RD 5-10) 1994 actual	\$59.400	\$70.700	\$75.100
1997 (p. RD 5-10) 1995 actual	\$70.700	\$71.700	\$66.400
1998 (p. RD 5-10) 1996 actual	\$71.500	\$64.400	\$29.800
1999 (p. RD 5-10) 1997 actual	\$64.400	\$29.800	\$16.000

OMO – Other Mission Operations (in 2000 Budget, all mission operations except for HST lumped into a single cost account line item). There were over 20 operational missions from 2000 to 2003. Using the 1999 Budget Request and including the Mission Cost breakout for FY 1997 actuals, removing HST operations, the total budget for 20+ mission operations is \$341.9. Galileo was \$64.4 or

18.8% of the 1997 actual costs. This is inconsistent with the projected 1998 and 1999 budgets, as well as the decreasing trend of Mission Operations from 1998 to 2003.

end of prime mission - start of extended			
2000 (p. RD 5-10) 1998 OMO	\$136.4	@ 9.65%	= \$13.162
2001 (p. RD 5-10) 1999 actual	\$115.2	@ 9.65%	= \$11.120
2002 (p. RD 5-10) 2000 actual	\$76.2	@ 9.65%	= \$7.353
2003 (p. RD 5-10) 2001 actual	\$122.8	@ 9.65%	= \$11.850
2003 (p. RD 5-10) 2002 predicted	\$174.8	@ 9.65%	= \$16.868
2003 (p. RD 5-10) 2003 predicted - ¾ of annual for Sept EoM	\$385.2	@ 9.65%	= \$27.879

Alternate approach: Using the 1999 Budget Request and including the Mission Cost breakout for FY 1998 “projected” costs, removing HST operations, the total budget for 20+ mission operations is \$308.1. Galileo was \$29.8 or 9.65% of the 1998 projected costs. This is consistent with the projected 1998 and 1999 budgets, which slightly underpredict the actual costs compared to the estimated costs.

There is significant cost development of the Centaur G-prime upper stage for Galileo and ISPM (mid-1986 launch). Air Force and NASA equally share the development costs. The failure of Challenger rendered the viability of the liquid-state Centaur G-prime for STS launches moot.

The 1984 Budget included \$106.7 million for the procurement of two Prime-Gs for Galileo and ISPM, with an additional purchase for a third for VRM, with a 1988 launch. Language supports the procurement of 4 units.

The 1983 Budget included the IUS launch for Galileo, but this was changed by Congress, with a cost of \$72.0. As a result, the IUS was then terminated and replaced by Centaur-G.

Reference: Space Exploration – Cost, Schedule, and Performance of NASA’s Galileo Mission to Jupiter, GAO Fact Sheet, May 1988, for details of funding and launch.

Galileo References

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NASA. (1995). *Galileo Jupiter Arrival (PDF) (Press Kit)*. NASA/ Jet Propulsion Laboratory. December 1995. https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/press_kits/gllarpk.pdf , downloaded Mar 4, 2024.

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Genesis

Mission Attributes Genesis																																																			
Last Updated		9/13/2024																																																	
Definition		<table border="1"> <tr><td>COSPAR</td><td>2001-034A</td></tr> <tr><td>Program</td><td>Discovery 5</td></tr> <tr><td>Destination</td><td>L1</td></tr> <tr><td>Success</td><td>Success</td></tr> <tr><td>Type</td><td>Sample Return</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch Vehicle</td><td>Delta 7326</td></tr> </table>		COSPAR	2001-034A	Program	Discovery 5	Destination	L1	Success	Success	Type	Sample Return	Launch Vehicle	Delta 7326																																				
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Genesis

- Discovery 5
- Mission life: 31 months with 24-month sample collection (initial plan)
- Extension: none
- Status: Successful
 - Sample returned 9/8/2004.

- Instruments – similar instrument designs to Ulysses (Genesis instrument data not located)
 - SWIM (5.56 kg, 4.0 W)
 - ELM (6.7 kg, 5.5 W)
 - 5 solar wind collector arrays
 - Solar wind concentrator
- Bus Volume: 2.3 x 2.0 x 2.0 m³
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 2
 - Sample capture (open and close)
 - Sample return (re-entry and parachute)
- Objectives:
 - Isotopic abundances of sufficient precision to address planetary science problems, (1)
 - Major improvement in our knowledge of the average chemical composition of the solar system, (2)
 - Independent compositional data on 3 diverse kinds of solar wind, (3) and
 - A reservoir of solar material used in conjunction with advanced analytical techniques available to 21st-century scientists. (4)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

- Gold Foil Collector
- Solar Wind Concentrator
- Wafers and Collectors
- Ion and Electron Monitors

From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Drogue parachute and capsule crashed into the Utah desert landing zone. After the recovery effort, the samples arrived at the Johnson Space Center in September or early October 2004.
- Spacecraft placed in hibernation on Dec 2, 2004, and is in heliocentric orbit.
- Control: Spin stabilized, 1.6 rpm
- Design: Main spacecraft with attached Sample Return Capsule (SRC)
- Launch mass: 636 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 52.4 kg
 - Fuel: 142.0 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 494 kg
 - SRC: 205 kg
 - Structure: 98.6 kg
 - Mechanism: 17.6 kg
 - Power: 36.5 kg
 - C&DH: 11.9
 - Thermal: 15.9
 - ACS: 10.0
 - Propulsion: 36.6
 - Communications: 10.1 kg
- S/A Area: 3.4 m²
- Power (1 Au): 265 W
- Science
 - SWIM: Solar Wind Ion Monitor
 - ELM: Electron Monitor
 - Four listed “flight instruments” – no data available

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

Genesis

In October 1997 NASA selected Genesis as the fifth Discovery mission. The Genesis mission is designed to collect samples of the charged particles in the solar wind and return them to Earth laboratories for detailed analysis. It is led by Dr. Donald Burnett from the California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA. JPL will provide the payload and project management, while the spacecraft will be provided by Lockheed Martin Astronautics of Denver, CO. Due for launch in January 2001, it will return the samples of isotopes of oxygen, nitrogen, the noble gases, and other elements to an airborne capture in the Utah desert in August 2003. Such data are crucial for improving theories about the origin of the Sun and the planets, which formed from the same primordial dust cloud.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B	11.4									11.4
DEVELOPMENT	33.0	65.1	33.2	7.3						138.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT	17.8	17.0								34.8
MISSION OPS				2.0	1.2	1.4				4.6
DATA ANALYSIS				8.2	5.2	5.5	2.8	2.1	1.8	25.6
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT				0.5	0.5	0.5				1.5
TOTAL	44.4	82.0	50.2	18.0	6.9	7.4	2.8	2.1	1.8	216.5
(ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE FTEs)		(5)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(4)	(4)		
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M)		0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5		

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-27)

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B	11.4									11.4
DEVELOPMENT	115.9	62.3	25.5							203.7
MISSION OPS			3.4	4.0	4.5					11.9
DATA ANALYSIS			2.9	2.4	2.4	2.8	2.1	1.5	0.3	14.4
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT			0.5	0.5	0.5					1.5
TOTAL	127.3	62.3	32.3	6.9	7.4	2.8	2.1	1.5	0.3	242.9

SI-27

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-46)

Genesis <http://genesismission.jpl.nasa.gov/>

Objective: “To capture a piece of the Sun and return it to Earth” – To provide a sample of the solar wind, helping answer fundamental questions about the exact composition of the Sun and the chemical diversity present at the birth of our solar system.

Salient Features:

- Principal Investigator: Don Burnett, California Institute of Technology
- Lead Center: JPL
- Spacecraft: Lockheed Martin; Launch vehicle: Delta 2
- Orbit about the Sun-Earth L1 point
- Science Instruments: Collector Arrays and Concentrator
- 2 Enabling Instruments: Electron Monitor and Ion Monitor
- Launched August 8, 2001; Sample Return to Earth: September 2004
- Minimum Sample Collection Time Required: 22 Months

Science:

- Measure Elemental & Isotopic Abundance’s of Solar Wind Ions
- Provide a Reservoir of Solar Matter for Future Analysis

Genesis Life Cycle Cost Data:

	Prior	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	FY 06	FY 07	BTC	Total
Pre-development	189.7	29.6	10.2	10.0	9.3	3.0	1.9	1.1	0.2	255.0
Development	11.5									11.5
Launch Services	130.7	20.8								151.5
Operations	47.5	1.2								48.7
Data Analysis		3.4	6.2	7.2	6.2	0.4				23.4
		4.2	4.0	2.8	3.1	2.6	1.9	1.1	0.2	19.9
(Est. Civil Servant FTE)		2	1	1	1	1	1	1		

Key Milestones:

	FY 2002 Budget Date	FY 2003 Budget Date	Comment
Launch	7/01	8/01	Launched August 8, 2001; sample return September 2004

SAT 1-46

Genesis References

- Krebs, Gunter D. **Genesis (Discovery 5)**. Gunter’s Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/genesis.htm.
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Grail – A

Grail – A/B

Mission Attributes Grail-A	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2011-046A
Program	Discovery 11A
Destination	Lunar
Success	Success
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7920
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	44.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	46.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	44.5
Initial Mission Life (years)	0.7
Realized Mission Life (years)	1.3
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.6
Phase A - Award	1/15/2008
PDR	11/11/2008
CDR	11/12/2009
Launch	9/10/2011
On Station	12/11/2011
Extend Mission	5/29/2012
End Mission	12/17/2012
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	306
Fuel	108
S/V Dry	198
S/V Bus	132.6
S/V Payload	65.4
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	1
Objectives	6
Deployments	2
Cost	
Start	2007
Launch	2011
Budget \$	213.5
Realized \$	224.35
Budget Schedule	44
Realized Schedule	44
Then \$	\$ 243.65
Development	\$ 147.95
Launch	\$ 76.40
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 9.65
Extended	\$ 9.65
NSII 2023\$	\$ 327.15
Development	\$ 200.40
Launch	\$ 101.95
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 12.40
Extended	\$ 12.40
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 312.25
Development	\$ 190.85
Launch	\$ 97.80
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 11.80
Extended	\$ 11.80
Payload	
Instruments	2
Mass (kg)	65
Power (W, ave)	191.2
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	700
Perihelion	-
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m ²)	7.2
S/A Type	Fixed
Blank	-

- Two satellites, mirror images of each other
- Based on XSS-11 satellite design
- Mission life: 9 months with a 3-month cruise
- Extension: Extended 1 time: July – December (6 months) 2012
- Status: Successful
 - Operations (4 years) – 12/11/2011 through July 2012
 - Extended Operations – July 2012 – December 2012 (6 months)
- Instruments
 - LGRS (unknown: assumed balance of dry mass – bus mass)
 - MoonKam (unknown: included with LGRS)
- Bus Volume: 1.0 m³
- Deployments: 2
 - Solar array x 2
- Objectives:
 - Determine the structure of the lunar interior from crust to core, (1)
 - Advance understanding of the thermal evolution of the Moon, (2) and
 - Extend knowledge gained on the internal structure and thermal evolution of the moon to other terrestrial planets, (3)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Grail – B

Mission Attributes Grail-B	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2011-046B
Program	Discovery 11B
Destination	Lunar
Success	Success
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7920
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	44.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	46.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	44.5
Initial Mission Life (years)	0.7
Realized Mission Life (years)	1.3
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.6
Phase A - Award	1/15/2008
PDR	11/11/2008
CDR	11/12/2009
Launch	9/10/2011
On Station	12/11/2011
Extend Mission	5/29/2012
End Mission	12/17/2012
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	306
Fuel	108
S/V Dry	198
S/V Bus	132.6
S/V Payload	65.4
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	1
Objectives	6
Deployments	2
Cost	
Start	2007
Launch	2011
Budget \$	213.5
Realized \$	224.35
Budget Schedule	44
Realized Schedule	44
Then \$	\$ 243.65
Development	\$ 147.95
Launch	\$ 76.40
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 9.65
Extended	\$ 9.65
NSII 2023\$	\$ 327.15
Development	\$ 200.40
Launch	\$ 101.95
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 12.40
Extended	\$ 12.40
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 312.25
Development	\$ 190.85
Launch	\$ 97.80
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 11.80
Extended	\$ 11.80
Payload	
Instruments	3
Mass (kg)	65
Power (W, ave)	191.2
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	700
Perihelion	-
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m ²)	7.2
S/A Type	Fixed
Blank	-

Not published in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 306 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Fuel: 108.0 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 198.0 kg
 - Payload: 65.4 kg
 - Bus: 132.6 kg (baseline XSS-11 is 100 kg. Tank size increases were an option. RWA increase in size)
- S/A Area: 7.2 m²
- Power (1 Au): 700 W
- Power (station): 700 W
- Science
 - LGRS: Lunar Gravity Ranging System
 - MK: MoonKam

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. SC-113)

FY 2010 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2008		FY 2009 Enacted	FY 2010	FY 2011				BTC	LCC TOTAL
		Actual	Enacted			FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014		
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	1.2	67.0	122.4	124.1	104.8	41.4	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	465.6
Formulation	1.2	27.0	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.5
Development / Implementation	0.0	40.0	100.1	124.1	104.5	27.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	396.4
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	13.7	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.7
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	1.2	0.0	122.4	122.8	113.1	24.9	5.7	=	0.0	=	390.0
Formulation	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	1.2
Development / Implementation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	--
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	--
Other	0.0	0.0	122.4	122.8	113.1	24.9	5.7	--	0.0	--	388.8
Changes from FY 2009 Request	0.0	67.0	0.0	1.3	-8.3	16.5	-0.9	=	0.0	=	75.6
Formulation	0.0	27.0	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	49.3
Development / Implementation	0.0	40.0	100.1	124.1	104.5	27.7	0.0	--	0.0	--	396.4
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	13.7	4.7	--	0.0	--	18.7
Other	0.0	0.0	-122.4	-122.8	-113.1	-24.9	-5.6	--	0.0	--	-388.8

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. Planet - 31)

FY 2011 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2009		FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012				BTC	LCC TOTAL
		Actual	Enacted			FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015		
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	68.3	152.9	124.1	104.8	41.4	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	496.2
Formulation	28.2	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.5
Development / Implementation	40.1	130.6	124.1	104.5	27.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	427.0
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	13.7	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.7
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	68.3	122.4	124.1	104.8	41.4	4.7	0.0	=	0.0	=	465.6
Formulation	28.2	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	50.5
Development / Implementation	40.1	100.1	124.1	104.5	27.7	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	396.5
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	13.7	4.7	0.0	--	0.0	--	18.7
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	-0.1
Changes from FY 2010 Request	0.0	30.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	=	0.0	=	30.6
Formulation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	--
Development / Implementation	0.0	30.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	30.5
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	--
Other	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--	0.1

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. MP-67)

2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2010		FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013				BTC	LCC TOTAL
		FY 2010	FY 2011			FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016		
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	221.2	124.1	=	40.5	4.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	=	=
FY 2011 Costs			105.4								
CSLE				0.3	0.3						
2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate	221.2	124.1	105.4	40.8	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	496.2
Formulation	50.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.6
Development	170.6	124.1	105.1	27.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	427.0
Operations	0.0	0.0	0.3	13.7	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.7

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-23)

FY 2013 BUDGET

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Notional			
	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	192.0	172.6	189.6	242.2	255.6	193.8	134.3
Discovery Research	17.4	17.5	16.9	15.9	16.1	16.3	16.3
Discovery Future Missions	4.5	60.7	138.3	197.4	195.5	163.9	96.2
Discovery Management	7.5	9.0	11.3	11.8	12.1	12.4	12.5
Strofio		6.2	1.6	0.9	1.3	0.7	0.8
GRAIL	103.4	29.8	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dawn	14.8	14.3	8.1	10.1	11.3	0.4	8.5
MESSENGER	22.7	34.9	4.6	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ASPERA-3	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
Deep Impact	5.3	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Stardust	7.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Moon Mineralogy Mapper	1.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	16.9				
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	9.8%				

NASA Budget requests are consistent with PEBD data.

Grail References

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Insight

Mission Attributes		Insight	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition			
COSPAR Program	2018-042A	Discovery 12	
Destination	Mars		
Success	Success		
Type	Lander		
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	43.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	69.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	70.1		
Initial Mission Life (years)	2.0		
Realized Mission Life (years)	4.6		
Extended Mission Life (years)	2.1		
Phase A - Award	8/1/2012		
PDR	8/1/2013		
CDR	5/1/2014		
Launch	5/5/2018		
On Station	11/26/2018		
Extend Mission	11/24/2020		
End Mission	12/15/2022		
Cost			
Start	2011		
Launch	2018		
Budget \$	425		
Realized \$	633.1		
Budget Schedule			
Realized Schedule			
Then \$	\$ 822.80		
Development	\$ 596.40		
Launch	\$ 163.40		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 36.70		
Extended	\$ 26.30		
NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,015.10		
Development	\$ 745.80		
Launch	\$ 199.30		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 41.60		
Extended	\$ 28.40		
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 973.00		
Development	\$ 712.90		
Launch	\$ 192.00		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 40.90		
Extended	\$ 27.20		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass	721	Payload	
Fuel	67	Instruments	
S/V Dry	608	Mass (kg)	
S/V Bus		Power (W, ave)	
S/V Payload	48.3	RTG or S/A	
Probe/Rover	-	S/A Power	
Cruise	-	BoL 1 Au	
Lander	-	Perihelion	
Aeroshield +	-	Aphelion	
Bus Volume (m ³)	2.06	S/A Area (m ²)	
Objectives	5	S/A Type	
Deployments	3	Blank	

Insight

- The 2010 AO occurred in August 2012, with a launch in March 2016.
- Missed launch window due to primary instrument design issues (SEIS had a design flaw in the French-built seismometer, which prevented maintaining the vacuum inside the instrument. The estimated delay cost was \$153.8)
- Press Kit – US investment \$813.8, including \$163.4 for launch vehicle and launch services, and \$180 mission from European Partners for the SEIS (Seismometer Investigation) and HP3 (heat flow investigation). Additionally, JPL invested \$18.5M in Mars Cube One
- Initial Budget \$425 less launch vehicle for 720-day mission
- Mission life: 1 year cruise and 3-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
- Extension: Mission extended one time, Dec 2020, last communication Dec 15, 2022
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - SEIS (29.5 kg, 8.5 W)
 - IDA (8.5 kg, - W)
 - HP3 (3.0 kg, 2 W)
 - RISE (7.3, 78 W)
 - Payload – 2 x MarCO 6U cubesats
- Bus Volume: 1.56 dia x 1.08m³

- Deployments: 2
 - Solar array x 2 @ 2 m dia each
- Objectives:
 - Determine the size, composition, and physical state of the core, (1)
 - Determine the thickness and structure of the crust, (2)
 - Determine the composition and structure of the mantle, (3)
 - Determine the thermal state of the interior by measuring the magnitude, rate, and geographical distribution of the internal seismic activity and rate of meteorite impacts on the surface, (4) and
 - Deliver MarCO (+1)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not listed in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Lander mission
- Launch mass: 721 kg.
 - Ballast (Adapter, unaccounted mass, MarCo): 46 kg
 - MarCO: 13.5 kg (each x2)
 - Fuel: 67 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 694kg
 - Launder: 358 kg
 - Aeroshell: 189 kg
 - Cruise Stage: 79 (from mass at re-entry)
 - Power (+ ballast, remaining mass): 44.2
- S/A Area: 7.4 m²
- Power (1 Au): 1300 W
- Power (station): 600-700 W
- Science
 - SEIS: Seismic Experiment for Interior Structure
 - RISE: Rotation and Interior Structure Experiment
 - HP3: Heat Flow and Physical Properties Package
 - IDS: Instrument Deployment System
 - APSS: Auxiliary Payload Sensor Suite
 - LaRRI: Laser Retro-Reflector of Insight

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-18)

FY 2014 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Notional			
	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	42.1	--	193.3	175.2	116.5	15.2	10.6
Change from FY 2012	--	--	151.2				
Percentage change from FY 2012	--	--	359.1%				

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-14)

FY 2015 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Request FY 2015	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2013	FY 2014		FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019		
Formulation	65.1	33.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	98.9
Development/Implementation	0.0	88.9	203.3	170.0	79.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	541.8
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.4	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	34.4
2014 MPAR LCC Estimate	65.1	122.7	203.3	170.0	92.0	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	675.1
Total Budget	65.1	122.7	193.3	170.0	92.1	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	665.1
Change from FY 2014				-23.3						
Percentage change from FY 2014				-12.1%						

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-13)

FY 2016 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Request FY 2016	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2014	FY 2015		FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020		
Formulation	98.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	98.9
Development/Implementation	88.9	203.3	170.0	79.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	541.8
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.4	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.4
2015 MPAR LCC Estimate	187.8	203.3	170.0	92.0	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	675.1
Total Budget	187.8	203.3	170.0	92.1	13.3	8.7	9.0	9.0	0.0	693.1
Change from FY 2015				-77.9						
Percentage change from FY 2015				-45.8%						

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-16)

FY 2017 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Request FY 2017	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2015	FY 2016		FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021		
Formulation	98.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	98.9
Development/Implementation	292.2	170.0	79.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	541.8
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	12.5	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.5
2016 MPAR LCC Estimate	391.1	170.0	92.1	13.3	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	675.2
Total Budget	391.1	170.0	92.1	13.3	8.7	9.0	9.0	0.0	0.0	693.1
Change from FY 2016				-78.8						
Percentage change from FY 2016				-85.6%						

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-15)

FY 2018 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Request FY 2018	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2016	FY 2017		FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022		
Formulation	98.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	98.9
Development/Implementation	463.2	92.1	32.3	86.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	673.5
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.5	22.3	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	56.6
2017 MPAR LCC Estimate	561.1	92.1	32.3	109.4	22.3	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	829.0
Total Budget	561.1	92.1	32.3	109.4	22.3	11.8	9.0	9.0	0.0	846.9
Change from FY 2017				77.1						
Percentage change from FY 2017				238.7%						

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-32)

FY 2019 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Request FY 2019	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2017	FY 2018		FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023		
Formulation	98.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	98.9
Development/Implementation	554.3	32.3	86.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	673.5
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	22.5	22.3	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	56.6
2018 MPAR LCC Estimate	653.1	32.3	109.4	22.3	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	828.9
Total Budget	653.1	32.3	109.4	22.3	11.8	9.0	9.0	9.0	0.0	856.9
Change from FY 2018				-87.1						
Percentage change from FY 2018				-79.6%						

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-48)

FY 2020 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Request FY 2020	Notional			
	FY 2018	FY 2019		FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024
InSight	74.3	--	11.8	9.0	9.0	9.0	0.0
Strofiio	0.6	--	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.7
International Mission Contributions (IMC)	2.2	--	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.0
Planetary Missions Program Office	11.4	--	15.5	14.6	16.4	16.5	16.5
Discovery Future	28.0	--	15.1	7.7	103.1	273.6	290.1
Discovery Research	6.7	--	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
Dawn	11.1	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Planetary SmallSats	0.0	--	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Mars-moon Exploration with Gamma rays and NEUTRONS (MEGANE)	0.7	--	6.4	5.0	1.8	0.7	0.7
Total Budget	134.9	--	71.0	58.1	152.0	321.4	329.0

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-49)

FY 2021 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2019	Enacted FY 2020	Request FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025
Strofiio	0.9	--	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.8
International Mission Contributions (IMC)	3.1	--	11.0	16.5	16.6	15.9	32.6
Planetary Missions Program Office	13.2	--	15.0	16.1	16.2	16.2	16.2
Discovery Future	13.0	--	67.0	122.5	307.5	450.4	359.9
Discovery Research	7.7	--	7.9	8.8	8.6	8.6	8.6
Dawn	0.2	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Planetary SmallSats	4.9	--	19.7	28.6	30.0	30.0	30.0
Mars-moon Exploration with Gamma rays and NEUTRONS (MEGANE)	3.9	--	9.7	5.9	1.0	0.6	1.8
Total Budget	69.8	--	143.5	208.3	389.6	522.5	450.9

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-59)

Insight – Op Plan FY 2020 - \$13.6

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

Insight – Op Plan FY 2020 - \$14.9

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-66)

Insight – Op Plan FY 2020 - \$11.4

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Juno

Mission Attributes		Juno	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition			
COSPAR	2011-040A		
Program	New Frontiers 2		
Destination	Jupiter		
Success	Success		
Type	Orbiter		
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	46.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	72.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	73.3		
Initial Mission Life (years)	6.0		
Realized Mission Life (years)	13.4		
Extended Mission Life (years)	7.2		
Phase A - Award	5/1/2005		
PDR	5/1/2008		
CDR	4/1/2009		
Launch	5/8/2011		
On Station	7/6/2016		
Extend Mission	6/30/2017		
End Mission	9/13/2024		
Cost			
Start	2001		
Launch	2006		
Budget \$	700		
Realized \$	1114.1		
Budget Schedule	51		
Realized Schedule	51		
Then \$	\$ 1,304.50		
Development	\$ 726.20		
Launch	\$ 190.40		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 167.80		
Extended	\$ 220.10		
NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,669.80		
Development	\$ 995.90		
Launch	\$ 254.10		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 208.00		
Extended	\$ 211.80		
PCEPL 2023\$	\$ 1,594.00		
Development	\$ 943.90		
Launch	\$ 243.80		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 200.20		
Extended	\$ 206.10		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass	3625		
Fuel	2032		
S/V Dry	1593		
S/V Bus	1438.14		
S/V Payload	154.86		
Probe/Rover	-		
Cruise	-		
Lander	-		
Aeroshield +	-		
Bus Volume (m ³)	33.65		
Objectives	5		
Deployments	4		
Payload			
Instruments	10		
Mass (kg)	154.86		
Power (W, ave)	124.4		
RTG or S/A	S/A		
S/A Power	-		
BoL 1 Au	14000		
Perihelion	500		
Aphelion	400		
S/A Area (m ²)	60.4		
S/A Type	3-articulated		
Blank	-		

Juno

- Mission life: 5-year cruise and 1-year prime mission (Primary mission: 6 years)
- Extension: extended through 2025
- Status: Currently Operational
 - Operations (5 years) – 6/30/2017
 - Extended Operations – 7/1/2017 through current
- Instruments
 - MAG (24.33 kg, 19.0 W) – FGM (15.25 kg, 12.5 W) and SHM (9.08 kg, 6.5 W)
 - MWR (42.13 kg, 32.6 W)
 - Gravity Science (unknown – communications system)
 - JEDI (21.6 kg, 9.7 W)
 - JADE (27.52 kg, 17.3 W)
 - UVS (13.65 kg, 11.8 W)
 - Waves (10.87 kg, 9.6 W)
 - JunoCam (1.66 kg, 6.0 W)
 - JIRAM (13.10 kg, 18.4 W)
- Bus Volume: 3.5 diameter x 3.5 m³ (hexagon core)
- Launch Vehicle: Atlas-5 – 5(551)
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 3
 - Mag Boom
- Objectives: Investigate -

- The formation and origin of Jupiter’s atmosphere and potential migration of planets through the measurement of Jupiter’s global abundance of oxygen (water) and nitrogen (ammonia), (1)
- Variations in Jupiter’s deep atmosphere related to meteorology, composition, temperature profiles, cloud opacity, and atmospheric dynamics, (2)
- The fine structure of Jupiter’s magnetic field, (3)
- The gravity field and distribution of mass inside the planet, (4) and
- Jupiter’s three-dimensional polar magnetosphere and aurorae. (5)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 3625 kg.
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 0 kg
 - Fuel: 1280 (fuel) + 752 (oxidizer) kg
 - Space Vehicle: 1593 kg
 - Payload: 154.86 kg
 - Vault: 150 kg (0.8 x 0.8 x 0.6 m titanium “vault” protects avionics from radiation)
- S/A Area: 60.4 m²
 - Three-wing. 4 panels x 2, 3 panels x1 with a boom structure holding science instruments.
 - Solar arm length is 9 meters with a width of 2.65 meters – surface area 60 m²
- Power (1 Au): 14000 W Press Kit (18000 W NSSDCA)
- Power (station): 500 W
- Science
 - MAG: Magnetometer
 - FGM: FluxGate Magnetometer
 - SHM: Scalar Helium Magnetometer
 - MWR: Microwave Radiometer
 - Gravity Science
 - JEDI: Jupiter Energetic-particle Detector Instrument
 - JADE: Jovian Auroral Distribution Experiment
 - UVS: Ultraviolet Spectrograph
 - Waves: Radio and Plasma Wave Instrument
 - JunoCam: Camera
 - JIRAM: Jovian Infrared Auroral Mapper
- Science orbit is 14 day near polar orbit with perijove of 1.05 jovian radii and an apojoive of 39 Jovian radii.
- Spacecraft rotates at 2 rpm during science orbit.
- Due to high dose radiation levels, the mission life is anticipated to be 37 orbits (before critical failure)

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p. SMD-172)

- Baseline mission defined: PI, schedule, FY 2006 budgeting (nothing reported for 2005)

NASA 2008 Budget Request (p. SMD-172)

Budget / Life Cycle Cost

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY06	FY07	FY08
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	40.4	124.1	120.2
FY 2007 President's Budget Request	62.3	117.2	127.9
Total Change from FY 2007 President's Budget Request	-11.9	6.9	-7.7

Note: FY 2007 column represents the 2007 President's Budget in full-cost simplification and shown in the new Theme structure.

NASA 2009 Budget Request (p. Sci-137)

FY 2009 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2007 Actual	FY 2008 Enacted	FY 2009	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	106.6	132.2	263.9	250.3	232.3	227.7	236.9
Juno	87.8	108.3	245.0	225.2	168.0	14.4	17.8
Other Missions and Data Analysis	18.8	23.9	19.0	25.1	64.3	213.3	219.1
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	158.1	147.3	296.0	277.5	267.9	274.5	0
Juno	124.1	120.2	272.9	242.6	190.9	16.0	0
Other Missions and Data Analysis	34.0	27.0	23.1	35.0	76.9	258.5	0
Changes from FY 2008 Request	-51.5	-15.1	-32.1	-27.2	-35.6	-46.8	236.9

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. SCI-122)

FY 2010 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2008 Actual	FY 2009 Enacted	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	130.2	95.0	245.0	237.2	174.2	71.4	17.8	18.1	102.4	1,091.2
Formulation	130.8	55.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	186.3
Development / Implementation	0.1	39.5	245.0	237.2	158.5	46.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	727.2
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.7	24.5	17.8	18.1	102.3	178.4
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	--
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	130.2	108.3	245.0	225.2	168.0	14.4	17.8	--	0.0	909.5
Formulation	130.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	--	0.0	130.9
Development / Implementation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	--	0.0	--
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	--	0.0	--
Other	0.0	108.3	245.0	225.2	168.0	14.4	17.8	--	0.0	778.6
Changes from FY 2009 Request	0.0	-13.3	0.0	12.0	6.2	57.0	0.0	--	102.4	182.4
Formulation	-0.1	55.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	--	0.0	55.4
Development / Implementation	0.1	39.5	245.0	237.2	158.5	46.9	0.0	--	0.0	727.2
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.7	24.5	17.8	--	102.3	178.4
Other	0.0	-108.3	-245.0	-225.2	-168.0	-14.4	-17.8	--	-0.1	-778.6

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET-40)

FY 2011 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2009 Actual	FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	225.2	260.1	237.2	184.2	46.4	17.8	18.1	16.8	85.6	1,092.0
Formulation	186.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	186.3
Development / Implementation	39.6	260.1	237.2	184.2	22.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	727.4
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.7	24.4	17.8	18.1	16.8	85.6
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	225.2	245.0	237.2	174.2	71.4	17.8	18.1	--	102.4	1,091.2
Formulation	186.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	186.3
Development / Implementation	39.6	245.0	237.2	174.2	158.5	46.9	0.0	--	0.0	727.2
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.7	24.5	17.8	--	102.4	178.5
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	-0.1
Changes from FY 2010 Request	0.0	15.1	0.0	10.0	-25.0	0.0	0.0	--	-16.8	0.1
Formulation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--
Development / Implementation	0.0	15.1	0.0	10.0	-24.9	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	0.2
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	--	-16.8	-0.1
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. MP-71)

2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	485.9	257.1	--	31.2	17.6	17.3	16.7	29.6	--	--
FY 2011 Costs			194.2							
CSLE				0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3		
2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate	485.9	257.2	194.2	31.4	17.8	18.1	16.8	29.9	55.7	1107.0
Formulation	186.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	186.3
Development	299.6	257.2	178.5	7.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	742.3
Operations	0.0	0.0	15.7	24.4	17.8	18.1	16.8	29.9	55.7	178.4

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-35)

FY 2013 BUDGET

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2011	Estimate FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	208.3	50.5	37.5	41.0	55.4	57.8	110.1
New Frontiers Future Missions	2.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.5	65.3
New Frontiers Management	5.7	6.4	6.4	6.5	6.7	6.9	7.0
New Frontiers Research	1.2	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
New Horizons	9.7	12.4	13.3	16.4	26.8	18.5	4.5
Juno	189.2	31.4	17.8	18.1	21.8	29.9	33.4
Change from FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-13.0				
Percent Change from FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-25.8%				

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-33)

FY 2014 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	43.9	--	38.8	53.1	62.1	120.1	105.1
New Frontiers Management	2.7	--	4.7	4.9	5.9	5.8	6.0
New Horizons	26.5	--	16.4	26.8	18.5	4.6	0.0
Juno	14.4	--	17.7	21.4	29.5	33.4	19.5
New Frontiers Future Missions	0.0	--	0.0	0.0	8.2	76.3	79.7
New Frontiers Research	0.3	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Change from FY 2012	--	--	-5.1				
Percentage change from FY 2012	--	--	-11.6%				

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-34)

- Juno Operations 2013 actual \$17.8

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-32)

- Juno Operations 2014 actual \$7.7

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-35)

- Juno Operations 2015 actual \$35.4

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-37)

- Juno Operations 2016 actual \$45.8

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-54)

- Juno Operations 2017 actual \$61.9

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-56)

- Juno Operations 2018 actual \$17.8

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-62)

- Juno Operations 2019 actual \$11.8

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-76)

- Juno Operations 2020 actual \$33.8

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-87)

- Juno Operations 2021 actual \$35.0
- Juno Operations 2023 budget \$30.5

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-83)

- Juno Operations 2022 actual \$31.8
- Juno Operations 2024 budget \$28.4

Juno References

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LADEE

Mission Attributes		Ladee	
Last Updated	9/13/2024		
Definition			
COSPAR	2013-047A		
Program			
Destination	Lunar		
Success	Success		
Type	Orbiter		
Launch Vehicle	Minotaur V		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	56.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	68.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	66.2		
Initial Mission Life (years)	0.4		
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.6		
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.1		
Phase A - Award	4/1/2008		
PDR	8/23/2010		
CDR	5/20/2011		
Launch	9/7/2013		
On Station	10/6/2013		
Extend Mission	3/1/2014		
End Mission	4/18/2014		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass	375.5		
Fuel	134.8		
S/V Dry	240.7		
S/V Bus	191.1		
S/V Payload	49.7		
Probe/Rover	-		
Cruise	-		
Lander	-		
Aeroshield+	-		
Bus Volume (m ³)	7.69		
Objectives	4		
Deployments	0		
Cost			
Start	2008		
Launch	2013		
Budget \$	262.9		
Realized \$	279.2		
Budget Schedule	26		
Realized Schedule	38		
Then \$	\$ 279.20		
Development	\$ 204.30		
Launch	\$ 58.70		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 11.00		
Extended	\$ 5.20		
NSII 2023\$	\$ 365.80		
Development	\$ 269.80		
Launch	\$ 75.50		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 14.00		
Extended	\$ 6.50		
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 348.70		
Development	\$ 257.60		
Launch	\$ 71.60		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 13.30		
Extended	\$ 6.20		
Payload			
Instruments	4		
Mass (kg)	49.7		
Power (W, ave)	195		
RTG or S/A	S/A		
S/A Power	-		
BoL 1 Au	295		
Perihelion	295		
Aphelion	260		
S/A Area (m ²)	7.1		
S/A Type	Body		
Blank	-		

LADEE

- Mission life: 100 days in orbit
 - 30 days reaching nominal lunar orbit.
 - 100-day science mission
- Extension: extended one time (extremely low orbit – 1 month)
- Status: Successful, deorbited onto the Moon
- Instruments
 - NMS (11.8 kg, 36 W)
 - LDEX (3.6 kg, 5 W)
 - UVS (3.6 kg, 13 W)
 - LLST (30.7 kg, 141 W)
- Bus Volume: 1.85 x 1.85 x 2.37 m³ (hexagon)
- Deployments: 0 (body mounted array, instrument deck)
- Objectives:
 - Determine the composition of the lunar atmosphere and investigate the process that controls its distribution and variability – sources, sinks, and surface interactions, (1)
 - Characterize the lunar exosphere dust environment and measure any spatial and temporal variability and impacts on the lunar atmosphere, (2)
 - Demonstrate the Lunar Laser Com Demonstration (LLCD), (3) and
 - Develop a low-cost, reusable spacecraft architecture that meets the needs of planetary science missions. (4)
- Manufacturer: Ames Research Center

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 375.5 kg (Minotaur launch)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Propellant: 134.8 kg (Fuel MMH – 51.2 kg, Oxidizer N2O4 – 82.1 kg, Pressurant He2 – 0.26 kg)
 - Space Vehicle: 240.7 kg
 - Payload: 49.6 kg
 - Bus: 191.1 kg
- S/A Area: 7.1 m²
 - 22 panels 22.3 cm²
 - 8 panels 27.5 cm²
- Power (1 Au): 295 W
- Power (station): 260 W
- Science
 - NMS: Neutral Mass Spectrometer
 - UVS: Ultraviolet/Visible Spectrometer
 - LDE: Lunar Dust Experiment
 - LLCD: Lunar Laser Communications Demonstration

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. SCI-99)

FY 2010 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2008 Actual	FY 2009 Enacted	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	41.3	105.0	103.6	142.6	138.6	145.5	118.7
Lunar Science	36.2	64.8	33.3	52.4	58.5	64.3	39.4
Lunar Atmosphere and Dust Environment Explorer	5.1	30.2	66.5	73.9	31.1	0.0	0.0
International Lunar Network	0.0	10.0	3.7	16.3	48.9	81.2	79.3
Changes from FY 2009 Request	41.3	105.0	103.6	142.6	138.6	145.5	--

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET – 20)

FY 2011 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2009 Actual	FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	30.2	55.3	57.9	54.7	18.7	0.0	0.0
Total Change from 2010 President's Budget Request	30.2	55.3	57.9	54.7	18.7	0.0	--

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. PS-23)

FY 2012 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2010	Ann CR, FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	35.3	48.2	--	63.2	33.1	0.0	0.0	0.0

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-10)

FY 2013 BUDGET

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2011	Estimate FY 2012	Notional FY 2013	Notional FY 2014	Notional FY 2015	Notional FY 2016	Notional FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	130.2	139.9	61.5	6.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
Lunar Science	61.7	66.7	17.3	3.7	0.0	0.0	0.0
Lunar Atmosphere and Dust Environment Explorer	64.5	70.4	41.4	2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
Surface Science Lander Technology	4.0	2.8	2.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-78.4				
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-56.0%				

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-12)

FY 2014 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual FY 2012	FY 2013	Notional FY 2014	Notional FY 2015	Notional FY 2016	Notional FY 2017	Notional FY 2018	BTC	Total
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	148.6	70.4	41.4	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	262.9
2014 MPAR ICC Estimate	148.6	70.4	41.4	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	262.9
Formulation	79.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	79.5
Development/Implementation	69.1	70.4	36.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	176.1
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	4.8	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.2
Change from FY 2012	--	--	-70.0							
Percentage change from FY 2012	--	--	-99.4%							

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. SD-34)

COMPARABILITY ADJUSTMENT TABLES

FY2013 Operating Plan Crosswalk to FY2015 Budget Structure

Planetary Science	1,271.5	1,274.6
Planetary Science Research	192.7	195.8
Planetary Science Research and Analysis	128.6	128.6
Directorate Management	3.9	3.9
Near Earth Object Observations	20.5	20.5
Other Missions and Data Analysis	39.7	42.8
Science Data and Computing		3.1
OMDA - Planetary Science Research Projects	39.7	39.7
Lunar Quest Program	21.8	63.8
Lunar Science	20.3	12.2
Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Science Mission	8.1	
Lunar Management	1.5	1.5
Lunar Science	10.8	10.8
Lunar Atmosphere and Dust Environment Explorer	48.7	48.7
Surface Science Lander Technology	2.8	2.8
Discovery	207.4	215.5
InSight	122.7	122.7
Other Missions and Data Analysis	207.4	92.8
InSight	122.7	
Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Science Mission	8.1	8.1
OMDA - Discovery Projects	84.7	84.7
New Frontiers	158.8	158.8
Mars Exploration	369.2	369.2
Mars Atmosphere and Volatile Evolution	86.5	
Other Missions and Data Analysis	283.0	369.5
OMDA - Mars Exploration Projects	283.0	283.0
Mars Atmosphere and Volatile Evolution		86.5
Outer Planets	147.8	147.8
Jupiter Europa Mission	69.7	
Other Missions and Data Analysis	78.1	
Technology	123.4	123.4

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. BUD-3) – Lunar Quest Program line item cost for 2014 operations

	Fiscal Year						
	Actual 2014	Enacted 2015	Request 2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Planetary Science	1,345.7	--	1,301.2	1,420.2	1,458.1	1,502.4	1,527.8
Planetary Science Research	221.8	--	276.3	282.0	292.0	291.7	285.7
Planetary Science Research and Analysis	130.0	--	162.5	164.0	166.7	170.6	170.6
Directorate Management	4.0	--	7.1	7.4	7.4	7.4	7.4
Near Earth Object Observations	40.5	--	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0
Other Missions and Data Analysis	47.3	--	56.7	60.6	67.9	63.7	57.7
Lunar Quest Program	11.4	--	--	--	--	--	--
Discovery	297.4	--	156.1	201.6	277.2	337.4	344.9
InSight	203.3	170.0	92.1	13.3	8.7	9.0	9.0
Other Missions and Data Analysis	94.1	--	64.0	188.4	268.5	328.4	335.9
New Frontiers	231.6	--	259.0	124.0	81.5	85.7	137.8
Origins-Spectral Interpretation-Resource Identification-Security-Regolith Explorer	207.3	216.8	189.7	44.0	38.1	43.1	27.7
Other Missions and Data Analysis	24.3	--	69.3	80.0	43.4	42.6	110.1
Mars Exploration	288.0	--	411.9	539.3	561.3	531.5	464.2
Outer Planets	152.4	--	116.2	117.7	81.6	87.6	110.5
Jupiter Europa	80.0	100.0	30.0	30.0	50.0	75.0	100.0
Technology	143.1	--	141.7	155.5	164.4	168.5	184.7

Ladee References

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Lucy

Mission Attributes		Lucy	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition			
COSPAR	2021-093A		
Program	Discovery 13		
Destination	Jupiter		
Success	Operational		
Type	Flyby		
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	58.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	58.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	58.2		
Initial Mission Life (years)	11.5		
Realized Mission Life (years)	2.9		
Extended Mission Life (years)	-9.1		
Phase A - Award	1/4/2017		
PDR	10/20/2018		
CDR	10/21/2019		
Launch	10/16/2021		
On Station	4/20/2025		
Extend Mission	10/16/2033		
End Mission	9/13/2024		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass	1550	Payload	
Fuel	729	Instruments	4
S/V Dry	821	Mass (kg)	61.66
S/V Bus	759.34	Power (W, ave)	70
S/V Payload	61.66	RTG or S/A	S/A
Probe/Rover	-	S/A Power	-
Cruise	-	BoL 1 Au	26400
Lander	-	Perihelion	-
Aeroshield +	-	Aphelion	504
Bus Volume (m ³)	10.982	S/A Area (m ²)	83.7
Objectives	4	S/A Type	2 fixed
Deployments	3	Blank	-

Lucy

- Mission life: 11.6-year mission, 6-year cruise, and 5.6-year prime mission
- Extension: None. On station 2027, end of primary mission 2033.
- Status: Currently Operational
 - Operations – cruise
- Instruments
 - L’LORRI (14.0 kg, 12.4 W)
 - L’TES (7.7 kg, 17.6 W)
 - L’Ralph/MVIC (37.0 kg, 30.0 W)
 - L’Ralph/LEISA (included in L’Ralph/MVIC)
 - TTCam (2.96 kg, 10 W)
- Bus Volume: 3.8 x 1.7 x 1.7 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Payload deck
 - Solar arrays deploy (unfurl) x2 (not considered)
- Objectives:
 - Surface Geology – Lucy will map the shape, albedo, and crater spatial and size-frequency distributions; determine the nature of crustal structure and layering; and determine the relative ages of surface units, (1)

- Surface Color and Composition – Lucy will map the color, composition, and regolith properties of the surface, and determine the distribution of minerals, ices, and organic species, (2)
- Interiors and Bulk Properties – Lucy will determine the masses and densities, and study sub-surface composition via excavation by craters, fractures, ejecta blankets, and exposed bedding, (3)
- Satellites and Rings – Lucy will look for and study satellites and/or rings that might orbit the targeted Trojan asteroids. (4)

- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 1550 kg (Atlas-5(401))
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 729 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 821 kg
 - Payload: 61.66 kg
- S/A Area: 83.6 m² (2 x 7.3-meter diameter arrays)
- Power (1 Au): 26,400 W
- Power (station): 504 W (at 5.71 AU)
- Science
 - L’LORRI: high resolution imaging
 - L’TES: measures thermal infrared emission
 - L’Ralph/MVIC: Multispectral Visible Imaging Camera
 - L’Ralph/LEISA: Linear Etalon Imaging Spectral Array
 - TTCam: Terminal Tracking Camera (x2) – considered part of GN&C

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-18)

FY 2018 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2016	Enacted FY 2017	Request FY 2018	FY 2019	Notional		
					FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022
Total Budget	0.0	--	101.4	170.9	205.1	141.1	36.2

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-38)

FY 2019 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2017	FY 2018	CR FY 2018	Request FY 2019	FY 2020	Notional		
					FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024
Total Budget	54.5	--	--	153.3	209.3	154.7	56.4	16.5

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-36)

FY 2020 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual FY 2018	Enacted FY 2019	Request FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	BTC	Total
Formulation	57.5	37.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	94.7
Development/Implementation	0.0	44.2	170.5	218.5	153.4	32.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	619.2
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.4	16.5	18.6	208.7	267.2
2019 MPAR LCC Estimate	57.5	81.4	170.5	218.5	153.4	56.0	16.5	18.6	208.7	981.1
Total Budget	57.5	81.4	170.5	218.5	153.4	56.0	16.5	18.6	208.7	981.1
Change from FY 2019				48.0						
Percentage change from FY 2019				28.2%						

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-36)

FY 2021 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Op Plan		Request					BTC	Total	
		FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025			
Formulation	94.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	94.7
Development/Implementation	44.2	165.5	210.7	153.4	40.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	614.2
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.4	16.5	18.6	22.9			272.2
2020 MPAR LCC Estimate	138.9	165.5	210.7	153.4	63.8	16.5	18.6	22.9			981.1
Total Budget	138.9	165.5	210.8	153.4	63.7	16.5	18.6	22.9			981.1
Change from FY 2020				-57.4							
Percentage change from FY 2020				-37.2%							

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-46)

FY 2022 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Op Plan		Request					BTC	Total	
		FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026			
Formulation	94.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	94.7
Development/Implementation	209.7	208.6	143.6	52.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	614.2
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.0	18.0	20.2	24.5	41.7			280.2
2021 MPAR LCC Estimate	304.4	208.6	143.6	77.3	18.0	20.2	24.5	41.7			989.1
Total Budget	304.4	208.6	143.6	77.3	18.0	20.2	24.5	41.7			989.1
Change from FY 2021				-66.3							
Percentage change from FY 2021				-46.2%							

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

FY 2023 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2021	Request FY 2022	Request FY 2023	Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	Request FY 2026	Request FY 2027
Janus	23.7	15.3	1.2	0.6	0.6	1.1	0.0
Venus Technology	4.9	6.6	7.0	7.3	7.5	7.0	7.0
InSight	14.9	14.6	7.8	14.8	3.7	0.0	0.0
Lucy	139.9	43.3	22.9	24.8	26.4	23.3	38.1
Strofia	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.8	1.2	2.3
International Mission Contributions (IMC)	5.5	10.3	7.8	7.5	8.9	9.7	8.0
Planetary Management	22.2	18.9	20.4	20.9	32.6	27.5	23.5
Discovery Future	22.4	22.2	13.7	11.4	12.2	54.1	62.6
Discovery Research	6.8	9.7	9.7	10.2	11.5	12.8	13.8
Planetary SmallSats	4.8	14.7	0.9	20.3	37.1	46.1	22.6
Mars-moon Exploration with Gamma Rays an	12.2	7.9	2.8	2.6	2.8	3.2	2.0
Total Budget	262.1	171.5	111.2	160.1	190.3	233.3	222.6
Change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-60.3				
Percent change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-53.2%				

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-66)

FY 2024 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2022	Enacted FY 2023	Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	Request FY 2026	Request FY 2027	Request FY 2028
Janus	16.3	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Venus Technology	6.6	-	7.0	3.2	1.7	1.0	1.0
InSight	11.4	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Lucy	44.6	-	24.8	25.9	23.8	34.8	34.0
Strofia	1.0	-	1.0	1.8	1.2	2.3	2.4
International Mission Contributions (IMC)	8.4	-	6.8	8.5	10.3	10.2	8.6
Planetary Management	18.3	-	41.2	41.2	38.5	40.0	43.0
Discovery Future	4.5	-	5.3	28.3	21.8	82.4	257.2
Discovery Research	7.8	-	9.2	10.1	12.1	13.1	13.4
Planetary SmallSats	1.6	-	0.1	7.5	31.4	40.0	6.1
Mars-moon Exploration with Gamma rays and Neutrons (MEGANe)	2.9	-	4.1	3.8	4.2	1.6	1.7
Total Budget	141.1	-	132.5	177.5	188.8	272.0	396.0

Lucy References

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Lunar Prospector

Mission Attributes		
Lunar Prospector		
Last Updated	9/13/2024	
Definition	COSPAS 1998-001A Program Discovery 3	
Destination	Lunar	
Success	Success	
Type	Orbiter	
Launch Vehicle	Athena 2	
Schedule	Initial Design Duration (months) 30.0 Realized Design Duration (months) 34.0 Calculated Design Duration (months) 34.8 Initial Mission Life (years) 1.0 Realized Mission Life (years) 1.6 Extended Mission Life (years) 0.6 Phase A - Award 2/28/1995 PDR 4/1/1995 CDR 10/1/1995 Launch 1/6/1998 On Station 1/11/1998 Extend Mission 1/1/1999 End Mission 7/31/1999	
Cost	Start 1996 Launch 1998 Budget \$ 61.3 Realized \$ 61.7 Budget Schedule 30 Realized Schedule 34 Then \$ 63.90 Development \$ 30.60 Launch \$ 26.00 Operations - Primary \$ 5.10 Extended \$ 2.20 NSII 2023\$ 125.20 Development \$ 60.20 Launch \$ 51.10 Operations - Primary \$ 9.80 Extended \$ 4.10 PCEPI 2023\$ 106.30 Development \$ 51.00 Launch \$ 43.40 Operations - Primary \$ 8.40 Extended \$ 3.50	
Technical Scope	Launch Mass 296.4 Fuel 137.7 S/V Dry 158.7 S/V Bus 135 S/V Payload 23.7 Probe/Rover - Cruise - Lander - Aeroshield + - Bus Volume (m³) 1.7 Objectives 6 Deployments 3	
Payload	Instruments 5 Mass (kg) 23.7 Power (W, ave) 17 RTG or S/A S/A S/A Power - BoL 1 Au 200 Perihelion 186 Aphelion - S/A Area (m²) 5.2 S/A Type body Blank -	

Lunar Prospector

- Mission life: 1-year prime mission
- Extension: extended 6 months, intentionally crashed into the Moon's surface
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - GRS (6.6 kg, 0.36 W)

- APS/NS (5.6 kg, 0.94 W)
- SES: (6.2, 11.2 W)
- MAG/ER (5.3 kg, 4.5 W)
- DGE: (comm payload)
- Bus Volume: 1.3 m dia x 1.28 H – 1.7 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Boom x 3
- Objectives:
 - Determine the global elemental and mineralogical composition of the Moon’s surface, (1)
 - Determine the global surface topology and gravitational field, (2)
 - Map the distribution of surface magnetic anomalies and magnitude of induced dipole moment, (3) and
 - Global image database in stereo and color, (4)
 - Measure the microwave brightness temperature as a function of wavelength (5) and
 - Measure the global composition, structure, and temporal variability of the lunar atmosphere. (6)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: spin stabilized
- Launch mass: 296.4 kg ()
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 137.7 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 158.7 kg
 - Payload: 23.7 kg
- S/A Area: 5.2 m² (body mount)
- Power (1 Au): 200 W
- Power (station): 186 W
- Science
 - GRS: Gamma Ray Spectrometer
 - APS/NS: Alpha Particle Spectrometer/ Neutron Spectrometer
 - SES: Spectrometer Electronics System
 - MAG/ER: Magnetometer/Electron Reflectometer
 - DGE: Doppler Gravity Experiment

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

Lunar Prospector

Lunar Prospector was selected as the third Discovery mission in FY 1995, and Phase C/D development started in the first quarter of FY 1996. The mission is designed to search for resources on the Moon, with special emphasis on the search for water in the shaded polar regions. Ames Research Center is managing the mission, and Lockheed Martin will provide the spacecraft, instruments, launch and operations. Launch will be on a Lockheed Launch Vehicle-II (LLV-II) and is planned for September 1997. Launch costs are included in the development cost. Tracking and communications support will be provided by the Deep Space Network.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		36.4	19.8							56.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS			.8	4.3	2.2					7.3
TOTAL		36.4	20.6	4.3	2.2					63.5

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

Lunar Prospector

Lunar Prospector was selected as the third Discovery mission in FY 1995, and Phase C/D development started in the first quarter of FY 1996. The mission is designed to search for resources on the Moon, with special emphasis on the search for water in the shaded polar regions. Ames Research Center is managing the mission, and Lockheed Martin will provide the spacecraft, instruments, launch and operations. Launch on a Lockheed Launch Vehicle-II (LLV-II) occurred in January 1998. Launch costs are included in the development cost. Tracking and communications support will be provided by the Deep Space Network.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	36.4	19.8								56.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS		0.8	4.3	2.2						7.3
TOTAL	36.4	20.6	4.3	2.2						63.5

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-37)

DISCOVERY PROGRAM

	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000
	(Thousands of Dollars)		
Lunar Prospector *	400	--	--
Stardust *	56,200	22,300	--
Genesis *	29,900	82,900	50,200
CONTOUR *	--	--	51,800
Future Missions	13,500	19,700	78,500
ELV (Non-add)	[23,500]	[30,300]	[42,900]
Total	100,000	124,900	180,500

Lunar Prospector References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Lunar Prospector (Discovery 3)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/lunar_prospector.htm .
 NASA. *Lunar Prospector*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1998-001A> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

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Hubbard, G.S., Alan B. Binder, Thomas A. Dougherty, Sylvia A. Cox, *The Lunar Prospector Discovery Mission: A new Approach to Planetary Science*, Acta Astronautica, Volume 41, Issues 4–10, 1997, Pages 585-597, ISSN 0094-5765, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-5765\(98\)00070-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0094-5765(98)00070-8) .

Mars 2020 (Perseverance)

Mission Attributes M2020 - Perseverance	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR Program	2020-052A
Destination	Mars
Success	Operational
Type	Rover
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	68.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	68.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	69.6
Initial Mission Life (years)	1.9
Realized Mission Life (years)	4.2
Extended Mission Life (years)	1.7
Phase A - Award	11/1/2014
PDR	2/3/2016
CDR	3/1/2017
Launch	7/20/2020
On Station	2/18/2021
Extend Mission	1/6/2023
End Mission	9/13/2024
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	3839
Fuel	1400
S/V Dry	
S/V Bus	
S/V Payload	1052
Probe/Rover	
Cruise	539
Lander	575
Aeroshield +	440
Bus Volume (m ³)	17.82
Objectives	5
Deployments	5
Cost	
Start	2013
Launch	2020
Budget \$	2351
Realized \$	2715.6
Budget Schedule	68
Realized Schedule	69
Then \$	\$ 2,880.60
Development	\$ 2,232.20
Launch	\$ 230.40
Operations	
Primary	\$ 253.00
Extended	\$ 165.00
NSII 2023\$	\$ 3,338.10
Development	\$ 2,635.50
Launch	\$ 263.90
Operations	
Primary	\$ 273.70
Extended	\$ 165.00
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 3,244.50
Development	\$ 2,558.70
Launch	\$ 257.80
Operations	
Primary	\$ 263.00
Extended	\$ 165.00
Payload	
Instruments	8
Mass (kg)	50.675
Power (W, ave)	435.7
RTG or S/A	RTG
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	110
Perihelion	
Aphelion	
S/A Area (m ²)	-
S/A Type	-
Blank	-

Mars 2020 (Perseverance)

- RTG vs Solar array. Perseverance RTG - \$75M for 110 W (Space Exploration, Meghan Bartels, last updated October 11, 2022 – Why NASA’s Mars rover Perseverance will use nuclear power to keep itself warm) – (uses PU238, not PU239, not nuclear)
- Bagan Phase A formulation in November 2014 with payload selection (from 53 submissions) with AO on September 24, 2013, and selection on July 31, 2014 (originally listed as Spring 2014) through competitive selection. NASA selected 7 science instruments and exploration technology investigations for the Mars Rover 2020 payload.
- NASA Budget 2016 Request (2014-2020) - \$1759.5
- NASA Budget 2017 Request (adds 2021 - \$140) - \$1899.5
- NASA Budget 2018 Request states Total - \$2443.5
- The Mars 2020 Mission was procured through JPL with the radioisotope power system (RTG) through the Department of Energy (DoE).
- Design utilized contracts existing from the MSL project to procure new versions of the “as-flown” hardware.
- Mission life: 1 Mars Year (687 days) with Launch in July 2020 and landing on Mars in February 2021 (7 months): prime mission (Primary mission: 7 months + 687 days)
- Extension: Mission extended January 2023

- Status: Operational (successful)
- Instruments
 - Ingenuity (1.8 kg, 0 W) – self-powered
 - Mastcam-Z (4.0 kg, 17.4 W)
 - MEDA (5.5 kg, 17.0 W)
 - MOXIE (14.14 kg, 300.0 W)
 - PIXL (4.3+2.6+0.015 kg, 25.0 W)
 - RIMFAX (3.0 kg, 10.0 W)
 - SHERLOC (3.11 + 1.61 kg, 32.2 + 16.2 W)
 - SuperCam (5.6 + 4.8 + 0.2 kg, 17.9 W)
- Bus Volume: (rover) 3.0 x 2.7 x 2.2 m³
- Deployments: 5
 - Rover
 - Rover arm
 - Instruments x 2
 - Helicopter (Ingenuity)
- Objectives:
 - Geology - Study the rocks and landscape at its landing site to reveal the region’s history, (1)
 - Astrobiology - Determine whether an area of interest was suitable for life, and look for signs of ancient life itself, (2)
 - Sample Caching - Find and collect promising samples of Mars rock and soil that return to Earth in the future, (3)
 - Prepare for Humans: Test technologies that would help sustain human presence on Mars someday, (4)
 - Deliver Ingenuity (+1)
- Manufacturer: JPL

Not listed in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Lander mission
- Launch mass: 3839 kg.
 - Ballast (Adapter, unaccounted mass): kg
 - Cruise Stage: 539 kg
 - Cruise Fuel: kg
 - Backshell (Aeroshell): 575 kg
 - Parachute System: 81 kg.
 - Ballast: 140 kg (2 x 70 kg)
 - Descent Stage: 1070 kg
 - Descent Fuel: 400 kg
 - Ballast: 150 kg (6 x 25 kg)
 - Rover: 1025 kg
 - Payload: 57 kg
 - Helicopter (Ingenuity): 1.8 kg
 - Heat Shield: 440 kg.
- Power: RTG
- Power (1 Au): 110 W
- Power (station): 110 W ave
- Science
 - Ingenuity: Helicopter rover
 - Mastcam-Z: Mast Zoom Camera
 - MEDA: Mars Environmental Dynamics Analyzer
 - MOXIE: Mars Oxygen ISRU Experiment

- PIXL: Planetary Instrument for X-ray Lithochemistry
- RIMFAX: Radar Imager for Mars Subsurface Exploration
- SHERLOC: Scanning Habitable Environments with Raman and Luminescence for Organics and Chemicals
- SuperCam: -

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-39)

FY 2015 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Request	Notional			
	FY 2013	Enacted FY 2014		FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA)	14.4	--	25.0	20.0	10.0	2.7	0.7
ExoMars	4.8	--	3.5	2.6	1.4	1.4	1.5
Mars Program Management	17.9	--	19.5	19.1	19.2	19.3	19.5
Mars Future Missions	108.5	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Rover 2020	0.0	65.0	92.0	202.7	388.6	416.6	370.2
Mars Mission Operations	1.8	--	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9
Mars Research and Analysis	18.6	--	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Mars Technology	4.0	--	4.0	4.0	6.5	11.0	4.8
2011 Mars Science Lab	63.8	--	59.4	58.0	58.0	58.0	58.0
Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO)	20.6	--	29.5	29.5	30.5	30.5	30.5
Mars Exploration Rover 2003	13.2	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Odyssey 2001	13.2	--	12.3	12.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Express	2.2	--	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2
Mars Atmosphere & Volatile Evolution	86.5	--	20.1	19.5	19.5	19.5	19.5
Total Budget	369.5	--	279.3	381.7	547.8	573.1	518.8

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-38)

FY 2016 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Request	Notional			
	FY 2014	Enacted FY 2015		FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA)	20.9	--	14.3	6.8	5.2	4.6	3.0
Mars Rover 2020	78.3	--	228.0	377.5	397.5	370.2	308.0
ExoMars	3.1	--	2.6	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.5
Mars Program Management	18.1	--	19.1	19.2	19.3	19.5	19.5
Mars Future Missions	0.5	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Mission Operations	1.5	--	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9
Mars Research and Analysis	19.5	--	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
Mars Technology	4.0	--	4.0	4.0	9.0	8.3	4.8
2011 Mars Science Lab	69.6	--	58.0	58.0	58.0	58.0	58.0
Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO)	29.2	--	29.5	30.5	30.5	30.5	30.5
Mars Exploration Rover 2003	14.0	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Odyssey 2001	12.3	--	12.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Express	2.1	--	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Mars Atmosphere & Volatile Evolution	14.9	--	29.3	27.0	25.5	24.0	24.0
Total Budget	288.0	--	411.9	539.3	561.3	531.5	464.2

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-42)

MARS ROVER 2020

Formulation	Development	Operations

FY 2017 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Request	Notional			
	FY 2015	Enacted FY 2016		FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2021
Total Budget	103.6	--	377.5	409.0	381.0	322.0	140.0

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-42)

FY 2018 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Request	Notional			
	Prior	FY 2016		FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020
Formulation	274.4	118.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Development/Implementation	0.4	227.7	0.0	392.6	373.4	293.0	0.0
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.1	153.4
2017 MPAR LCC Estimate	274.8	346.4	0.0	392.6	373.4	325.0	153.4
Total Budget	253.3	321.8	377.5	374.3	363.8	322.8	150.0
Change from FY 2017				-3.2			
Percentage change from FY 2017				-0.8%			
Total NASA Budget	274.4	346.5	387.7	392.6	373.4	325	153.4

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-60)

FY 2019 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		CR	Request	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2017			FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021		
Formulation	393.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	393.1
Development/Implementation	227.3	425.2	400.9	355.4	277.6	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1687.6
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.4	157.6	134.8	61.7	0.0	377.5
2017 MPAR LCC Estimate	620.4	425.2	400.9	355.4	301.1	158.7	134.8	61.7	0.0	2458.2
Total Budget	575.1	408.0	347.3	348.0	296.9	154.8	133.0	60.4	0	2350.5
Change from FY 2018										
Percentage change from FY 2018										
Total NASA Budget	620.4	425.2	400.9	355.4	301.1	158.7	134.8	61.7	0.0	2458.2

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-62)

FY 2020 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Enacted	Request	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2018			FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022		
Formulation	397.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	397.6
Development/Implementation	648.1	536.6	311.7	229.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1725.4
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	148.9	111.9	43.3	0.0	0.0	337.4
2018 MPAR LCC Estimate	1045.7	536.6	311.7	262.3	148.9	111.9	43.3	0.0	0.0	2460.4
Total Budget	983.1	505.8	305.6	278.0	145.0	110.0	60.0	60.0	0.0	2447.5
Change from FY 2019										
Percentage change from FY 2019										
Total NASA Budget	1045.7	536.6	311.7	262.3	148.9	111.9	43.3	0.0	0.0	2460.4

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-68)

FY 2021 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Enacted	Request	Notional				BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2019			FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023		
Formulation	397.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	397.6
Development/Implementation	1186.4	515.3	300.3	34.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2036.2
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.7	133.6	100.5	35.1	0.0	0.0	292.0
2020 MPAR LCC Estimate	1584.0	515.3	323.0	167.9	100.5	35.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	2725.8
Total Budget	1488.9	502.6	318.7	162.3	97.0	33.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2602.5
Change from FY 2020										
Percentage change from FY 2020										
Total NASA Budget	1584.0	515.3	323.0	167.9	100.5	35.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	2725.8

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-82)

OTHER MISSIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS

FY 2022 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Enacted	Request	Notional			
	FY 2020	FY 2021			FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025
Mars Ice Mapper	0.0	7.2	15.0	40.0	40.0	30.0	30.0	
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA)	7.3	5.1	4.9	7.3	6.5	3.0	0.0	
Mars Rover 2020	353.0	150.0	95.7	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	
ExoMars	1.9	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	
Mars Program Management	11.2	11.2	12.5	10.9	9.6	13.2	15.3	
Mars Future Missions	65.5	23.3	7.5	5.8	15.0	13.0	15.0	
Mars Mission Operations	5.9	6.7	6.7	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.6	
Mars Research and Analysis	9.9	14.0	15.0	15.7	15.7	15.7	15.7	
Mars Technology	3.7	8.5	3.2	5.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	
2011 Mars Science Lab	47.0	47.5	45.0	40.0	30.0	20.0	20.0	
Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO)	26.9	27.0	26.0	25.5	24.5	24.5	25.0	
Mars Odyssey 2001	11.7	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	
Mars Express	1.1	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	
Mars Atmosphere & Volatile Evolution	20.5	21.0	23.0	23.0	23.0	24.0	24.0	
Total Budget	565.7	334.8	267.8	251.9	249.1	228.1	229.8	
Change from FY 2021								
Percentage change from FY 2021								

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-93)

FY 2023 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2021	Request FY 2022	Request FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	FY 2027
Mars Ice Mapper	0.0	8.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA)	5.1	4.9	6.2	3.7	4.0	3.0	0.0
Mars Rover 2020	155.0	105.7	80.0	70.0	60.0	60.0	60.0
ExoMars	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Mars Program Management	12.8	10.9	10.9	9.6	13.2	15.3	13.3
Mars Future Missions	23.3	8.1	6.4	15.6	13.6	32.0	57.4
Mars Mission Operations	6.8	6.7	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.6	5.4
Mars Research and Analysis	14.4	15.1	15.7	15.7	15.7	15.7	15.7
Mars Technology	10.1	8.5	2.5	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.1
2011 Mars Science Lab	48.9	43.3	45.0	40.0	35.0	30.0	25.0
Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO)	28.3	24.4	25.5	24.5	24.5	25.0	25.0
Mars Odyssey 2001	11.4	10.5	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0
Mars Express	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Mars Atmosphere & Volatile Evolution	21.0	22.0	23.0	23.0	24.0	24.0	24.0
Total Budget	339.5	270.7	233.9	223.8	211.7	226.8	242.1
Change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-36.8				
Percent change from FY 2022 Budget Request			-13.6%				

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-89)

FY 2024 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2022	Enacted FY 2023	Request FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	FY 2027	FY 2028
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer (MOMA)	3.4	--	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Rover 2020	109.6	--	85.0	80.5	82.0	82.5	83.0
Trace Gas Orbiter - ExoMars	2.0	--	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Mars Program Management	11.8	--	6.9	13.2	15.3	13.3	13.5
Mars Future Missions	6.9	--	49.9	68.5	108.4	118.8	177.4
Mars Mission Operations	6.7	--	5.5	5.5	5.6	5.4	5.4
Mars Research and Analysis	15.1	--	15.7	15.7	15.7	15.7	15.7
Mars Technology	9.1	--	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
2011 Mars Science Lab	43.3	--	40.5	35.0	30.0	25.0	20.0
Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO)	24.4	--	25.6	25.4	25.4	25.4	25.0
Mars Odyssey 2001	10.6	--	11.0	6.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Express	0.0	--	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Mars Atmosphere & Volatile Evolution	22.0	--	23.0	24.0	24.0	24.0	22.0
Total Budget	265.0	--	268.6	279.2	311.6	315.3	367.2

Mars 2020 (Mars Perseverance) References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars 2020 (Perseverance)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars-2020.htm.

NASA. *Mars 2020*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2020-052A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

Magellan

Mission Attributes		Magellan	
Last Updated: 9/13/2024			
Definition		COSPAS 1989-033B	
Destination		Venus	
Success		Success	
Type		Orbiter	
Launch Vehicle		STS	
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)		52.0	
Realized Design Duration (months)		60.0	
Calculated Design Duration (months)		65.0	
Initial Mission Life (years)		1.0	
Realized Mission Life (years)		5.4	
Extended Mission Life (years)		3.4	
Phase A - Award		1/1/1984	
PDR			
CDR			
Launch		5/4/1989	
On Station		8/10/1990	
Extend Mission		5/16/1991	
End Mission		10/12/1994	
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass		3449	
Fuel		22414	
S/V Dry		1035	
S/V Bus			
S/V Payload		15.2	
Probe/Rover		-	
Cruise		-	
Lander		-	
Aeroshield +		-	
Bus Volume (m³)		106	
Objectives		4	
Deployments		2	
Cost			
Start		1984	
Launch		1989	
Budget \$		294.6	
Realized \$		698.2	
Budget Schedule		52	
Realized Schedule		64	
Then \$		\$ 864.80	
Development		\$ 463.20	
Launch		\$ 235.00	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 93.70	
Extended		\$ 72.90	
NSII 2023\$		\$ 2,390.80	
Development		\$ 1,343.80	
Launch		\$ 649.80	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 232.00	
Extended		\$ 165.20	
PCEPI 2023\$		\$ 1,845.60	
Development		\$ 1,030.20	
Launch		\$ 501.10	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 181.60	
Extended		\$ 132.70	
Payload			
Instruments		1	
Mass (kg)		15.2	
Power (W, ave)		210	
RTG or S/A		S/A	
S/A Power		-	
Bol. 1 Au		625	
Perihelion		1200	
Aphelion			
S/A Area (m²)		12.6	
S/A Type		2 articulated	
Blank		-	

Magellan

- “Built partially with spare parts from other missions” – NASA Magellan Summary Sheet – GAO Report (p. 5) – use existing spacecraft designs and technology, and residual hardware.
- Mission life: 15-month cruise and 243-day prime mission (700-day prime mission – 1.91 years)
- Extension: extended
- Status: Successful
 - Launch: May 4, 1989 (STS-30 – Atlantis)
 - Arrival: Aug 10, 1990 (15 months)
 - Operations (primary): Aug 10, 1990 – May 15, 1991
 - Extended Operations: May 16, 1991 – Oct 12, 1994
 - End of Mission: Oct 13, 1994
- Instruments
 - RDRS (15.2 kg, 110.0 W) – operates in three modes: SAR, ALT, RAD
- Bus Volume: 4.6 m dia x 6.4 H m – 106 m³
- Deployments: 2
 - Solar array x 2
- Objectives:
 - Obtain near-global radar images of the planet’s surface, (1)
 - Obtain a near-global topographic map (2)

- Obtain near-global gravity field data, (3) and
- Develop an understanding of the geological evolution of the planet, density distribution, and dynamics. (4)

- Manufacturer: Martin Marietta (Lockheed Martin)

Not included in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 3449 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 2414 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 1035 kg
 - Payload: 15.2 kg
- S/A Area: 12.2 (11.4 m² - 2 wings 2.5 x 2.5 meters)
- Power (1 Au):
- Power (station): 1200 W (1029 W at EoM)
- Science
 - SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar
 - ALT: Altimetry
 - RAD: Radiometry

NASA 1985 Budget Request (p. RD 5-6)

BASIS OF FY 1985 FUNDING REQUIREMENTS

	1983 Actual	1984		1985
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	---	14,200	15,900	65,800
Experiments.....	---	11,600	12,600	24,500
Ground Operations.....	---	3,200	500	2,200
Total.....	---	29,000	29,000	92,500
Space transportation system operations	(---)	(---)	(500)	(12,300)

NASA 1986 Budget Request (p. RD 5-7)

VENUS RADAR MAPPER MISSION

	1984 Actual	1985		1986
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	15,955	65,800	64,100	75,800
Experiments.....	12,483	24,500	26,200	29,800
Ground Operations.....	562	2,200	6,400	6,400
Total.....	29,000	92,500	92,500	112,000
Space Transportation system operations	(---)	(12,300)	(10,000)	(27,500)

NASA 1987 Budget Request (p. RD 5-7)

MAGELLAN (FORMERLY VENUS RADAR MAPPER MISSION)

	1985 Actual	1986		1987
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	64,325	75,800	66,400	24,800
Experiments.....	25,995	29,800	32,300	25,100
Ground Operations.....	2,180	6,400	10,600	18,800
Total.....	92,500	112,000	109,300	66,700
Space Transportation system operations	(28,400)	(27,500)	(39,500)	(47,800)

NASA 1988 Budget Request (p. RD 5-7)

MAGELLAN

	1986 Actual	1987		1988
		Amended Budget	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	74,965	27,800	58,100	38,300
Experiments.....	40,823	23,100	25,600	7,900
Ground Operations.....	4,512	18,800	8,900	13,400
Total.....	120,300	69,700	92,600	59,600
Space transportation system operations	(20,200)	(22,000)	(22,000)	(74,700)

NASA 1989 Budget Request
(p. RD 2-9) – Upper Stage accounting

NDA	PRIOR	FY87	FY88	FY89	FY90	FY91	FY92	FY93	FY 88 COMB TOTAL	FY 89 COMB TOTAL	
FY88 CONGRESSIONAL	830.9	180.3	158.7	106.6	68.6	68.3	42.8	2.0			
CHANGE APPROP. INTED.		(4.4)	(6.2)	(10.2)	(0.3)	(0.2)	(6.2)	42.1			
CHANGE				39.9	6.5	(24.1)	5.0				
FY89 CONGRESSIONAL	826.5	186.1	156.9	146.2	74.8	67.9	37.7	46.9	1,225.6	1,437.3	
DDTEE	582.3	11.2	16.0	6.2	0.4				442.8	440.6	
OPERATIONS	518.3	155.4	128.2	139.3	75.4	55.8	52.7	58.2	1,001.8	996.9	
IUS	167.2	93.6	124.3	114.0	52.0	26.1	30.7	37.8	673.0	565.3	
TORC C 8/88		STB	0.2	1.6					1.8	1.8	
TORC D 2/88		STB	24.6	0.3	9.0				48.3	47.3	
TORC EFF		STB/RELV	28.2	35.3	28.2	17.3			122.0	124.8	
TORC G		ELV	0.2	0.3	0.3				101.2	92.2	
GALILEO 10/89		STB	9.2	6.4	24.2	29.1			82.4	79.4	
MAGELLAN 4/88		STB	8.0	10.4	24.3	20.1			72.1	70.2	
ULYSSES 10/90		STB	11.4	8.0	30.4	38.0			117.0	93.2	
OTHER			75.8	32.4	8.4	3.3	1.5	2.0	126.6	113.0	
MOD KIT FOR PLANETARY B/U				(8.3)	(5.2)						
TOP			18.0	44.0	4.5	17.3	14.2	8.7	7.8	115.5	98.6
MARS OBSERVER 8/82		ELV/STB	12.3	22.1	4.6	17.3	14.2	8.7	7.8	86.9	63.5
MOD KIT INCL ABOVE				(4.0)	(4.7)						
ACTS			5.7	21.9	(0.0)	(12.8)	(8.9)	(3.8)		27.6	7.0
CLUSTER											
PAM			13.7	.2	.3	.2	.2	.2	2	15.2	64.2
SPIP			10.2	7.1	9.8	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	70.0	24.1
CENTAUR			207.2						207.2	222.7	

(p. RD 2-13) -Payload Operations accounting

	FY87	FY88	FY89	FY90	FY91	FY92	FY93
FY89 CONG. BUDGET	40.4	84.6	67.3	82.4	118.5	127.7	166.6
Payload Operations	32.4	69.8	53.3	67.3	98.0	108.9	144.6
P/L Spt Ops Direct	6.3	13.0	20.7	24.1	27.0	24.1	30.6
APE			1.9	0.4		0.1	0.1
ASTRO-1				1.5	1.3	1.5	
ATLAS			2.1	0.1	0.0		
EDIM-3		0.5	2.0	0.5			
GALILEO	0.2	0.1	1.5	0.3			
GRO							
HST-DEPLOY	2.1	2.7	3.1				
HST-REVISIT	0.8	0.8	0.0	0.1	1.5	0.7	1.4
IML-1/2				1.4	0.4	1.6	0.3
LAGEOS-2				0.3	0.2	0.2	
LEDF-1A			1.1	0.0	0.1		
LITE-1				0.8	0.6	0.1	
MAGELLAN		1.1	0.5	0.4	1.8	2.2	
MAST-1/3			0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
MSLs			0.2	0.9	0.7	1.7	
OMV-1							
SHARE							
SHAL-2				0.2	0.1		
SLS-1/2		0.2	0.4	1.7	1.3	0.3	
SPACELAB D2				0.2	1.6	0.1	
SPACELAB J				1.1	1.0		
SPARTANs				3.1	4.0	0.7	
SRL-1/2				1.0	2.6	0.3	
SSBUVs					0.4	0.2	
TORS-C/E	0.2	2.6	0.2	0.5			
TSS-1		0.2	0.3	1.0	0.3		
UARS		2.2	2.2	1.4	2.3	1.0	
ULYSSES		0.2	0.5	1.6			
Others	0.8	-1.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.8	2.6
Manif. Var. NASA			0.2	0.8	0.2	7.5	12.0

(p. RD 5-7) Vehicle accounting (\$8.0 added to Ground Operations - "Ops")

BASIS OF FY 1989 FUNDING REQUIREMENTS

	1987 Actual	1988		1989
		Revised Budget	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	54,525	38,000	43,000	14,300
Experiments.....	29,170	7,900	15,200	5,400
Ground operations.....	13,605	13,400	14,800	14,200
Total.....	97,300	59,300	73,000	33,900
Space transportation system operations	(11,800)	(37,400)	(49,300)	(51,600)

OBJECTIVES AND STATUS *7 of Plan Stage Funding +8.0M*

(p. RD 5-13) Mission operations accounting (primary mission)

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS

	FY 86 & Prior	FY 87	FY 88	FY 89	FY 90	FY 91	FY 92	BIC	Total
Voyager Extended Missions	113.8	26.9	25.6	48.6	9.3	5.3	5.7		232.2
Uranus Mission	105.1	2.8	2.7	3.3					113.9
Neptune Mission	8.7	26.1	22.9	40.3	9.3	5.3	5.7		118.3
Pioneer Extended Operations	47.2	8.3	7.9	9.3	9.8	10.3	11.0		Continues
Pioneer Venus		30.0	3.1	3.5	3.9	5.3	6.5		
Pioneer 6-11		16.8	3.1	3.5	3.9	3.9	4.3		
Galileo Operations					39.2	48.2	48.1		317.6
Ulysses Operations					7.5	7.0	25.5		40.0
Magellan Operations				17.1	37.8	32.7	5.1		92.7
Mars Observer Operations								50.0	50.0
Viking Extended Operations	7.7								7.7
Helios Extended Mission	1.1								1.1
Flight Support		37.9	41.2	42.7	44.3	38.7	39.0		Continues
TOTAL, NASA	75.1	74.7	112.7	140.4	142.7	115.9	115.9		Continues

NASA 1990 Budget Request (p. RD 5-7)

BASIS OF FY 1990 FUNDING REQUIREMENT				
MAGELLAN DEVELOPMENT				
	1988	1989		1990
	Actual	Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Spacecraft.....	43,395	14,300	23,430	--
Experiments.....	17,017	5,400	5,880	--
Ground operations.....	12,588	14,200	13,790	--
Total.....	73,000	33,900	43,100	--
Mission operations and data analysis.....	(--)	(17,100)	(17,100)	(37,800)
Space transportation system operations.....	(49,900)	(51,600)	(52,600)	(--)

(p. RD 5-15)

BASIS OF FY 1990 FUNDING REQUIREMENT				
MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	1988	1989		1990
	Actual	Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	--	--	--	39,200
Magellan operations.....	--	17,100	17,100	37,800
Voyager extended mission.....	2,308	3,300	2,300	--
Pioneer programs.....	7,894	9,300	8,300	9,800
Voyager/Neptune mission.....	22,312	40,300	40,124	9,300
Voyager interstellar mission.....	--	--	--	15,000
Planetary flight support.....	41,278	42,700	42,876	44,300
Total.....	73,792	112,700	110,700	155,400

NASA 1991 Budget Request (p. RD 5-13) – Operations accounting

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	1989	1990		1991
	Actual	Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	--	39,200	38,035	44,200
Magellan operations.....	17,100	37,800	41,207	32,700
Ulysses operations.....	--	--	--	8,900
Mars observer operations.....	--	--	--	15,000
Voyager extended mission.....	2,300	--	--	--
Pioneer programs.....	8,300	9,800	9,406	10,300
Voyager/Neptune mission.....	40,100	9,300	8,834	5,300
Voyager interstellar mission.....	--	15,000	16,658	14,300
Planetary flight support.....	42,900	44,300	42,716	42,800
Total.....	110,700	155,400	156,856	173,500

(p. RD 5-1) – General accounting (refer to 1990 budget for allocation of 1989 actuals)

OFFICE OF SPACE SCIENCE AND APPLICATIONS						PLANETARY EXPLORATION	
SUMMARY OF RESOURCES REQUIREMENTS							
	1989	1990		1991			
	Actual	Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate	Page		
		(Thousands of Dollars)			Number		
Galileo development.....	73,400	17,400	17,127	--		RD 5-5	
Magellan.....	43,100	--	--	--		RD 5-7	
Ulysses.....	10,300	14,500	14,252	3,300		RD 5-9	
Mars observer.....	102,200	100,500	98,922	68,900		RD 5-9	
Mars balloon relay.....	--	--	4,400	2,000		RD 5-11	
Comet rendezvous asteroid flyby/cassini.....	--	30,000	29,519	148,000		RD 5-13	
Mission operations and data analysis.....	110,700	155,400	156,856	173,500		RD 5-15	
Research and analysis.....	76,900	72,100	70,610	82,500			
Total.....	416,600	326,900	391,686	485,200			
Distribution of Program Amount by Installation							
Johnson Space Center.....	9,312	9,100	8,996	9,400			
Marshall Space Flight Center.....	134	150	150	160			
Goddard Space Flight Center.....	17,870	17,500	17,291	18,200			
Jet Propulsion Laboratory.....	326,324	308,950	304,833	393,440			
Ams Research Center.....	15,074	15,700	13,543	14,200			
Langley Research Center.....	25	--	--	--			
Headquarters.....	47,861	47,500	46,873	49,800			
Total.....	416,600	326,900	391,686	485,200			

NASA 1992 Budget Request (p. RD 5-1)

SUMMARY OF RESOURCES REQUIREMENTS					
	1990	1991		1992	
	Actual	Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate	Page
		(Thousands of Dollars)			Number
Galileo development.....	17,127	--	--	--	
Magellan.....	--	--	--	--	
Ulysses.....	14,252	3,300	3,034	--	RD 5-4
Mars observer.....	98,922	68,900	78,328	54,400	RD 5-6
Mars balloon relay.....	--	4,400	1,497	1,200	RD 5-6
Comet rendezvous asteroid flyby/cassini.....	29,519	148,000	145,000	328,000	RD 5-8
Mission operations and data analysis.....	155,956	173,500	161,175	150,500	RD 5-10
Research and analysis.....	70,672	82,500	87,866	93,200	RD 5-12
Total.....	390,848	485,200	457,100	627,300	

(p. RD 5-10) Mission Operations

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	1990	1991		1992
	Actual	Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	37,315	44,200	49,120	57,700
Magellan operations.....	41,207	32,700	32,700	29,200
Ulysses operations.....	--	8,900	8,346	--
Mars observer enhancement.....	--	15,000	--	--
Pioneer programs.....	9,406	10,300	9,560	10,900
Voyager/Neptune data analysis.....	8,834	5,300	3,400	5,700
Voyager interstellar mission.....	16,658	14,300	14,385	--
Planetary flight support.....	42,536	42,800	43,664	47,000
Total.....	155,956	173,500	161,175	150,500

NASA 1993 Budget Request (p. RD 5-9)

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	1991	1992		1993
	Actual	Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	48,074	57,700	57,700	63,000
Magellan operations.....	43,300	29,200	38,200	7,000
Ulysses operations.....	7,977	--	--	--
Mars observer operations.....	--	--	--	45,600
Pioneer operations.....	9,560	10,900	10,600	--
Voyager/Neptune data analysis.....	3,400	5,700	5,700	6,000
Voyager interstellar mission.....	14,177	--	--	--
Planetary flight support.....	43,664	47,000	43,900	48,700
Total.....	170,152	150,500	156,100	170,300

NASA 1994 Budget Request (p. RD 5-9)

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	1992	1993		1994
	Actual	Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	57,700	63,000	59,429	57,600
Magellan operations.....	45,100	7,000	7,000	5,100
Mars observer operations.....	--	45,600	40,526	34,300
Pioneer programs.....	10,600	--	--	--
Voyager/Neptune data analysis.....	4,300	6,000	5,010	5,700
Planetary flight support.....	43,021	48,700	51,517	58,000
Total.....	160,721	170,300	163,482	160,700

NASA 1995 Budget Request (p. SAT 1.2-12)

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	FY 1993	FY 1994		FY 1995
		(Thousands of dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	59,429	59,900	59,900	70,700
Magellan operations.....	7,000	7,000	7,000	11,800
Mars observer operations.....	40,526	10,300*	--	--
Voyager/Neptune data analysis.....	5,010	4,300	--	--
Planetary flight support.....	51,500	55,400	57,000	57,000
Total.....	163,465	141,700	141,700	127,700

* Funds to be transferred to Mars Surveyor program

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SAT 1.2-19)

MISSION OPERATIONS AND DATA ANALYSIS				
	FY 1994	FY 1995		FY 1996
		(Thousands of Dollars)		
Galileo operations.....	59,400	70,700	75,100	75,100
Magellan operations.....	11,800	--	--	--
Voyager neptune data analysis.....	4,300	--	--	--
Near earth asteroid operations.....	--	--	3,300	3,300
Planetary flight support.....	55,200	46,500	49,400	49,400
Total.....	130,700	117,200	127,800	127,800

Magellan References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Magellan*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved Mar 3, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/magellan.htm .

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NASA. *Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/experiment/display.action?id=1989-033B-01> , downloaded Mar 7, 2024.

NASA. *Magellan Mission at a Glance*. Solar System Exploration – Magellan Mission to Venus. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/magellan/fact.html>, viewed Apr 1, 2024.

GAO. *Space Exploration – Cost, Schedule, and Performance of NASA’s Magellan Mission to Venus*. GAO Home - Reports & Testimonies. May 27, 1988, NSIAD-88-130FS, <https://www.gao.gov/products/nsiad-88-130fs>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

Mars Climate Orbiter

Mission Attributes Mars Climate Orbiter	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	1998-073A
Program	MPLMCO 1 of 2
Destination	Mars
Success	Failure
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7425
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	37.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	37.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	37.9
Initial Mission Life (years)	2.1
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.8
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.0
Phase A - Award	11/1/1995
PDR	3/1/1996
CDR	1/1/1997
Launch	12/11/1998
On Station	9/23/1999
Extend Mission	9/23/1999
End Mission	9/23/1999
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	629
Fuel	291
S/V Dry	338
S/V Bus	294
S/V Payload	44
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	6.72
Objectives	6
Deployments	1
Cost	
Start	1996
Launch	1999
Budget \$	183.6
Realized \$	183.25
Budget Schedule	39
Realized Schedule	39
Then \$	\$ 147.95
Development	\$ 94.50
Launch	\$ 45.30
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 8.15
Extended	-
NSH 2023\$	\$ 285.60
Development	\$ 183.25
Launch	\$ 87.30
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 15.05
Extended	-
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 243.85
Development	\$ 156.20
Launch	\$ 74.60
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 13.05
Extended	-
Payload	
Instruments	2
Mass (kg)	44
Power (W, ave)	45
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	1000
Perihelion	500
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m ²)	11.0
S/A Type	2-axis Gimbal
Blank	-

- Deployments: 1
 - Solar array x 1
- Objectives:
 - Monitor the daily weather and atmospheric conditions, (1)
 - Record changes on the Martian surface due to wind and other atmospheric effects, (2)
 - Determine temperature profiles of the atmosphere, (3)
 - Monitor the water vapor and dust content of the atmosphere, (4) and
 - Look for evidence of past climate change. (5)
 - Communication relay. (+1)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

From Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Space: 5.7 m
- Launch mass: 629 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 291 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 338 kg
 - Bus: 294 kg
 - Payload: 44.0 kg
- S/A Area: 11.0 m² – single wing, 2-axis gimbal
- Power (1 Au): 1000 W
- Power (station): 500 W
- Science
 - MARCI: Mars Climate Orbiter Color Imager
 - PMIRR: Pressure Modulated Infrared Radiometer

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-28)

Mars Surveyor Program
 The Mars Surveyor program is a series of small missions designed to resume the detailed exploration of Mars. The first mission in this program was approved as a new start in FY 1994, the Mars Global Surveyor mission. Future small missions are targeted for launch in the launch windows that occur approximately every two years.

The budgetary estimates below are the amounts indicated in the budget justification within the Space Science/Planetary Exploration section in the Science, Aeronautics and Technology appropriation. The specific write-up for the Mars Global Surveyor includes the amounts for the development of the spacecraft and instruments, two years of mission operations, and launch services. It does not include the NASA civil service workforce salary and expenses, the use of government facilities and general and administrative support used to carry out the program. A more detailed description of the program goals, objectives and activities is provided in the specific budget justification narrative.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)									
	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
MARS GLOBAL SURVEYOR		14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4					140.2
FUTURE MISSIONS			1.4	80.3	80.1	98.6	104.2	107.3		Continues

Mars Global Surveyor
 This mission will obtain a majority of the expected science return from the lost Mars Observer mission by flying a science payload comprised of spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. Launch is planned for November 1996 on a Delta II launch vehicle. The funding estimates provided below do not include the previous expenditures of spare Mars Observer instruments or the amount recovered from the prime contractor after the Mars Observer untimely failure.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)									
	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4					140.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					16.6	19.8	20.8			57.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT			21.8	20.1	10.4					52.3
TOTAL		14.6	79.8	78.3	36.4	19.8	20.8			249.7

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-28)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander
 The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on a 4ed-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulated Infrared Radiometer (PMIRR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)									
	PRIOR	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		52.3	77.5	40.5	13.3					183.6
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					10.3	21.3	15.0			46.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT			11.2	26.0	29.6	16.4				83.2
TRAINING & DATA SUPPORT					0.2	0.4	0.3			0.9
TOTAL		63.5	109.5	70.1	40.2	21.7	15.3			314.5

- Formerly Mars Surveyor '98 Orbiter
- Failed due to navigation errors (unit of measure), missed target altitude.
- Follow-on to the Mars Surveyor program (Mars Global Surveyor)
- Mission life: 1 year cruise and 3-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
- Extension: none
- Status: Failed
 - Operations () –
- Instruments
 - MARCI (2.0 kg, 4.0 W)
 - PMIRR (42.0 kg, 41 W) – Mars Observer payload instrument
- Bus Volume: 2.1 x 1.6 x 2.0 m³

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on Med-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin Aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer (PMIRR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		52.4	86.9	40.5	13.3					193.1
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					10.3	21.3	21.9	22.7		76.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT		7.4	29.8	38.8	7.2					83.1
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT					0.2	0.4	0.3			0.9
TOTAL		59.8	116.7	79.3	30.9	21.7	22.2	22.7		353.3

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-27)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on a Med-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin Aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer (PMIRR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		52.4	86.3	41.1	13.3					193.1
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					8.3	12.3	10.3	7.5	CONT.	38.4
LAUNCH SUPPORT		12.5	31.9	38.7	7.2					90.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT					0.2	0.4	0.3			0.9
TOTAL		64.9	118.2	79.8	29.0	12.7	10.6	7.5		322.7

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-41)

MARS SURVEYOR PROGRAM

	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000
	79,600	22,000	126,800
98 Orbiter and Lander.....	71,200	150,700	4,100
Mars Network.....	--	--	5,000
Micromissions.....	37,100	55,700	114,800
Future Missions.....	142,700	148,700	150,900
ELV (Non-add).....			
Total	187,900	228,400	250,700

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander consisted of the Mars Climate Orbiter (MCO) and the Mars Polar Lander (MPL). MCO was intended to study the planet's weather for one Martian year, acquiring data to help scientists better understand the Martian climate. The MPL was to focus primarily on Mars' climate and water. The MPL mission would search for near-surface ice and possible surface records of cyclic climate change, and characterize physical processes key to the seasonal cycles of water, carbon dioxide and dust on Mars. MCO launched in December 1998 and MPL launched in January 1999; however, both missions failed upon arrival at Mars.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	FY 99	FY 00	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		179.8	9.2							189.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT		83.0	7.7							90.7
MISSION OPERATIONS			9.4	3.6	8.9	6.4	3.5			31.8
DATA ANALYSIS			0.7	1.6	1.2	0.9				4.4
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT			0.2	0.4	0.3					0.9
TOTAL		262.8	27.2	5.6	10.4	7.3	3.5			316.8

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-22)

1998 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander consisted of the Mars Climate Orbiter (MCO) and the Mars Polar Lander (MPL). MCO was intended to study the planet's weather for one Martian year, acquiring data to help scientists better understand the Martian climate. The MPL was to focus primarily on Mars' climate and water. The MPL mission would search for near-surface ice and possible surface records of cyclic climate change, and characterize physical processes key to the seasonal cycles of water, carbon dioxide and dust on Mars. MCO launched in December 1998 and MPL launched in January 1999; however, both missions failed upon arrival at Mars.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		189.7								189.7
LAUNCH SUPPORT		90.7								90.7
MISSION OPERATIONS			9.4	5.6						15.0
DATA ANALYSIS										
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT			0.2	0.4						0.6
TOTAL		290.0	6.0							296.0

Mars Climate Orbiter References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Climate Orbiter (MCO)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars_climate_orbiter.htm.

NASA. *Mars Climate Orbiter*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1998-073A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

NASA. (1999) *Mars Climate Orbiter Arrival – Press Kit*. Sep 1999. https://mars.nasa.gov/internal_resources/812/, downloaded Mar 12, 2024.

Mars Exploration Rovers - Spirit

Mission Attributes		
MERA - Spirit		
Last Updated	9/13/2024	
Definition	COSPASAR 2003-027A	
Program	Mars	
Destination	Mars	
Success	Success	
Type	Rover	
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925	
Schedule	Initial Design Duration (months) 34.0 Realized Design Duration (months) 34.0 Calculated Design Duration (months) 37.8 Initial Mission Life (years) 0.2 Realized Mission Life (years) 6.8 Extended Mission Life (years) 6.0 Phase A - Award 5/1/2000 PDR 2/1/2001 CDR 12/11/2001 Launch 6/10/2003 On Station 1/4/2004 Extend Mission 4/3/2004 End Mission 3/22/2010	
Technical Scope	Launch Mass 1063 Fuel 45 S/V Dry S/V Bus S/V Payload 190 Probe/Rover Cruise 193 Lander 348 Aeroshield + 287 Bus Volume (m³) 5.52 Objectives 7 Deployments 3	
Cost	Start 2000 Launch 2003 Budget \$ 328.6 Realized \$ 399 Budget Schedule 34 Realized Schedule 34 Then \$ 483.30 Development \$ 321.50 Launch \$ 50.60 Operations - Primary \$ 26.90 Extended \$ 84.30 NSII 2023S \$ 800.50 Development \$ 547.20 Launch \$ 86.80 Operations - Primary \$ 43.00 Extended \$ 123.50 PCEPI 2023S \$ 720.70 Development \$ 489.90 Launch \$ 77.50 Operations - Primary \$ 39.00 Extended \$ 114.30	
Payload	Instruments 7 Mass (kg) 190 Power (W, ave) 20 RTG or S/A S/A S/A Power - BoL 1 Au 300 Perihelion 140 Aphelion S/A Area (m2) 1.5 S/A Type 2 fixed Blank -	

Mars Exploration Rovers - Opportunity

Mission Attributes		
MERB - Opportunity		
Last Updated	9/13/2024	
Definition	COSPASAR 2003-032A	
Program	Mars	
Destination	Mars	
Success	Success	
Type	Rover	
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925H	
Schedule	Initial Design Duration (months) 34.0 Realized Design Duration (months) 35.0 Calculated Design Duration (months) 38.8 Initial Mission Life (years) 0.2 Realized Mission Life (years) 14.9 Extended Mission Life (years) 14.1 Phase A - Award 5/1/2000 PDR 2/1/2001 CDR 12/11/2001 Launch 7/8/2003 On Station 1/21/2004 Extend Mission 4/20/2004 End Mission 6/10/2018	
Technical Scope	Launch Mass 1063 Fuel 45 S/V Dry S/V Bus S/V Payload 190 Probe/Rover Cruise 193 Lander 348 Aeroshield + 287 Bus Volume (m³) 5.52 Objectives 7 Deployments 3	
Cost	Start 2000 Launch 2003 Budget \$ 328.6 Realized \$ 399 Budget Schedule 34 Realized Schedule 34 Then \$ 595.60 Development \$ 321.50 Launch \$ 50.60 Operations - Primary \$ 26.90 Extended \$ 196.60 NSII 2023S \$ 940.10 Development \$ 547.20 Launch \$ 86.80 Operations - Primary \$ 43.00 Extended \$ 263.10 PCEPI 2023S \$ 854.60 Development \$ 489.90 Launch \$ 77.50 Operations - Primary \$ 39.00 Extended \$ 248.20	
Payload	Instruments 7 Mass (kg) 190 Power (W, ave) 20 RTG or S/A S/A S/A Power - BoL 1 Au 300 Perihelion 140 Aphelion S/A Area (m2) 1.5 S/A Type 2 fixed Blank -	

Mars Exploration Rovers

- Two identical robotic geologists, 2nd rover mission
- Mission life: 90 days plus cruise
- Extension: each rover mission was extended until non-operation on March 22, 2010, and Jun 10, 2018
- Status: Operational (successful)
- Instruments – Athena Science Package (peak power values – sequential operations, heaters, etc., assume max instrument power plus 50% of second instrument – 20W ave)
 - PanCam (0.54 kg, 6.5 W)
 - Mini-TES (2.4 kg, 5.6 W)
 - MB (0.55 kg, 2 W)
 - APXS (4.0 kg, 17.4 W)
 - MI (0.29 kg, 4.8 W)
 - RAT (0.72 kg, 0 W)
 - RSS (part of rover)
 - MA ()
 - CT ()
- Bus Volume: (rover) 1.5 x 2.3 x 1.6 m³
- Deployments: 5
 - Solar Array x 2
 - Entry separation x 1
 - Airbags x 1
 - Instruments Deployment Device x 1
- Objectives:
 - Search for and characterize a variety of rocks and soils that hold clues to past water activity, (1)
 - Determine the distribution and composition of minerals, rocks, and soil surrounding the landing sites, (2)
 - Determine what geologic processes have shaped the local terrain and influenced the chemistry, (3)
 - Perform “ground truth” of surface observations made by Mars orbiter instruments, (4)
 - Search for iron-bearing materials, identify and quantify relative amounts of specific mineral types that contain water or form in water, (5)
 - Characterize the mineralogy and textures of rocks and soil and determine the processes that created them, (6) and
 - Search for geological clues to the environmental conditions that existed when liquid water was present and assess whether those environments were conducive to life.
- Manufacturer: JPL

- Cruise Fuel: kg
- Backshell (Aeroshell): 209 kg
 - Parachute System: kg
 - Ballast: kg
- Lander: 348 kg
- Rover: 185 kg
 - Payload: 8.5 kg
- Heat Shield: 78 kg.
- Power: S/A
- S/A Area: 1.51 m²
- Power (1 Au): 300 W
- Power (station): 140 W ave
- Science
 - PanCam: Panoramic Camera
 - Mini-TES: Miniature Thermal Emission Spectrometer
 - MB: Mossbauer Spectrometer
 - APXS: Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer
 - MI: Microscopic Imager
 - RAT: Rock Abrasion Tool
 - RSS: Radio Science Experiment
 - MA: Magnet Array (not included in instrumentation)
 - CT: Calibration Targets (not included in instrumentation)

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)

In 2003, two powerful new Mars rovers will be on their way to the red planet. With far greater mobility than the 1997 Mars Pathfinder rover, these robotic explorers will be able to trek up to 100 meters (about 110 yards) across the surface each Martian day. Each rover will carry a sophisticated set of instruments that will allow it to search for evidence of liquid water that may have been present in the planet's past. The rovers will be identical to each other, but will land at different regions of Mars. The rovers will be launched separately in May and June of 2003, and will arrive at Mars in October of 2004.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		18.9	270.6	169.5	74.1					533.1
LAUNCH SUPPORT	(23.0)	(4.6)	31.4	37.5	32.2					101.1
MISSION OPERATIONS						3.6	27.3	4.7		35.6
DATA ANALYSIS						8.6	TBD	TBD		29.9
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT						TBD	TBD	TBD		
TOTAL		18.9	302.0	207.0	118.5	48.6	4.7			699.7

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-56)

2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER) - Lifecycle cost

	Prior	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	FY 06	FY 07	BTC	Total
Development	18.9	296.0	245.2	122.1	41.1	17.0				740.3
Launch Support	18.9	263.7	199.5	81.4						563.5
Operations		32.3	45.7	32.5						110.5
Data Analysis				5.9	25.7	4.4				36.0
[Est. Civil Servant FTE]	4	20	19	13	13					30.3

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 3-8)

BUDGET/LIFE CYCLE COST

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	Prior	FY02	FY03	FY04	FY05	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget (LCC)	337.6	277.6	122.1	51.8	11.6		800.6	
Phase A	(5.4)						(5.4)	
Development	337.6	277.6	113.6				729.4	
Operations		5.9	26.6	4.5			37.0	
Data Analysis		2.3	25.2	7.9			34.5	
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget		+32.4		+19.7	-5.8		+37.8	Reason for Change:
- Development		32.4					32.4	Resolving mass & sched prob.
- Operations			0.9	0.1			1.0	
- Data Analysis			9.8	-5.6			4.2	Added sci seq contingency.
FY 2003 President's Budget (LCC)	337.6	245.2	122.1	41.1	17.0		763.3	
Development	337.6	245.2	113.6				697.0	
Operations		5.9	25.7	4.4			36.0	
Data Analysis		2.3	15.4	12.6			30.3	
Initial Baseline (LCC)	343.6	207.0	118.5	48.6	4.7		722.7	
Development	343.6	207.0	108.3				657.2	Includes ELV.
Operations		3.8	27.3	4.7			35.6	
Data Analysis		8.6	21.3				29.9	

Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
FY 2002, FY 2003, Prior and BTC are not in full cost.

Not listed in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Lander mission
- Launch mass: 1063 kg.
 - Ballast (Adapter, unaccounted mass): 50 kg
 - Cruise Stage: 193 kg

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 3-5)

BUDGET				
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	Change	FY 2005 Comments
Mars Exploration	506.4	595.1	+95.8	690.9
Development	303.5	182.4	-78.2	104.2
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers	151.5			
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)	146.9	182.4	-78.2	104.2
Small Development Projects	5.2			
Operations	26.2	44.5	-34.6	9.9
Research	27.7	63.5	-2.3	61.2
Technology	142.9	304.7	+210.9	\$15.6 Supports new space exploration vision

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

(p. ESA 3-13)

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRESBUD	26.2	44.5	9.9	
Mars Global Surveyor	6.0	4.4		
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.5	9.9		
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)	5.9	26.4	1.6	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)			4.2	
Mars Multi-Mission Operations	3.9	3.8	4.1	
Changes since 2004 PRESBUD	+0.2	-0.3		
2001 Mars Odyssey	-0.1	-0.1		Full cost adjustments
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)		-0.1		Full cost adjustments; MO&DA realignment
Mars Multi-Mission Operations	+0.4			Full cost adjustments
FY2004 PRESBUD	26.0	44.5		
Mars Global Surveyor	6.0	4.4		
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.6	10.0		
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)	5.9	26.5		
Mars Multi-Mission Operations	3.5	3.8		

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

- NASA 2006 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2007 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2008 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2009 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2010 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2011 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2012 Budget Request (p.) – nothing
- NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-49)

FY 2013 BUDGET

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual	Estimate	Notional				
	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	386.8	341.4	214.4	190.1	171.4	261.6	503.1
Mars Research and Analysis	17.4	19.0	15.2	15.2	15.3	15.3	15.3
Mars Technology	2.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	7.0	23.0	75.0
Mars Mission Operations	1.6	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9
Mars Extended Operations	0.0	0.0	53.7	40.1	56.3	51.2	51.4
Mars Next Decade	8.0	4.3	62.0	72.8	72.8	151.7	346.1
Mars Program Management	21.0	27.5	13.5	17.6	18.1	18.5	13.4
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.1	12.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2003 Mars Exploration Rover	13.6	15.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Express	0.9	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter	30.1	40.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2011 Mars Science Laboratory	242.9	174.0	65.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer	6.0	11.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2016 ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter	32.6	27.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-127.0				
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-37.2%				

- NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-43)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$15.0 – FY2012 Actual
- NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-39)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$13.2 – FY2013 Actual
- NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-38)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$14.0 – FY2014 Actual
- NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-48)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$13.7 – FY2015 Actual

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-50)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$14.2 – FY2016 Actual

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-69)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$12.5 – FY2017 Actual

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-69)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$12.5 – FY2018 Actual

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-76)
Mars Exploration Rover 2003 - \$3.6 – FY2019 Actual

* Includes additional \$15M for first extended ops:
<http://www.planetary.org/explore/space-topics/space-missions/mer-updates/2004/04-09-mer-update.html>
 ** 2 - 4th mission extensions totaled \$91M. Source:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20071019042407/http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/21327647/>

MER A (MER 2) Spirit Rover References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Exploration Rover A, B (MER A, B / Spirit / Opportunity)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars_exploration_rover.htm

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NASA. (2003) *Mars Exploration Rover Launches*. Jun 2003. https://mars.nasa.gov/internal_resources/827/, viewed Mar 14, 2024.

Cook, Richard A., 2004, *The Mars Exploration Rover Project*, <https://hdl.handle.net/2014/40202>, International Astronautical Congress, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada, October 02, 2004., JPL Open Repository.

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MSNBC. *NASA extends the Mars rovers' mission*. Associated Press. Oct. 16, 2007. <https://web.archive.org/web/20071019042407/http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/21327647/>, viewed Apr 24, 2024.

MER B (Mer 1) Opportunity Rover References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Exploration Rover A, B (MER A, B / Spirit / Opportunity)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024,

from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars_exploration_rover.htm.

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Mars Global Surveyor

Mission Attributes Mars Global Surveyor	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	1996-062A
Program	
Destination	Mars
Success	Success
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	26.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	25.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	25.6
Initial Mission Life (years)	5.7
Realized Mission Life (years)	10.0
Extended Mission Life (years)	4.8
Phase A - Award	10/1/1994
PDR	
CDR	2/1/1996
Launch	11/7/1996
On Station	9/12/1997
Extend Mission	2/1/2002
End Mission	11/2/2006
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	1030.5
Fuel	360.5
S/V Dry	666.3
S/V Bus	590
S/V Payload	76.3
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	2.32
Objectives	8
Deployments	4
Cost	
Start	1994
Launch	1996
Budget \$	140.2
Realized \$	130.7
Budget Schedule	31
Realized Schedule	34
Then \$	\$ 303.00
Development	\$ 130.70
Launch	\$ 52.60
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 74.90
Extended	\$ 44.80
NSII 2023\$	\$ 579.60
Development	\$ 263.90
Launch	\$ 105.20
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 138.20
Extended	\$ 72.30
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 496.60
Development	\$ 222.50
Launch	\$ 88.90
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 119.60
Extended	\$ 65.60
Payload	
Instruments	6
Mass (kg)	76.3
Power (W, ave)	76.6
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	1980
Perihelion	940
Aphelion	660
S/A Area (m ²)	13.3
S/A Type	2 articulated
Blank	-

Mars Global Surveyor

- The mission costs about \$154 million to develop, \$65 million to launch, and mission operations and data analysis about \$20 million/year.
- Extension of Mars Observer – JPL had flown MO for 8 months (experience); completed 8 years of development for the MO spacecraft, mission, and science instruments; and had a complete set of spare hardware for the MO spacecraft and spare elements of the science payload. New spacecraft composite bus structure and a new dual-mode propulsion system. JPL brought \$30M of spacecraft hardware and upwards of \$80M of engineering design into the partnership (JPL and Lockheed Martin Denver)
- Mission life: 1 year cruise and 3-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
- Extension: extended three times, 3rd extension was 10/1/2008 (through 2015), currently operational (date 3/17/2024 in database)

- Premature loss of mission – result of a series of events linked to a computer error made five months before the assumed battery failure.
- Status: Completed
 - Operations (4 years 3 months): arrived Mars (9/12/1997), Operational (September 1998 – extended aerobraking due to solar array latch issue),
 - Extended Operations: extended mission (February 2002), loss of communications (November 2, 2006)
- Instruments (five primary instruments and spacecraft telecommunications system)
 - Accelerometer (0 kg, 0 W)
 - MAG/ER (5.4 kg, 4.6 W)
 - MOC (21.0 kg, 8.0 W)
 - MOLA (25.9 kg, 30.9 W)
 - MRCE: (10.5 kg, 12.5 W)
 - RS (1.3 kg, 3 W)
 - TES (14.1 kg, 13.2 W)
- Bus Volume: 1.17 x 1.17 x 1.7 m³
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 2
 - HGA x 1
 - MAG/ER boom x 1
- Objectives: (a replacement for Mars Observer science)
 - Characterize surface morphology at high spatial resolution to quantify surface characteristics and geological processes, (1)
 - Determine the composition and map the distribution of surface minerals, rocks, and ices, and measure surface thermophysical properties, (2)
 - Determine globally the topography, geodetic figure, and gravitational field, (3)
 - Establish the nature of the magnetic field and map the crustal remnant field, (4)
 - Study surface-atmospheric interaction by monitoring surface features, polar caps, polar thermal balance, atmospheric dust, and condensate clouds over a seasonal cycle, (5)
 - Study surface-atmospheric interaction by monitoring surface features, polar caps, polar thermal balance, atmospheric dust, and condensate clouds over a seasonal cycle, (6) added to the mission.
 - Provide multiple years of on-orbit relay communications capability for Mars landers and atmospheric vehicles from any nation interested in participating in the International Mars Surveyor Program, and
 - Support landing site selection planning for future Mars Surveyor Program missions through the acquisition of high-resolution imaging and other relevant data sets.
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 1030.5 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 385 kg (216.5 kg hydrazine, 144 kg N2O4 = 360.5 kg)
 - Space Vehicle: 590 kg
 - Payload: 76.3 kg
- S/A Area: 13.3 m² (two panels 3.5 m x 1.9 m)
- Power (1 Au): 1500 W
- Power (station Perihelion): 940 W
- Power (station aphelion): 640 W
- Science
 - Accelerometer
 - MAG/ER: Magnetometer/Electron Reflectometer
 - MOC: Mars Orbiter Camera
 - MOLA: Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter
 - MRCE: Mars Relay Communications Experiment
 - RS: Radio Science Investigations
 - TES: Thermal Emission Spectrometer

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

Mars Global Surveyor
 This mission will obtain a majority of the expected science return from the lost Mars Observer mission by flying a science payload comprised of spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. Launch is planned for November 1996 on a Delta II launch vehicle. The funding estimates provided below do not include the previous expenditures of spare Mars Observer instruments or the amount recovered from the prime contractor after the Mars Observer untimely failure.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)										
	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4					140.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					16.4	19.8	20.8			57.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT			21.8	20.1	10.4					52.3
TOTAL		14.6	79.8	78.3	36.4	19.8	20.8			249.7

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-28)

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)										
	PRIOR	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	Balance	TOTAL
MARS GLOBAL SURVEYOR										
DEVELOPMENT	14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4						140.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				16.4	19.6	10.4				46.4
LAUNCH SUPPORT		21.8	20.1	6.4						48.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2				1.6
TOTAL	14.8	80.0	78.7	32.5	19.9	10.6				296.5

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)										
	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	72.6	58.1								130.7
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS			16.4	19.6	10.4					46.4
LAUNCH SUPPORT	21.8	24.4	6.4							52.6
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2					1.6
TOTAL	94.8	82.9	23.1	19.9	10.6					231.3

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-27)

Mars Global Surveyor

This mission will obtain a majority of the expected science return from the lost Mars Observer mission by flying a science payload comprised of spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. Launch occurred in November 1996 on a Delta II launch vehicle, and MGS entered Mars orbit in September 1997. The funding estimates provided below do not include the previous expenditures on spare Mars Observer instruments or the amount recovered from the prime contractor after the Mars Observer failure.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)										
	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	130.7									130.7
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS		46.2	6.4							52.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT										
TOTAL	176.9	21.1	19.5	14.2	8.7	6.2	3.1			249.7

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-46)

BASIS OF FY 2000 FUNDING REQUIREMENT

MISSION OPERATIONS			
	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000
(Thousands of Dollars)			
HST operations	2,300	2,100	2,100
Other mission operations	136,400	104,200	83,200
Total	138,700	106,300	85,300

(p. SAT 1-50)

Mars Global Surveyor (launched November 7, 1996; expected operations beyond FY 2000)
 MGS will return an unprecedented amount of data regarding Mars surface features, atmosphere, and magnetic properties. The spacecraft reached Mars in September 1997 and has begun the aerobanking maneuvers to achieve its desired mapping orbit in March 1999, about one year later than planned due to unanticipated deflections in one of the solar array panels. No loss of science is anticipated.

FY 2000 performance: Acquire 70% of science data available, conduct at least two 5-day atmospheric mapping campaigns, and relay to Earth at least 70% of data transmitted at adequate signal levels by the DS2 Mars microprobes.

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

Mars Global Surveyor

This mission will obtain a majority of the expected science return from the lost Mars Observer mission by flying a science payload comprised of spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. Launch occurred in November 1996 on a Delta II launch vehicle, and MGS entered Mars orbit in September 1997. The funding estimates provided below do not include the previous expenditures on spare Mars Observer instruments or the amount recovered from the prime contractor after the Mars Observer failure.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)											
	PRIOR	FY 99	FY 00	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	BTC	TOTAL	
DEVELOPMENT	130.7									130.7	
LAUNCH SUPPORT	52.6									52.6	
MISSION OPERATIONS	17.9	6.0	11.2	4.7	3.2	3.2	1.8	1.5		48.5	
DATA ANALYSIS	6.3	7.0	4.4	4.8	5.9	1.0	1.0	0.7		31.1	
TOTAL	207.5	13.0	15.6	9.5	9.1	4.2	2.8	2.2		263.9	

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-22)

Mars Global Surveyor (MGS)

Mars Global Surveyor (MGS), the first of the MEP missions, is an orbiter that carries a science payload comprised of 5 of the original 8 spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. MGS was launched successfully in November 1996 aboard a Delta II launch vehicle and has been producing highly valuable science output since it arrived at Mars in September 1997. MGS completed its primary mission on January 31, 2001, and moved immediately into an extended mission phase. In the extended phase MGS will study the most interesting locations on the planet in detail and observe variability on the Martian surface. MGS will also study potential landing sights for the Mars 2003 rovers.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)										
	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	130.7									130.7
LAUNCH SUPPORT	52.6									52.6
MISSION OPERATIONS	23.9	12.8	9.1	4.3						50.1
DATA ANALYSIS	13.3	6.0	8.4	5.9						33.6
TOTAL	220.5	18.8	17.5	10.2						287.0

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 3-14)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget (Operations)	24.8	26.0	44.8	
Mars Global Surveyor (MGS)	7.4	6.0	4.4	
2001 Mars Odyssey	14.0	10.6	10.0	
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)		5.9	29.6	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)				
Mars Multi-Mission Operations	3.4	3.5	3.8	
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget			+1.7	Reason for Change:
Programmatic Changes			+0.1	
2001 Mars Odyssey			+0.1	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)				Full cost.
Full Cost Changes			+1.6	
Indicates budget numbers in full cost. Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit. FY 2002 and FY 2003 are not in full cost.				

(p. SAE 3-16)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget (Research)	23.4	25.5	50.2	
Mars Research & Analysis				
Mars Data Analysis	23.4	25.5	50.2	
Mars Global Surveyor (MGS)	6.7	4.9	2.4	
2001 Mars Odyssey	9.1	9.8	11.0	
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)		2.3	25.2	
Mars Express		0.8	4.6	
ASPERA-3			0.8	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)				
NetLander				
Characterization & MSN Extension	7.6	7.7	12.2	
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget			+16.5	Reason for Change:
Programmatic Changes			+14.5	
Characterization				Added for FY 08.
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)				Added for FY 08.
2001 Mars Odyssey			+1.2	Added reserve for science sequencing.
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)			+9.0	Added reserve for science sequencing.
Mars Express			+0.3	Added reserve for science sequencing.
Future Mars DA			+4.0	Reduced funding for science extension.
Full Cost Changes			+2.0	Full cost.
Indicates budget numbers in full cost. Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit. FY 2002 and FY 2003 are not in full cost.				

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 3-13)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRESBUD	26.2	44.5	9.9	
Mars Global Surveyor	6.0	4.4		
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.5	9.9		
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)	5.9	26.4	1.6	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)			4.2	

(p. ESA 3-16)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRESBUD	27.7	63.5	61.2	
Mars Global Surveyor (MGS)	4.9	2.4		
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.7	10.9	4.2	
2003 Mars Exploration Rovers (MER)	3.6	25.1	10.3	
Mars Express	1.0	4.6	4.3	

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. -)
Mission operations and research (data analysis) switched to Deep Space Mission Systems lump funding.

Mars Global Surveyor References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Global Surveyor (MGS)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved Mar 3, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars_global_surveyor.htm.

NASA. *Mars Global Surveyor*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1996-062A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

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JPL. *Mars Global Surveyor – Press Releases*. Apr 13, 2007. <https://mars.nasa.gov/mgs/newsroom/20070413a.html>, viewed Mar 17, 2024.

Mars Observer

Mission Attributes		Mars Observer		
Last Updated: 9/13/2024				
Definition		1992-063A		
COSPAR	1992-063A			
Program				
Destination	Mars			
Success	Failure			
Type	Orbiter			
Launch Vehicle	Titan 3			
Schedule				
Initial Design Duration (months)	60.0			
Realized Design Duration (months)	60.0			
Calculated Design Duration (months)	49.5			
Initial Mission Life (years)	3.4			
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.9			
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.0			
Phase A - Award	9/1/1988			
PDR	9/1/1998			
CDR	10/1/1990			
Launch	9/25/1992			
On Station	8/21/1993			
Extend Mission	8/21/1993			
End Mission	8/21/1993			
Technical Scope				
Launch Mass	2573		Payload	
Fuel	1346		Instruments	8
S/V Dry	1028		Mass (kg)	139.9
S/V Bus	862		Power (W, ave)	107.7
S/V Payload	139.9		RTG or S/A	s/a
Probe/Rover	-		S/A Power	-
Cruise	-		BoL 1 Au	3400
Lander	-		Perihelion	1408
Aeroshield +	-		Aphelion	1147
Bus Volume (m³)	3.46		S/A Area (m²)	25.9
Objectives	6		S/A Type	2-axis Gimbal
Deployments	4		Blank	-
			k	-
Cost				
Start	1985			
Launch	1992			
Budget \$	458.6			
Realized \$	511.2			
Budget Schedule	60			
Realized Schedule	60			
Then \$	\$ 825.50			
Development	\$ 511.20			
Launch	\$ 293.10			
Operations	-			
Primary	\$ 21.20			
Extended	-			
NSII 2023\$	\$ 2,092.70			
Development	\$ 1,309.30			
Launch	\$ 736.20			
Operations	-			
Primary	\$ 47.20			
Extended	-			
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 1,636.00			
Development	\$ 1,021.20			
Launch	\$ 576.20			
Operations	-			
Primary	\$ 38.60			
Extended	-			

Mars Observer

- The restart of interplanetary science since Voyager
- GAO: 1985 cost estimate \$292.5M (less launch vehicle), 1986 cost estimate \$340.5M, 1987 cost estimate \$513.8M (Challenger accident replan),
- NASA 1989 Budget Replan: \$458.6M (less launch vehicle: \$273.6M, operations: \$50.0M, data analysis: \$19.8M = total: \$802.0M) – which included an addition of \$60M for “spares” (this includes space vehicles and instruments). With LV const of \$160-180M and Upper Stage \$87M.
- Mission life: 1 year cruise, 2-year prime science, and relay (? year) mission (Primary mission: 3.4 years)
- Extension: failed, not extended
- Premature loss of mission – Mars Observer Mission Failure Investigation Board, December 31, 1993
- Status: Failed
- Instruments (five primary instruments and spacecraft telecommunications system)
 - GRS (24.4 kg, 16.3 W)
 - MAG/ER (5.4 kg, 4.6 W) – same
 - MBR (6.2 kg, 12.5 W)
 - MOC (21.0 kg, 22.8 W) – same mass (8.0 W), significant power reduction
 - MOLA (25.9 kg, 28.7 W) – (30.7 W) slight power increase

- PMIR (40.2 kg, 34.1 W)
- TES (14.1 kg, 15.2 W) – (13.2 W) slight power decrease
- USO (1.3 kg, 3.0 W)
- Bus Volume: 2.1 x 1.5 x 11 m³
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 2
 - HGA x 1
 - MAG/ER boom x1
- Objectives: (a replacement for Mars Observer science)
 - Determine the global elemental and mineralogical character of the surface material, (1)
 - Define globally the topography and gravitational field, (2)
 - Establish the nature of the magnetic field, (3)
 - Determine the time and space distribution, abundance, sources, and sinks of volatile material and dust over a seasonal cycle, (4) and
 - Explore the structure and aspects of atmospheric circulation. (5)
 - Communication relay (+1)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 1030.5 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 385 kg (216.5 kg hydrazine, 144 kg N2O4 = 360.5 kg)
 - Space Vehicle: 590 kg
 - Payload: 76.3 kg
- S/A Area: 13.3 m² (two panels 3.5 m x 1.9 m)
- Power (1 Au): 3400 W (scaled from prior missions. Potts provides a detailed power summary; however, the spacecraft's flow skews after launch (to shunt access power) with 4 of 6 solar panels exposed (2 folded during cruise).
- Power (station Perihelion): 1408 W
- Power (station aphelion): 1147 W
- Science
 - GRS: Gamma-ray Spectrometer
 - MAG/ER: Magnetometer/Electron Reflectometer
 - MBR: Mars Balloon Relay
 - MOC: Mars Orbiter Camera
 - MOLA: Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter
 - PMIR: Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer
 - TES: Thermal Emission Spectrometer
 - USO: Ultrastable Oscillator

NASA 1986 Budget Request (p. RD-11)

MARS OBSERVER MISSION (FORMERLY MARS GEOSCIENCE/CLIMATOLOGY ORBITER)

	1984 Actual	1985		1986
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
(Thousands of Dollars)				
Spacecraft development.....	---	6,000	6,000	28,600
Experiments.....	---	5,000	5,000	4,300
Ground Operations.....	---	5,000	1,600	10,900
Total.....	---	16,000	13,000	43,800

NASA 1987 Budget Request (p. RD 5-11)

BASIS OF FY 1987 FUNDING REQUIREMENT

MARS OBSERVER MISSION (FORMERLY MARS GEOSCIENCE/CLIMATOLOGY ORBITER)

	1985 Actual	1986		1987
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
(Thousands of Dollars)				
Spacecraft development.....	2,010	28,600	22,400	33,100
Experiments.....	6,705	4,300	13,900	26,600
Ground Operations.....	2,285	10,900	1,600	3,200
Total.....	13,000	43,800	37,900	62,900
Space transportation system operations	(---)	(---)	(---)	(9,100)

NASA 1988 Budget Request (p. RD 5-11)

MARS OBSERVER MISSION

	1986 Actual	1987		1988
		Amended Budget	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
(Thousands of Dollars)				
Spacecraft development.....	16,185	33,100	11,600	7,800
Experiments.....	16,390	26,600	22,800	18,100
Ground Operations.....	1,225	3,200	1,400	3,400
Total.....	33,800	62,900	35,800	29,300
Space transportation system operations	(18,900)	(9,100)	(6,500)	(15,800)

NASA 1989 Budget Request (p. not numbered, page after RD 5-10)

Description
The MARS Observer mission will provide a spacecraft platform in orbit about Mars from which the entire Martian surface and atmosphere may be mapped for at least one Martian year (243 Earth days).

Launch Date: 1992 (Voyager)
Payload: 8 instruments (27 individual investigations)

Orbit: Circular, low altitude (approx. 350 km), near-polar (93 inclination to equator), sun-synchronous (2 p.m. dayside pass local time)
Design Life: 2 years
Length: 2.2 m
Weight: 1700 kg (spacecraft dry mass)
Diameter: 1.6 m
Launch Vehicle: Shuttle-TOS (Titan III ELV alternative under study)
Foreign Participation: Austria, Federal Republic of Germany, France, United Kingdom

Mission Events
Terminative selection of investigations: April 1986
Final confirmation and selection: April 1987
Arrival at Mars: 1992

Summary
The spacecraft and Transfer Orbit Stage are now under development. The science payload has been confirmed. With the launch date changed to September 1992, the program is being rebaselined. Revised proposals from the spacecraft contractor and the eight instrument investigators are being implemented. Mission design studies are also being conducted for the new launch date.

	Prior	FY 87	FY 88	FY 89	FY 90	FY 91	FY 92	FY 93	EOC	1984
Spacecraft	9.2	13.7	21.2	29.4	38.8	51.1	61.3	70.8	80.3	188.8
Instruments	35.2	14.4	28.4	34.7	42.9	57.9	74.0	89.1	104.2	229.1
Ground Ops	2.4	3.7	4.1	4.7	7.5	10.8	17.4	24.0	30.6	51.6
Developers	41.8	35.8	53.9	102.8	87.4	73.8	54.3	40.8	28.8	420.6
Cost 8 Support	12.2	22.4	3.2	22.3	21.3	---	---	25.4	25.4	272.6
Cost 1 Support	6.2	2.2	3.3	3.8	4.3	4.8	1.3	---	---	18.8

Summary
454.4 - 500
800

(p. RD 5-11)

MARS OBSERVER MISSION

	1987 Actual	1988		1989
		Revised Budget	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
(Thousands of Dollars)				
Spacecraft development.....	15,715	7,800	21,200	39,400
Experiments.....	16,392	17,700	28,600	56,700
Ground operations.....	3,693	3,400	4,100	6,100
Total.....	35,800	28,900	53,900	102,200
Space transportation system operations	(---)	(---)	(---)	(5,000)

NASA 1990 Budget Request (p. RD 5-11)

MARS OBSERVER DEVELOPMENT

	1988 Actual	1989		1990
		Budget Estimate	Current Estimate	Budget Estimate
(Thousands of Dollars)				
Spacecraft.....	26,084	39,400	60,605	61,000
Experiments.....	24,842	56,700	36,095	30,900
Ground operations.....	2,974	6,100	5,500	8,600
Total.....	53,900	102,200	102,200	100,500
Space transportation system operations....	(--)	(5,000)	(5,000)	(44,700)

NASA 1991 Budget Request (p. RD 5-9)

	MARS OBSERVER DEVELOPMENT			
	1989 Actual	1990 Budget Estimate (Thousands of Dollars)	Current Estimate	1991 Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	60,605	61,000	59,522	31,200
Experiments.....	36,095	30,900	30,900	28,400
Ground operations.....	5,500	8,600	8,500	9,300
Total.....	102,200	100,500	98,922	68,900
Mars balloon relay experiment.....	--	--	4,400	2,000
Launch vehicle.....	(5,000)	(44,700)	(44,100)	(98,000)
Upper stage.....	(12,800)	(12,000)	(24,000)	(23,300)

NASA 1992 Budget Request (p. RD 5-6)

	MARS OBSERVER DEVELOPMENT			
	1990 Actual	1991 Budget Estimate (Thousands of Dollars)	Current Estimate	1992 Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	59,522	31,200	34,409	23,936
Experiments.....	30,900	28,400	31,609	21,760
Ground operations.....	8,500	9,300	12,510	8,704
Total.....	98,922	68,900	78,528	54,400
Mars balloon relay experiment.....	4,400	2,000	1,497	1,200
Launch vehicle.....	(39,900)	(98,000)	(98,000)	(44,200)
Upper stage.....	(27,300)	(23,300)	(15,400)	(11,800)

NASA 1993 Budget Request (p. RD 5-5)

	MARS OBSERVER DEVELOPMENT			
	1991 Actual	1992 Budget Estimate (Thousands of Dollars)	Current Estimate	1993 Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	43,020	23,936	33,936	--
Experiments.....	37,128	21,760	31,760	--
Ground operations.....	8,380	8,704	11,204	--
Total.....	88,528	54,400	76,900	--
Mars balloon relay experiment.....	1,497	1,200	1,200	--
Launch vehicle.....	(98,300)	(44,200)	(33,200)	--
Upper stage.....	(12,600)	(11,800)	(11,600)	(200)
Mission operations and data analysis..	--	--	--	(45,600)

NASA 1994 Budget Request (p. RD 4-5)

	MARS OBSERVER DEVELOPMENT			
	1992 Actual	1993 Budget Estimate (Thousands of Dollars)	Current Estimate	1994 Budget Estimate
Spacecraft.....	42,700	--	--	--
Experiments.....	36,000	--	--	--
Ground operations.....	6,300	--	--	--
Total.....	85,000	--	--	--
Mars balloon relay experiment.....	1,200	--	--	--
Mission operations and data analysis..	--	(45,600)	(40,526)	(34,300)
Launch vehicle.....	(32,600)	--	--	--
Upper stage.....	(6,800)	(200)	--	--

NASA 1995 Budget Request (p. not listed)

“Reduce funding for Mars Observer MO&DA (-\$24M)” – this would be from the 1994 MO&DA budget listed as \$45.6 (with an adjustment for Current Estimate of \$40.526). The “reduce funding” would be from the 1994 Budget amount and is accounted for as \$45.6 – 24.0 = \$21.6M for 1994 operations.

Mars Observer References

Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Observer (MO)*. Gunter’s Space Page. Retrieved Mar 3, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mars_observer.htm.

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Mars Pathfinder

Mission Attributes Mars Pathfinder	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	1996-068A
Program	Discovery 2
Destination	Mars
Success	Success
Type	Rover
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	36.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	38.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	38.7
Initial Mission Life (years)	0.6
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.8
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.1
Phase A - Award	10/1/1993
PDR	12/1/1993
CDR	9/1/1994
Launch	12/4/1996
On Station	7/4/1997
Extend Mission	8/4/1997
End Mission	9/27/1997
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	895
Fuel	100
S/V Dry	
S/V Bus	
S/V Payload	
Probe/Rover	16
Cruise	154
Lander	218
Aeroshield +	159
Bus Volume (m³)	0.0936
Objectives	4
Deployments	4
Cost	
Start	1993
Launch	1996
Budget \$	150
Realized \$	174.2
Budget Schedule	38
Realized Schedule	49
Then \$	\$ 258.80
Development	\$ 199.20
Launch	\$ 47.10
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 10.20
Extended	\$ 2.30
NSII 2023\$	\$ 527.60
Development	\$ 407.80
Launch	\$ 95.70
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 19.70
Extended	\$ 4.40
PECEI 2023\$	\$ 443.60
Development	\$ 342.50
Launch	\$ 80.50
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 16.80
Extended	\$ 3.80
Payload	
Instruments	6
Mass (kg)	23
Power (W, ave)	4.5
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL I Au	30
Perihelion	16
Aphelion	
S/A Area (m2)	0.2
S/A Type	body
Blank	-

Mars Pathfinder

- Funded for a 19-month “pre-project phase” for necessary trades for selection of an EDL approach (this is PDResque). – Success due to upfront due diligence, existing state of hardware assessment, cost-conscious design (cost cap design), drawing from interplanetary “heritage.”
- Second Discovery mission – Pathfinder Mission – Sojourner Rover
- Mission life: 7 months (6-month cruise, 1-month rover operations) (Primary mission: 7 months)
- Extension: extended option for up to 1 year of continued limited operations
- Rover and lander science missions
- Status: Successful
 - Operations – July 4 to September 22, 1997 – 77 days

- Instruments
 - XPXS (0.57 kg, 0.3 W) – Sojourner Rover
 - MAE (solar cell dust w/ movable dust cover) – Sojourner Rover
 - RIC (0.12 kg, 4.2 W) – Sojourner Rover
 - WAE (200-1000 angstrom film included with the middle left rover wheel) – Sojourner Rover
 - IMP (11.2 kg, 19 W)
 - GRS (30.3 kg, 32 W)

- Bus Volume Lander: $0.9 \times m^3$ – tetrahedron standing about 0.9 m tall - landed mass 360 kg.

- Bus Volume Rover: $0.65 \times 0.48 \times 0.30 \text{ m}^3$

- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 3
 - Mast Camera
 - Upright mechanism (not used)
 - Rover x 1
- Objectives:
 - Determine the geology and surface morphology, (1)
 - Determine the geochemistry and petrology of soils and rocks, (2)
 - Determine the magnetic and mechanical properties of surface materials, (3) and
 - Conduct a variety of atmospheric investigations and rotational/orbital dynamics of Mars. (4)

- Manufacturer: JPL

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 895 kg (although mission mass is 655 kg)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 100.7 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 331.8 kg (lander mass)
 - Rover: 17.0 kg
- S/A Area Lander: 2.5 m^2 – 178 W
- S/A Area Rover: 0.22 m^2 – 16 W
- Power (1 Au): 30 W
- Power (station): 16 W
- Science
 - XPXS: Alpha Proton X-ray Spectrometer (Sojourner Rover)
 - MAE: Materials Adherence Experiment (Sojourner Rover)
 - RIC: Rover Imaging Cameras (Sojourner Rover)
 - WAE: Wheel Abrasion Experiment
 - IMP: Imager for Mars Pathfinder
 - ASI/MET: Atmospheric Structure Instrument and Meteorology Package

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-20)

Mars Pathfinder

The Mars Pathfinder was approved as a new start in FY 1994 as one of the initial missions in the Discovery Program. The Mars Pathfinder mission will demonstrate the cruise, entry, descent, and landing system approach that will be available for future missions to place a network of small science landers on the Martian surface. Launch is scheduled for December 1996 on a Delta II expendable launch vehicle. The Mars Pathfinder is being conducted as an in-house effort at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. Portions of the science instruments are being provided by Germany and Denmark.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		60.8	77.5	35.9						174.2
MICROROVER		2.8	5.9	6.5	5.8	2.0				25.0
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					9.7	5.9	2.0			17.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT		3	9.6	19.0	18.5	4.9				52.3
TOTAL		3.1	76.3	106.0	60.2	16.6	5.9	2.0		260.1

(p. SAT 1.2-18b) Operations

PLANETARY MOBDA

	PRIOR	FY 1994	FY 1995	FY 1996	FY 1997	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000	BTC	TOTAL
PLANETARY EXPLORATION MOBDA		130.7	117.2	127.8	142.5	145.8	150.3	147.6		
10/89 GALILEO		202.2	59.4	70.7	75.1	66.9	19.3			492.6
4/89 MARSELLAN VOYAGER		153.7	11.8							165.5
10/97 CASSINI		118.4	4.3							122.7
12/95 MARS PATHFINDER						9.7	5.9	2.0		56.3
2/96 NEAR ORNS					3.3	5.4	8.8	22.3	7.8	47.6
DISCOVERY FOLLOW-ON										20.1
MARS SURVEYOR						16.6	19.8	20.8		27.2
FLIGHT SUPPORT			55.2	46.5	49.4	43.9	42.7	41.7	42.0	276.6
CIVIL SERVANTS		23	16	16	37	45	45	45		

(p. 1.2-27b) Launch Vehicle (Delta II)

PLANETARY EXPLORATION

SUMMARY OF LAUNCH SERVICES

	PRIOR	FY 94	FY 95	FY 96	FY 97	FY 98	FY 99	FY 100	BTC	TOTAL
SMALL (PEGASUS)					3.0	10.0	17.0	17.0		47.0
NEW MILLENNIUM SPACECRAFT					3.0	10.0	17.0	17.0	CONT.	CONT.
MED-LITE (TBD)				13.3	44.1	70.9	84.5	75.4	89.0	377.2
MARS SURVEYOR COMM ORBITER				5.1	13.6	13.9	5.6			38.2
MARS SURVEYOR NEOLANDER				5.1	13.6	13.9	5.6			38.2
MARS SURVEYOR COMM ORBITER					5.7	15.0	15.2	3.6	39.5	201
MARS SURVEYOR GEOLANDER					5.7	15.0	15.2	3.6	39.5	201
DISCOVERY #3			2.8	13.1	13.8	9.9				39.6
DISCOVERY #4					3.0	13.8	14.4	10.4		41.6
DISCOVERY #5							3.4	15.1	10.8	43.4
DISCOVERY #6								15.1	27.0	45.5
DISCOVERY #7								3.3	44.0	47.3
TAKES				0.3	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.1		5.4
MEDIUM (DELTA II)	0.3	34.2	56.7	49.8	15.3					156.3
MARS GLOBAL SURVEYOR			21.8	20.1	10.4					52.3
MARS PATHFINDER	0.3	9.6	19.0	18.5	4.9					52.3
NEAR		24.6	15.9	11.2						51.7

(p. SAT 5-12b) Rover

SPACECRAFT & REMOTE SENSING SUMMARY

	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Description of Work
Total Spacecraft & Remote Sensing	183.3	144.3	177.8	181.4	161.6	160.2	163.0	
Earth Applications Systems	57.8	49.8	71.1	64.1	64.6	65.1	67.2	
Earth Orbiting Spacecraft Technology	13.9	11.2	18.0	15.0	15.5	16.0	17.0	Photovoltaic arrays, batteries, power systems, maniaids and antennas, coordination instrument
Operations	5.9	2.9	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	Arch/Infrared tech. to ease use of EODSDS data
Sensors & Instruments	14.2	13.9	17.8	16.0	15.0	16.0	17.1	Instrument technologies for earth sensing
Commercial Remote Sensing	9.8	11.2	15.7	13.0	13.0	13.0	13.0	Applications for development of commercial remote sensing
Commercial Applications	4.9	4.4	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	Non-satellite applications of remote sensing technology
Systems Analysis	1.2	1.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	Identify areas for advanced new technologies
Center for Commercial Dev of Space (CCDS)	3.3	2.3	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	Institute for Technology Dev. Center for Mapping (Ohio State)
USERCA/Advanced Design Program	1.7	1.0	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	Foster next generation engineers/technologists
HEDUCAS	1.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	Research by technology back-channel university inventives
Software Release	1.5	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	West Virginia-system improvements thru reuse
Space & Planetary	55.8	50.5	50.1	53.5	53.7	53.8	54.5	
Heat-Earth Probe	3.8	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	Intake new technologies into missions, "bridge the gap"
Deep Space Probe	4.8	3.0	4.0	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	Sample analytically, microlander tech. for Mars
Specialized Technology	8.8	7.2	9.0	8.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	Smaller, more autonomous, highly capable spacecraft
Rover Technology	8.2	3.5	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	Systems technology for manned/unmanned rovers
Sensors & Instruments	13.7	10.4	17.0	16.0	17.2	17.3	18.0	Technologies for observation/instrument instruments
Telescope Technology	4.2	4.0	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	Miniaturize complexity of large/medium systems
Operations	8.0	7.5	10.4	9.4	10.4	10.4	10.4	Artificial intelligence for onboard autonomy of small spacecraft
Systems Analysis	1.0	0.8	2.0	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	Identify areas for advanced new technologies
USERCA/Advanced Design Program	4.4	2.3	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	Foster next generation engineers/technologists
MSUR Pathfinder	5.8	8.5	6.8	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	Flight micro rover for Mars Pathfinder

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

Mars Pathfinder

The Mars Pathfinder was approved as a new start in FY 1994 as one of the initial missions in the Discovery Program. The Mars Pathfinder mission will demonstrate a unique cruise, entry, descent, and landing system approach that will be available for future missions to Mars. Launch is scheduled for December 1996 on a Delta II expendable launch vehicle. The Mars Pathfinder is being conducted as an in-house effort at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. Portions of the science instruments are being provided by Germany and Denmark.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1996	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	60.8	79.7	33.7							174.2
MICROROVER	8.7	8.5	5.8	2.0						25.0
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				9.6	5.8	2.0				17.4
LAUNCH SUPPORT	9.9	21.1	16.0	1.3						48.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2					0.7
TOTAL	79.4	109.4	55.7	13.1	6.0	2.0				266.8

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

Mars Pathfinder

The Mars Pathfinder was approved as a new start in FY 1994 as one of the initial missions in the Discovery Program. The Mars Pathfinder mission will demonstrate a unique cruise, entry, descent, and landing system approach that will be available for future missions to Mars. Mars Pathfinder was launched in December 1996 on a Delta II expendable launch vehicle. The mission is being conducted as an in-house effort at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. Portions of the science instruments were provided by Germany and Denmark.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	140.5	33.7								174.2
MICROROVER	17.2	5.8	2.0							25.0
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS			9.6	5.8	0.1					15.5
LAUNCH SUPPORT	31.0	16.1	3.2							50.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2						0.7
TOTAL	198.8	55.8	15	6.0	2.0					265.7

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

Mars Pathfinder

The Mars Pathfinder was approved as a new start in FY 1994 as one of the initial missions in the Discovery Program. The Mars Pathfinder mission demonstrated a unique cruise, entry, descent, and landing system approach that will be available for future missions to Mars.

Table with columns: PRIOR, 1997, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, BTC, TOTAL. Rows include DEVELOPMENT, MICROROVER, MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS, LAUNCH SUPPORT, TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT, and TOTAL.

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

Discovery Missions

Discovery missions are planetary exploration missions designed with focused science objectives that can be met with limited resources. Total development costs are not to exceed \$150 million in constant FY 1992 dollars, and development schedules are limited to three years or less.

The budgetary estimates provided below are the amounts included in the specific budget justification for this program within the Space Science section in the Science, Aeronautics and Technology appropriation. Under the specific mission descriptions, see below, other direct program cost elements are included: the development of the spacecraft and experiments, one year of mission operations, the launch services, and unique tracking and data acquisition services.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

Table with columns: PRIOR, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, BTC, TOTAL. Rows include NEAR, LUNAR PROSPECTOR, STARDUST, GENESIS, CONTOUR, FUTURE MISSIONS, and CIVIL SERVICE COSTS ESTIMATE.

Mars Pathfinder excluded with \$2.4 M for "future missions" for 1998 – assumed Mars Pathfinder extended data analysis of primary mission and extended mission.

Mars Pathfinder References

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Mars Polar Lander

Complex table for Mars Polar Lander mission attributes, cost, schedule, and technical scope. Includes sub-tables for Definition, Schedule, Technical Scope, and Cost.

Mars Polar Lander

- Formerly Mars Surveyor '98 Lander – 1/2 of the Mars Surveyor 98 program with combined funding
Same cost structure as Mars Climate Orbiter (split equally between the two missions)
Failure believed to be due to a signal error in the lander legs that caused premature engine shutdown, a derivative of the failed Mars Climate Orbiter, and communication delays.
Follow-on to the Mars Surveyor program (Mars Global Surveyor)
Mission life: 11-month cruise and with a 3-month prime mission (Primary mission: 14/12 years)

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- Programming issues include an investigation team recognizing approximately 30% underfunding for the mission.
- Extension: none
- Status: Failed
 - Operations () –
- Instruments
 - LIDAR (1.0 kg, 0 W)
 - MARDI (0.42 kg, 2 W)
 - MMPE (none listed)
 - MM (0.05, 0.1 W)
 - MVACS (20 kg, unknown W) – 5.85 kg instrument, 6.12 kg robotic arm and camera, 1.79 kg MET package, 3.4 kg Thermal and Evolved Gas Analyzer (TEGA)
- Bus Volume: 11.9 m³ (calculated, hexagon with short diagonal 3.6m x 1.06 m height)
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 2
 - Robotic arm x 1
 - Mast x 1
- Objectives:
 - Record local meteorological conditions near the Martian south pole, including temperature, humidity, pressure, wind, surface frost, ground ice evolution, ice fogs, haze, and suspended dust, (1)
 - Analyze samples of the polar deposits for volatiles, (2)
 - Dig trenches and image the interior to look for seasonal layers and analyze soil samples for water, ice, hydrates, and other aqueously deposited minerals, (3)
 - Image the regional and immediate landing site surroundings for evidence of climate changes and seasonal cycles, (4) and
 - Obtain multi-spectral images of local regolith to determine soil types and composition. (5)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

- MARDI: Mars Descent Imager
- MMP: Mars Magnetic Properties
- MM: Mars Microphone
- MVACS: Mars Volatiles and Climate Surveyor

Not included in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 583 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 64 kg
 - Cruise Stage: 82 kg
 - Aeroshield/heatshield: 140 kg
 - Microprobes: 7.0 kg (3.5 kg each x 2)
 - Lander: 297 kg
- S/A Area: 3.1 m² for the cruise phase
- S/A Area: 2.9 m² for lander
- Power (1 Au): 674 W (calculated for GaAs cells)
- Power (station): 200 W (25 W allocated for payload)
- Science
 - LIDAR: Light Detection and Ranging

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-28)

Mars Surveyor Program
 The Mars Surveyor program is a series of small missions designed to resume the detailed exploration of Mars. The first mission in this program was approved as a new start in FY 1994, the Mars Global Surveyor mission. Future small missions are targeted for launch in the launch windows that occur approximately every two years.

The budgetary estimates below are the amounts indicated in the budget justification within the Space Science/Planetary Exploration section in the Science, Aeronautics and Technology appropriation. The specific write-up for the Mars Global Surveyor includes the amounts for the development of the spacecraft and instruments, two years of mission operations, and launch services. It does not include the NASA civil service workforce salary and expenses, the use of government facilities and general and administrative support used to carry out the program. A more detailed description of the program goals, objectives and activities is provided in the specific budget justification narrative.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)						Balance	TOTAL
	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998		
MARS GLOBAL SURVEYOR	14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4				140.2
FUTURE MISSIONS		1.4	50.3	80.1	98.6	104.2	107.3	Continues

Mars Global Surveyor
 This mission will obtain a majority of the expected science return from the last Mars Observer mission by flying a science payload comprised of spare Mars Observer instruments aboard a small, industry-developed spacecraft. Launch is planned for November 1996 on a Delta II launch vehicle. The funding estimates provided below do not include the previous expenditures of spare Mars Observer instruments or the amount recovered from the prime contractor after the Mars Observer untimely failure.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)						Balance	TOTAL
	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998		
DEVELOPMENT	14.6	58.0	58.2	9.4				140.2
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				16.6	19.8	20.8		57.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT		21.8	20.1	10.4				52.3
TOTAL	14.6	79.8	78.3	36.4	19.8	20.8		248.7

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-28)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander
 The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on a Med-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin Aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer (PMIR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)							Balance	TOTAL
	PRIOR	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000		
DEVELOPMENT	52.3	77.5	40.5	13.3				183.6	
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				10.3	21.3	15.0		46.6	
LAUNCH SUPPORT		11.2	26.0	29.6	16.4			83.2	
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT				0.2	0.4	0.3		0.9	
TOTAL	52.3	108.8	70.1	40.2	21.7	15.3		314.3	

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander
 The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on a Med-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin Aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer (PMIR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)							Balance	TOTAL
	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001		
DEVELOPMENT	52.4	86.9	40.5	13.3				193.1	
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				10.3	21.3	21.9	22.7	76.2	
LAUNCH SUPPORT		7.4	29.8	38.8	7.1			83.1	
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT				0.2	0.4	0.3		0.9	
TOTAL	52.4	116.7	79.3	30.9	21.7	22.2	22.7	353.3	

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-27)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander
 The 98 Mars Orbiter and Lander are the first follow-on missions in the Mars Surveyor program. The Orbiter will be launched on a Med-Lite launcher in December 1998, and the Lander will be launched on a Med-Lite in January 1999. Lockheed Martin Aerospace, Denver, was selected competitively to develop these spacecraft. The Orbiter will carry a color imager and a Pressure Modulator Infrared Radiometer (PMIR), which was also a Mars Observer payload. The Lander will carry a descent imager, a comprehensive volatiles and climate payload, and a Russian LIDAR atmospheric instrument.

	(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)								BTC	TOTAL
	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003		
DEVELOPMENT	52.4	86.3	41.1	13.3						193.1
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				8.3	12.3	10.3	7.5			38.4
LAUNCH SUPPORT		12.5	31.9	38.7	7.2					90.3
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT				0.2	0.4	0.3				0.9
TOTAL	52.4	118.2	79.8	29.0	12.7	10.6	7.5			322.7

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-41)

	MARS SURVEYOR PROGRAM		
	FY 1998	FY 1999	FY 2000
98 Orbiter and Lander.....	79,600	22,000	--
01 Orbiter and Lander	71,200	150,700	126,800
Mars Network	--	--	4,100
Micromissions	--	--	5,000
Future Missions.....	37,100	55,700	114,800
ELV (Non-add)	182,700	148,700	140,800
Total	187,900	228,400	250,700

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-21)

98 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The '98 Mars Orbiter and Lander consisted of the Mars Climate Orbiter (MCO) and the Mars Polar Lander (MPL). MCO was intended to study the planet's weather for one Martian year, acquiring data to help scientists better understand the Martian climate. The MPL was to focus primarily on Mars climate and water. The MPL mission would search for near-surface ice and possible surface records of cyclic climate change, and characterize physical processes key to the seasonal cycles of water, carbon dioxide and dust on Mars. MCO launched in December 1998 and MPL launched in January 1999; however, both missions failed upon arrival at Mars.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	FY 99	FY 00	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	179.8	9.2								189.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	83.0	7.7								90.7
MISSION OPERATIONS		9.4	3.6	8.9	6.4	3.5				31.8
DATA ANALYSIS		0.7	1.6	1.2	0.9					4.4
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		0.2	0.4	0.3						0.9
TOTAL	262.8	27.2	5.6	10.4	7.3	3.5				316.8

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-22)

1998 Mars Orbiter/Lander

The '98 Mars Orbiter and Lander consisted of the Mars Climate Orbiter (MCO) and the Mars Polar Lander (MPL). MCO was intended to study the planet's weather for one Martian year, acquiring data to help scientists better understand the Martian climate. The MPL was to focus primarily on Mars climate and water. The MPL mission would search for near-surface ice and possible surface records of cyclic climate change, and characterize physical processes key to the seasonal cycles of water, carbon dioxide and dust on Mars. MCO launched in December 1998 and MPL launched in January 1999; however, both missions failed upon arrival at Mars.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	189.7									189.7
LAUNCH SUPPORT	90.7									90.7
MISSION OPERATIONS		9.4	5.6							15.0
DATA ANALYSIS										
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		0.2	0.4							0.6
TOTAL	280.0	6.0								286.0

Mars Polar Lander References

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Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter

Mission Attributes		Mars Recon Orbiter	
Last Updated		9/13/2024	
Definition		COSPAS 2005-029A	
Program			
Destination		Mars	
Success		Success	
Type		Orbiter	
Launch Vehicle		Atlas 5	
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)		45.0	
Realized Design Duration (months)		46.0	
Calculated Design Duration (months)		47.0	
Initial Mission Life (years)		5.4	
Realized Mission Life (years)		18.6	
Extended Mission Life (years)		13.3	
Phase A - Award		10/3/2001	
PDR		7/1/2002	
CDR		7/1/2003	
Launch		8/12/2005	
On Station		3/10/2006	
Extend Mission		12/10/2010	
End Mission		3/17/2024	
Cost			
Start		1996	
Launch		1999	
Budget \$		334.4	
Realized \$		450	
Budget Schedule		43	
Realized Schedule		47	
Then \$		\$ 1,072.20	
Development		\$ 419.20	
Launch		\$ 90.00	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 169.50	
Extended		\$ 393.50	
NSII 2023S		\$ 1,531.40	
Development		\$ 681.60	
Launch		\$ 142.10	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 243.80	
Extended		\$ 463.90	
PCEPI 2023S		\$ 1,421.60	
Development		\$ 618.10	
Launch		\$ 129.10	
Operations		-	
Primary		\$ 226.20	
Extended		\$ 448.20	
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass		2180	
Fuel		1149	
S/V Dry		1031	
S/V Bus		892	
S/V Payload		139	
Probe/Rover		-	
Cruise		-	
Lander		-	
Aeroshield +		-	
Bus Volume (m³)		9.68	
Objectives		5	
Deployments		3	
Payload		7	
Instruments		139	
Mass (kg)		189	
Power (W, ave)		S/A	
RTG or S/A		-	
S/A Power		-	
Bol. 1 Au		6000	
Perihelion		3000	
Aphelion		2000	
S/A Area (m²)		20.0	
S/A Type		2 articulated	
Blank		-	

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter

- Mission life: 5.4 years after launch; Dec 31, 2010 – Primary Science Phase (PSP) Nov 2006 to Nov 2008; Extended Science Phase (ESP) & Relay Dec 2008 to Sept 2010 [Primary Mission]
- Extension: (EM1-approved) Oct 2010 to Sept 2012 [Beginning of extended mission, extended through current operations]
- Status: Currently Operational
- Instruments (132 kg, 189 W with reserve)
 - CRISM (33.1 kg, 46.0 W)
 - CTX (3.5 kg, 6.0 W)
 - HIRISE (65.1 kg, 60 W)
 - MARCI (1.0, 3 W)
 - MCS (9 kg, 2 W)
 - SHARAD (16.6 kg, 6 W)
 - ONC (2.9 kg, 16 W – cruise)
- Bus Volume: 2.2 x 2.2 x 2.0 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - HGA
- Objectives: (NASA facts lists 7 objectives)
 - Search for evidence of past or present life, (1)
 - Understand the climate and volatile history of Mars, (2)

- Understand geological processes and their role in shaping the surface and subsurface, (3) and
- Assess the nature and inventory of resources on Mars in preparation for human exploration. (4)
- Communication relay. (+1)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

From Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 2180 kg.
 - Fuel: 1149 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 892 kg
 - Payload: 139 kg
- S/A Area: 20.0 m² (2 x 10 m² each 1000W on Mars)
- Power (1 Au): 6000 W
- Power (station): 2000 W
- Science
 - CRISM: Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer
 - CTX: Context Imager
 - HIRISE: High Resolution Imaging Experiment
 - MARCI: Mars Color Imager
 - MCS: Mars Climate Sounder
 - SHARAD: Shallow Radar
 -
 - ONC: Optical Navigation Camera

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 3-10)

Budget Authority (in millions)	Prior	FY02	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	BTC*	Total	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget (LCC)	12.0	56.0	143.5	183.5	109.1	33.7	37.8	31.1	38.2	245.9	
Pre-Dev										70.0	
Development			143.5	183.5	103.5					430.5	
Operations				4.1	22.6	20.4	16.1			30.6	93.8
Data Analysis				1.4	11.1	17.4	15.0			7.6	52.6
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget	+0.1	+10.1	+5.3	+1.7	+1.1	+31.1	-28.0	322.1			Change Reason:
- Pre-Dev	+10.0									+10.0	
- Dev	-9.9		+10.1	+8.7						+5.8	JPL burden rate
- MO				+0.2	+1.4	+0.6	+16.1	-15.8		+2.6	and full cost
- DA				+0.3	+0.5	+15.0	-12.2			+3.7	changes.
FY 2003 President's Budget (LCC)	12.0	57.9	143.5	173.4	103.1	34.0	38.7		66.2	224.8	
Pre-Dev		12.0	46.0							60.0	
Development		9.9	143.5	173.4	97.8					424.8	
Operations			3.9	21.2	19.8		46.4			91.3	
Data Analysis			1.4	10.9	18.9		19.8			48.9	
Initial Baseline (LCC)	12.0	46.0	147.8	175.4	103.4	32.8	36.7	30.3	36.1	232.4	
Pre-Dev		12.0	56.0							70.0	
Development			147.8	175.4	98.0					421.2	
Operations			4.0	22.0	19.8	15.7				28.5	90.0
Data Analysis			1.4	10.8	16.9	14.6				7.6	51.3

Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
 Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
 FY 2002, FY 2003, Prior and BTC are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 3-8)

BUDGET/LIFE CYCLE COST											
Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	FY09	BTC	Total	Comments
FY2005 PRESBU	70.0	146.9	182.4	109.9	46.4	47.6	38.9	23.9	11.8	677.8	
Development	70.0	146.9	182.4	104.2						503.5	
Operations				4.2	24.1	23.7	17.8	11.6	11.8	93.2	
Data Analysis				1.5	22.3	23.9	21.1	12.3		61.1	
Changes since 2004 PRESBU		+3.4	-1.1	-0.8	+12.7	+9.8	+7.8	+23.9	-26.4	+30.9	JPL burden increased (FY03) and full cost adjustments
Development		+3.4	-1.1	-0.7						+3.0	
Operations				+0.1	+1.5	+3.3	+1.7	+11.6	-18.8	-0.6	MO&DA realignment Increased to reflect grass-root estimate and Independent team recommendation
Data Analysis				+0.1	+11.2	+6.5	+6.1	+12.3		+28.5	
FY2004 PRESBU	70.0	143.5	183.5	109.1	33.7	37.8	31.1		38.2	646.9	
Development	70.0	143.5	183.5	103.5						500.5	
Operations				4.1	22.6	20.4	16.1			30.6	93.8
Data Analysis				1.4	11.1	17.4	15.0			7.6	52.6
Initial Baseline	70.0	147.8	175.4	103.4	32.8	36.7	30.3		36.1	632.5	
Pre-Dev	70.0									70.0	
Development		147.8	175.4	98.0						421.2	
Operations				4.0	22.0	19.8	15.7			28.5	90.0
Data Analysis				1.4	10.8	16.9	14.6			7.6	51.3

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-6)

Budget Detail/Life Cycle Cost (Dollars in Millions)											
Budget Authority	Prior	FY2004	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2006 PRES BUD	216.9	195.3	102.7	45.6	44.0	37.2	22.8	21.6		686.0	
Changes	0.0	12.9	-7.2	-0.9	-3.6	-1.7	-1.0		-11.8	8.3	
FY2005 President's Budget	216.9	182.4	109.9	46.4	47.6	38.9	23.9		11.8	677.8	

Not listed as a line item in NASA Budgets from 2007-2010

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. BUD-1)

Planetary Science	\$1,364.4	\$1,540.7	\$1,429.3	\$1,394.7	\$1,344.2	\$1,256.8
Planetary Science Research	\$161.6	\$192.1	\$205.1	\$218.2	\$216.5	\$221.3
Planetary Science Research and Analysis	\$131.5	\$140.9	\$142.4	\$147.5	\$150.7	\$158.2
Other Missions and Data Analysis	\$21.3	\$25.3	\$27.2	\$33.6	\$30.1	\$26.2
Education and Directorate Management	\$3.0	\$5.4	\$15.0	\$16.6	\$17.0	\$16.8
Near Earth Object Observations	\$5.8	\$20.4	\$20.5	\$20.6	\$20.7	\$21.1
Lunar Quest Program	\$94.5	\$129.6	\$97.7	\$54.8	\$34.3	\$26.2
Lunar Science	\$31.4	\$54.4	\$50.3	\$51.4	\$30.7	\$22.4
Lunar Atmosphere and Dust Environment Explorer	\$48.2	\$71.8	\$44.2	\$0.0	\$0.0	\$0.0
International Lunar Network	\$14.9	\$3.4	\$3.3	\$3.4	\$3.6	\$3.8
Discovery	\$184.5	\$179.1	\$207.2	\$260.4	\$284.7	\$258.3
Gravity Recovery and Interior Laboratory (GRAIL)	\$124.1	\$40.8	\$4.7	\$0.0	\$0.0	\$0.0
Other Missions and Data Analysis	\$80.4	\$138.3	\$202.5	\$350.4	\$394.7	\$258.3
New Frontiers	\$279.6	\$181.8	\$273.2	\$257.2	\$305.9	\$315.7
Juno	\$257.1	\$31.4	\$17.8	\$18.1	\$16.8	\$29.9
Other Missions and Data Analysis	\$22.4	\$150.4	\$255.4	\$239.1	\$289.0	\$265.8
Mars Exploration	\$438.2	\$602.2	\$441.4	\$414.0	\$411.9	\$247.2
2009 Mars Science Lab	\$258.4	\$136.0	\$42.0	\$38.5	\$0.0	\$0.0
MAVEN	\$48.1	\$245.7	\$146.4	\$37.6	\$17.3	\$5.3

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-49)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual Estimate		Notional				
	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	386.8	341.4	214.4	190.1	171.4	261.6	503.1
Mars Research and Analysis	17.4	19.0	15.2	15.2	15.3	15.3	15.3
Mars Technology	2.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	7.0	23.0	75.0
Mars Mission Operations	1.6	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9
Mars Extended Operations	0.0	0.0	53.7	40.1	56.3	51.2	51.4
Mars Next Decade	8.0	4.3	62.0	72.8	72.8	151.7	346.1
Mars Program Management	21.0	27.5	13.5	17.6	18.1	18.5	13.4
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.1	12.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2003 Mars Exploration Rover	13.6	15.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Express	0.9	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter	30.1	40.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2011 Mars Science Laboratory	242.9	174.0	65.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer	6.0	11.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2016 ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter	32.6	27.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-127.0				
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-37.2%				

- NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-43)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 - \$39.9 FY 2012 Actual
- NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-39)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$20.6 FY 2013 Actual
- NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-38)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$29.2 FY 2014 Actual
- NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-48)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$27.9 FY 2015 Actual
- NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-50)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$27.7 FY 2016 Actual
- NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-69)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$28.0 FY 2017 Actual
- NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-69)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$26.3 FY 2018 Actual
- NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-76)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$26.0 FY 2019 Op Plan
- NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-82)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$26.9 FY 2020 Op Plan
- NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-93)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$28.3 FY 2021 Op Plan
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$25.5 FY 2023 Request

- NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-89)
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$24.4 FY 2022 Op Plan
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$ - FY 2023 Enacted
 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$25.6 FY 2024 Request

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO) References

- Krebs, Gunter D. *Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/mro.htm.
- NASA. *Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2005-029A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

- Zurek, R. W., and S. E. Smrekar (2007). *An overview of the Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter (MRO) science mission*. J. Geophys. Res., 112, E05S01, doi:10.1029/2006JE002701.
- Zurek, R.; Graf, J. (2001) *Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter Mission*, <https://hdl.handle.net/2014/36860>, ['IAF Congress', 'Toulouse, France'], JPL Open Repository.

Mars Science Laboratory (Curiosity Rover)

Mission Attributes MSL - Curiosity		
Last Updated		9/13/2024
Definition		
COSPAR	2011-070A	
Program	Flagship	
Destination	Mars	
Success	Operational	
Type	Rover	
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5	
Schedule		
Initial Design Duration (months)	46.0	
Realized Design Duration (months)	71.0	
Calculated Design Duration (months)	72.9	
Initial Mission Life (years)	2.5	
Realized Mission Life (years)	12.3	
Extended Mission Life (years)	9.7	
Phase A - Award	12/1/2005	
PDR	6/20/2006	
CDR	6/1/2007	
Launch	11/26/2011	
On Station	7/6/2012	
Extend Mission	7/10/2014	
End Mission	3/17/2024	
Technical Scope		
Launch Mass	3839	
Fuel	539	
S/V Dry	3300	
S/V Bus	3032	
S/V Payload	899	
Probe/Rover		
Cruise	536	
Lander	2016	
Aeroshield +	480	
Bus Volume (m ³)	17.82	
Objectives	8	
Deployments	7	
Cost		
Start	2002	
Launch	2011	
Budget \$	1068.5	
Realized \$	2337.1	
Budget Schedule	45	
Realized Schedule	70	
Then \$	\$ 3,046.00	
Development	\$	2,142.40
Launch	\$	194.70
Operations	-	
Primary	\$	176.90
Extended	\$	532.00
NSII 2023\$	\$ 4,197.70	
Development	\$	3,068.50
Launch	\$	255.70
Operations	-	
Primary	\$	266.70
Extended	\$	606.80
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 3,902.80	
Development	\$	2,853.80
Launch	\$	244.10
Operations	-	
Primary	\$	215.10
Extended	\$	589.80
Payload		
Instruments	10	
Mass (kg)	899	
Power (W, ave)	125	
RTG or S/A	RTG	
S/A Power	-	
BoL 1 Au	125	
Perihelion	125	
Aphelion	-	
S/A Area (m ²)	-	
S/A Type	-	
Blank	-	

Mars Science Laboratory (Curiosity Rover)

- Mars Science Laboratory Press Kit, p. 34, provides a comparison of two landers: Curiosity vs. Spirit and Opportunity
- Funded formulation started in Jun 2003, studied until approved in December 2005 (I assume 2005 budget authorization)
- No baseline cost until NASA 2008 Budget Request \$1686.0 with \$1068.5 design, development, test through launch
- Mission life: 1 Mars Year (687 days) with initial 10/2009, delayed for 11/2011 launch (RTG delays from DoE)
- Launch Nov 2011 and landing on Mars July 2012 (8 months): prime mission (Primary mission: 7 ½ months + 687 days)
- Extension: Mission extended July 10, 2014
- Status: Operational (successful)
- Instruments
 - MastCam (4.0 kg, 17.4 W)

This material is the property of Colorado State University

- MAHLI (12.5 kg, 30 W)
- MARDI (0.64 kg, 3.5 W) – added 0.08 for targets.
- APXS (kg, W)
- ChemCam (10.79 kg, W)
- CheMin (10 kg, W)
- SAM (40 kg, 45 W)
- RAD (kg, W)
- DAN (2.6 kg, 13 W)
- REMS (1.243 kg, 10 W)
- Bus Volume: (rover) 3.0 x 2.7 x 2.2 m³ (note: same size as Perseverance Rover)
- Deployments: 7
 - Cruise Stage x1
 - Aeroshell x1
 - Parachute x 1
 - Lander x1
 - Rover x1
 - Rover arm/mast x2
- Objectives:
 - Determine the nature and inventory of organic carbon compounds, (1)
 - Inventory the chemical building blocks of life, (2)
 - Identify features that may represent the effects of biological processes, (3)
 - Investigate the chemical, isotopic, and mineralogical composition of the Martian surface and near-surface geological materials, (4)
 - Interpret the processes that have formed and modified rocks and soils, (5)
 - Assess long-term atmospheric evolution processes, (6)
 - Determine the present state, distribution, and cycling of water and carbon dioxide, (7) and
 - Characterize the broad spectrum of surface radiation, including cosmic, galactic radiation, solar proton events, and secondary neutrons. (8)
- Manufacturer: JPL + industry

- Ballast: 150 kg (6 x 25 kg)
- Rover: 899 kg (900 kg)
 - Buggy 775 kg
 - Payload: 75 kg
- Heat Shield: 78 kg (480 kg) {the 78 kg reported is assumed inaccurate and updated to – 478 kg}
- Power: RTG
- Power (1 Au): 125 W
- Power (station): 125 W ave
- Science
 - MastCam: Mast Camera
 - MAHLI: Mars Hand Lens Imager
 - MARDI: Mars Descent Imager
 - APXS: Alpha Particle X-Ray Spectrometer
 - ChemCam: Chemistry & Camera
 - CheMin: Chemistry & Mineralogy X-Ray Diffraction/X-Ray Fluorescence Instrument
 - SAM: Sample Analysis at Mars Instrument Suite with Gas Chromatograph, Mass Spectrometer, and Tunable Laser Spectrometer
 - RAD: Radiation Assessment Detector
 - DAN: Dynamic of Albedo Neutrons
 - REMS: Rover Environmental Monitoring Station

Not listed in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Lander mission
- Launch mass: 3839 kg (4050 kg – source at end of section)
 - Ballast (Adapter, unaccounted mass): 118 kg
 - Cruise Stage: 536 kg
 - Cruise Fuel: 539 kg (440 kg)
 - Backshell (Aeroshell): 480 kg (525 kg) (946 kg)
 - Parachute System: kg.
 - Ballast: 150 kg (2 x 75 kg)
 - Descent Stage: 544 kg (730 kg dry, 340 kg fuel)
 - Descent Fuel: 219 kg

Independent Audit of Program: IG-11-019

Table 2. MSL Project Cost Summary (millions)

Phase	Initial Cost Estimate per 2006 Project Plan	Proposed FY 2012 Budget	Funds Expended as of December 2010
Formulation (Phases A and B)	\$ 515.1	\$ 515.5	\$ 515.5
Development (Phases C and D)	968.6	1,802.0	1,609.9
Operation (Phase E)	158.5	158.8	
Life-Cycle Cost	\$1,642.2	\$2,476.3	\$2,125.4

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. ESA 3-20)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (in millions)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget	65.9	177.5	275.4	
2007 Scout Mission	0.2	7.1	20.1	
2007 CNES Orbiter	4.0	19.4	14.1	
2007 ASI/GMO		3.2		
2009 ASI/SAR				
2009 MSL	5.7	21.6	119.0	
2009 US Telesat			9.3	
Mars Technology	26.5	50.0	36.3	
Program CoF (JPL Flight Project Bldg)		16.5		
JPL Discrete CoF			15.6	
Mars Program Plan & Architecture	29.5	59.7	53.0	
Next Planaria Mission				To be addressed in FY 04 budget

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 3-9)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRES BUD	142.9	304.7	515.6	
Optical Comm		31.0	55.8	
2007 Scout Mission	8.8	28.9	102.8	
2009 MSL	60.6	117.3	174.6	
2009 US Telesat	4.2	9.2	25.1	
Mars Technology	28.7	36.1	20.2	
JPL Discrete CoF	1.4	15.5	11.5	
Mars Program Plans & Architecture and Other	39.1	66.7	125.6	Supports new exploration vision
Changes since 2004 PRES BUD		-34.6	+29.3	
Optical Comm			+31.0	Transferred from SSE Theme
2007 Scout Mission		+1.7	-0.2	Deleted Mission of Opportunity (MoO)
2009 MSL		+39.0	-0.7	Increased MMRTG budget consistent with contract award
2009 US Telesat		+4.2	-0.1	Rephased funding profile
Mars Technology		-21.3	-0.2	
JPL Discrete CoF		-15.1	-0.1	Deferred Flt Project Building to 2005
Mars Program Plans & Architecture and Other		+39.1	+66.7	
2007 CNES Orbiter		-19.4	-14.1	
FY2004 PRES BUD	177.5	275.4		
2007 CNES Orbiter	19.4	14.1		
2007 Scout Mission	7.1	29.1		
2009 MSL	21.6	118.0		
2009 US Telesat		9.3		
Mars Technology	50.0	36.3		
JPL Discrete CoF	16.5	15.6		
2007 Scout Mission	62.9	52.9		

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. Appendix SAE 2-9)

President's FY 2006 Budget Request (Dollars in Millions)

	FY2004	FY2005	FY2006
2009 Mars Science Laboratory			
FY 2006 PRES BUD	111.7	162.3	183.9
Changes from FY 2005 Request	-5.8	-12.3	

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p. SAE SMD 2-38)

President's FY 2007 Budget Request (Dollars in Millions)

	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	FY2011
2009 Mars Science Lab (Formulation)							
FY 2007 PRES BUD	117.5	253.4	347.9	285.6	231.0	50.4	41.2
Changes from FY 2006 Request	-44.8	69.5	18.6	-7.2	62.3	9.8	

NASA 2008 Budget Request (p. SMD-151)

Budget / Life Cycle Cost

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY06	FY07	FY08	FY09	FY10	FY11	FY12	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	289.1	253.4	378.4	345.0	238.2	73.6	58.2	40.1	--	1,686.0
Formulation	290.1	216.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Development	--	37.4	378.4	345.0	234.9	5.8	--	--	--	--
Operations	--	--	--	--	3.3	67.8	58.2	40.1	--	--
Other	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
FY 2007 President's Budget Request	284.7	253.4	347.9	285.6	231.0	50.4	41.2	--	--	1,504.1
Formulation	294.7	216.0	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Development	--	37.4	347.9	285.6	231.0	--	--	--	--	--
Operations	--	--	--	--	--	50.4	41.2	--	--	--
Other	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Changes	4.4	--	30.5	59.4	7.2	23.2	17.1	40.1	--	181.9
Formulation	4.4	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	4.4
Development	--	--	30.5	59.4	3.9	5.8	--	--	--	99.6
Operations	--	--	--	--	--	3.3	17.4	40.1	--	77.8
Other	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

NASA 2009 Budget Request (p. Sci-153)

FY 2009 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2007 Actual	FY 2008 Enacted	FY 2009	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	553.0	416.8	305.5	223.3	69.0	54.6	37.6	--	--	1,658.8
Formulation	515.6	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	515.6
Development / Implementation	37.4	416.8	305.5	220.0	5.4	--	--	--	--	985.1
Operations / Close-out	--	--	--	3.3	63.6	54.6	37.6	--	--	159.1
Other	--	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	--	0.0
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	552.4	378.4	345.0	238.2	73.6	58.2	40.1	--	--	1,686.0
Formulation	515.1	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	515.1
Development / Implementation	37.3	342.6	311.0	211.1	5.4	--	--	--	--	907.4
Operations / Close-out	--	--	--	3.0	63.5	54.5	37.5	--	--	158.5
Other	0.0	35.8	34.0	24.1	4.7	3.7	2.6	--	--	105.0
Changes from FY 2008 Request	0.6	38.4	-39.5	-14.9	-4.6	-3.7	-2.5	--	--	-26.2
Formulation	0.5	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	0.5
Development / Implementation	0.1	74.2	-5.5	8.9	--	--	--	--	--	77.7
Operations / Close-out	--	--	--	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	--	--	0.6
Other	0.0	-35.8	-34.0	-24.1	-4.7	-3.8	-2.6	--	--	-105.0

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. SCI-136)

FY 2010 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2008 Actual	FY 2009 Enacted	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	970.1	545.0	223.3	204.0	194.6	67.3	65.0	30.0	0.0	2,239.3
Formulation	515.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	515.5
Development / Implementation	454.6	545.0	223.3	204.0	194.6	3.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,625.0
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	63.8	65.0	30.0	0.0	158.8
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
FY 2009 President's Budget Request	969.8	305.5	223.3	69.0	54.6	37.6	0.0	--	0.0	1,659.8
Formulation	515.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	515.6
Development / Implementation	454.2	305.5	220.0	5.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	985.1
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	3.3	63.6	54.6	37.6	0.0	--	0.0	159.1
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	0.0
Changes from FY 2009 Request	0.3	239.4	0.0	135.0	140.0	29.7	65.0	--	0.0	639.4
Formulation	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	-0.1
Development / Implementation	0.4	239.5	3.3	198.6	194.6	3.5	0.0	--	0.0	639.9
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	-3.3	-63.6	-54.6	26.2	65.0	--	0.0	-0.3
Other	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	-0.1

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET - 54)

FY 2011 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2009 Actual	FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	1,515.1	229.3	204.0	231.5	91.8	42.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	2,352.3
Formulation	515.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	515.5
Development / Implementation	999.6	229.3	204.0	231.5	13.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1,678.0
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	78.3	42.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	158.8
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	1,515.1	223.3	204.0	194.6	67.3	65.0	30.0	--	0.0	2,289.3
Formulation	515.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	515.5
Development / Implementation	999.6	223.3	204.0	194.6	3.5	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	1,625.0
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	63.8	65.0	30.0	--	0.0	158.8
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	0.0
Changes from FY 2010 Request	0.0	6.0	0.0	37.0	24.5	-23.0	8.5	--	0.0	53.0
Formulation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	--
Development / Implementation	0.0	6.0	0.0	37.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	53.0
Operations / Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.5	-23.0	8.5	--	0.0	--
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	--	0.0	0.0

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. MP-76)

2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2010	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	1744.4	258.4	-	136.43	40.5	37.0	0.0	0.0	-	-
FY 2011 Costs			254.9							
CSLE				1.5	1.5	1.5				
Administrative Labor Adjustments		0.1								
2011 MPAR Project Cost Estimate	1744.4	258.5	254.9	138.6	42.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	2476.3
Formulation	515.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	515.5
Development	1228.9	258.5	254.9	59.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1802.0
Operations	0.0	0.0	0.0	78.3	42.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	158.8

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-49)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Estimate		Notional			
	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	386.8	341.4	214.4	190.1	171.4	261.6	503.1	
Mars Research and Analysis	17.4	19.0	15.2	15.2	15.3	15.3	15.3	
Mars Technology	2.5	5.0	3.0	4.0	7.0	23.0	75.0	
Mars Mission Operations	1.6	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	
Mars Extended Operations	0.0	0.0	53.7	40.1	56.3	51.2	51.4	
Mars Next Decade	8.0	4.3	62.0	72.8	72.8	151.7	346.1	
Mars Program Management	21.0	27.5	13.5	17.6	18.1	18.5	13.4	
2001 Mars Odyssey	10.1	12.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2003 Mars Exploration Rover	13.6	15.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Mars Express	0.9	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2005 Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter	30.1	40.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2011 Mars Science Laboratory	242.9	174.0	65.0	38.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Mars Organic Molecule Analyzer	6.0	11.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
2016 ExoMars Trace Gas Orbiter	32.6	27.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-137.0					
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	-37.2%					

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-43)

2011 Mars Science Lab - \$174.0 FY 2012 Actual

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-39)

2011 Mars Science Lab - \$63.8 FY 2013 Actual

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-38)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$69.6 FY 2014 Actual

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-48)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$63.5 FY 2015 Actual

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-50)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$50.3 FY 2016 Actual

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$56.2 FY 2017 Actual

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$51.4 FY 2018 Actual

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-76)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$51.1 FY 2019 Op Plan

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-82)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$47.0 FY 2020 Op Plan

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-93)

2011 Mars Science Lab - \$48.9 FY 2021 Op Plan

2011 Mars Science Lab - \$45.0 FY 2023 Request

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$25.5 FY 2023 Request

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-89)

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$43.3 FY 2022 Op Plan

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$ - FY 2023 Enacted

Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter 2005 (MRO) - \$40.5 FY 2024 Request

Mass of Major Spacecraft Systems: 27th Space Simulation Conference, November 2012

Mars Science Laboratory (MSL, Curiosity) References

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Martin, Paul K. (2011). *NASA's Management of the Mars Science Laboratory Project*. Office of the Inspector General – Audit Report. Jun 8, 2011. Report No. IG-11-019 (Assignment Number A-10-007-00). <https://oig.nasa.gov/docs/IG-11-019.pdf>, downloaded 3/6/2024.

Fields, Keith, 2012, *Mass Property Measurements of the Mars Science Laboratory Rover*, <https://hdl.handle.net/2014/42953>, 27th Space Simulation Conference, Annapolis, Maryland, November 5-8, 2012, JPL Open Repository.

Maven

Mission Attributes MAVEN	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2013-063A
Program	Scout 2
Destination	Mars
Success	Operational
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	62.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	62.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	63.0
Initial Mission Life (years)	9.0
Realized Mission Life (years)	10.3
Extended Mission Life (years)	4.2
Phase A - Award	9/15/2008
PDR	7/1/2010
CDR	7/15/2011
Launch	11/18/2013
On Station	9/22/2014
Extend Mission	1/1/2020
End Mission	3/17/2024
Cost	
Start	2007
Launch	2013
Budget \$	567.2
Realized \$	551.1
Budget Schedule	62
Realized Schedule	
Then \$	\$ 771.20
Development	\$ 382.40
Launch	\$ 168.70
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 26.40
Extended	\$ 193.70
NSII 2023\$	\$ 942.50
Development	\$ 499.50
Launch	\$ 218.10
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 33.00
Extended	\$ 191.90
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 901.20
Development	\$ 475.60
Launch	\$ 207.30
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 31.50
Extended	\$ 186.80
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	2454
Fuel	1645
S/V Dry	809
S/V Bus	737.5
S/V Payload	71.5
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	10.58
Objectives	5
Deployments	3
Payload	
Instruments	8
Mass (kg)	71.5
Power (W, ave)	90
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	3400
Perihelion	1700
Aphelion	1135
S/A Area (m ²)	12.0
S/A Type	2 fixed
Blank	-

- Determine the current state of the upper atmosphere, ionosphere, and interactions with the solar wind, (2)
- Determine the current rates of escape of neutral gases and ions to space, the process controlling them, (3), and
- Determine the ratios of stable isotopes that will tell Mars' history of loss through time, (4)
- Communication relay. (+1)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not listed in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 2454 kg.
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 33 kg
 - Fuel: 1645 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 809 kg
 - Payload: 65 kg
 - Comm Relay: 6.5 kg (included as payload – communication box for surface uplink)
- S/A Area: 20.0 m²
- Power (1 Au): 1500 W
- Power (station): 1700 W (perihelion)
- Power (station): 1135 W (aphelion)
- Science
 - IUVS: Imaging Ultraviolet Spectrograph
 - LPW: Langmuir Probe and Waves
 - MAG: Magnetometer
 - NGIMS: Neutral Gas Ion Mass Spectrometer
 - ROSE: Radio Occultation Science Experiment
 - SEP: Solar Energetic Particle
 - SWEA: Solar Wind Electron Analyzer
 - SWIA: Solar Wind Ion Analyzer
 - SATIC: SupraThermal and Thermal Ion Composition

Maven

- Second Scout class mission
- Mission life: 11/2013 launch, 10/2015 End of Prime Mission
- Extension: currently on the 5th extended mission
- Status: Currently Operational
- Instruments
 - IUVS (22.1 kg, W)
 - LPW (4.98 kg, 2.7 W)
 - MAG (0.39 kg, W)
 - NGIMS (14.0 kg, W)
 - ROSE (kg, W)
 - SEP (1.48 kg, W)
 - SWEA (1.4 kg, W)
 - SWIA (2.62 kg, 1.75 W)
 - STATIC (3.3 kg, 4.62 W) – 165 mA max (assumed 28 Vdc)
- Bus Volume: 2.3 x 2.3 x 2.0 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Science Platform x 1
- Objectives:
 - Determine the role that loss of volatiles from the Mars atmosphere to space has played through time, (1)

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. ii)

MAVEN (Mars Exploration) FY 2008 Actuals - \$1.0M

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET – 60)

FY 2011 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2009 Actual	FY 2010 Enacted	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015
FY 2011 President's Budget Request	6.7	53.4	161.2	210.9	170.5	25.8	18.4
FY 2010 President's Budget Request	6.7	53.4	168.7	182.6	138.4	30.6	-
Total Change from 2010 President's Budget Request	0.0	0.0	-7.5	28.3	32.2	-4.8	-

Note: Rephased project reserve profile, and added funds for a higher than anticipated launch vehicle cost.

NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. PS-63)

FY 2012 Budget Request

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY 2010	Ann CR. FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016
FY 2012 President's Budget Request	9.9	48.1	-	240.3	140.6	34.9	15.4	4.7

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-42)

FY 2013 BUDGET

Budget Authority (in \$ million)	Actual		Estimate						LCC	
	Prior	FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	BTC	Total
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	58.4	160.6	245.7	146.4	37.6	17.3	5.3	0.0	0.0	671.2
2012 MPAR Project Cost Estimate	58.4	160.6	245.7	146.4	37.6	17.3	5.3	0.0	0.0	671.2
Formulation	58.4	5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	63.9
Development	0.0	155.0	245.7	146.4	20.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	567.2
Implementation	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	17.5	17.3	5.3	0.0	0.0	40.1
Operations/Close-out										
Change From FY 2012 Estimate		--	--	-99.3						
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate		--	--	-40.4%						

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-37)

FY 2014 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual			Notional					BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018		
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	218.9	245.7	127.4	50.1	20.2	6.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	668.8
2014 MPAR LCC Estimate	218.9	245.7	127.4	50.1	20.2	6.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	668.8
Formulation	63.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	63.9
Development/Implementation	155.0	245.7	127.4	22.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	550.5
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.8	20.2	6.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	54.5
Change from FY 2012		--	--	-195.6						
Percentage change from FY 2012		--	--	-79.6%						

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-39)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$86.5 FY 2013 Actual

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-38)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$14.9 FY 2014 Actual

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-48)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$13.8 FY 2015 Actual

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-50)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$12.3 FY 2016 Actual

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-69)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$20.5 FY 2017 Actual

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-9)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$22.2 FY 2018 Actual

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-76)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$17.9 FY 2019 Actual

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-82)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$20.5 FY 2022 Actual

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-93)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$21.0 FY 2021 Actual

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$86.5 FY 2023 Request

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-89)

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$22.0 FY 2022 Actual

Mars Atmosphere & Volatile EvolutionN - \$23.0 FY 2024 Request

Maven References

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Messenger

Mission Attributes Messenger	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	2004-030A
COSPAR	2004-030A
Program	Discovery 7
Destination	Mercury
Success	Success
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	51.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	57.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	55.9
Initial Mission Life (years)	8.0
Realized Mission Life (years)	10.7
Extended Mission Life (years)	3.2
Phase A - Award	1/1/2000
PDR	5/24/2001
CDR	3/22/2002
Launch	8/3/2004
On Station	3/18/2011
Extend Mission	3/1/2012
End Mission	4/30/2015
Cost	
Start	1999
Launch	2004
Budget \$	326.2
Realized \$	390
Budget Schedule	46
Realized Schedule	57
Then \$	\$ 457.80
Development	\$ 216.20
Launch	\$ 69.00
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 104.80
Extended	\$ 67.80
NSII 2023\$	\$ 710.30
Development	\$ 363.30
Launch	\$ 115.20
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 145.70
Extended	\$ 86.10
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 649.60
Development	\$ 326.40
Launch	\$ 104.20
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 137.00
Extended	\$ 82.00
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	1108
Fuel	607.8
S/V Dry	485.2
S/V Bus	442.8
S/V Payload	42.4
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m³)	3.28
Objectives	6
Deployments	3
Payload	
Instruments	7
Mass (kg)	42.4
Power (W, ave)	67.5
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	370
Perihelion	450
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m2)	5.0
S/A Type	2 articulated
Blank	-

Messenger

- 7th Discovery Mission
- Mission life: initial launch Mar 2004; 5-year cruise with two flybys of Venus and two flybys of Mercury; enter Mercury orbit Apr 2009, orbit for one Earth year science (6-year primary mission – 72 months)
- Extension: Extended twice, the last plan was to extend until December 2014, with fuel depletion
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - MDIS (7.9 kg, 10.0 W)
 - GRNS (13.1 kg, 23.6 W)
 - XRS (3.4 kg, 11.4 W)
 - MAG (4.4 kg, 4.2 W) – includes boom.
 - MLA (7.4 kg, 38.6 W)
 - MASCS (3.1 kg, 8.2 W)
 - EPPS (3.1 kg, 7.8 W)
 - DPU (5.0 kg, 18.0 W) – not instrument, data processing unit, required support for payload – typical instrument growth was 50% - 100% mass, 30% - 60% power from source #1 to source #2 (pk)
 - Instruments (3.25 kg, 0 W) – not instruments, harness, brackets, and attachments for payload accommodation
 - RS (not listed in payload accommodation)
- Bus Volume: 2.2 x 1.7 x 2.6 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Instrument boom x 1
- Objectives: (Budget 2004)
 - Determine the chemical composition of Mercury’s surface, (1)
 - Mercury’s geological history, (2)
 - The nature of Mercury’s magnetic field, (3)
 - The size and state of Mercury’s core, (4)
 - Record the radiation environment in low Mars orbit, (5)
 - The nature of Mercury’s exosphere and magnetosphere. (6)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 1108 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 33 kg
 - Fuel: 607.8 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 485.2 kg
 - Payload: 42.4 kg
- S/A Area: 5.0 m² (reflector array)
- Power (1 Au): 370 W
- Power (station): 450 W
- Science
 - MDIS: Mercury Dual Imaging System

- GRNS: Gamma-Ray and Neutron Spectrometer
- XRS: X-ray Spectrometer
- MAG: Magnetometer
- MLA: Mercury Laser Altimeter
- MASCS: Mercury Atmospheric and Surface Composition Spectrometer
- EPPS: Energetic Particle and Plasma Spectrometer
- RS: Radio Science (not included as not specifically manifest, but listed in science)

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B DEVELOPMENT	1.7	9.6	20.3							31.6
MISSION OPS			31.7	97.4	64.7	31.0	2.9	4.2	4.2	23.5
DATA ANALYSIS							1.3	2.8	2.7	28.2
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT							TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
TOTAL	1.7	9.6	52.0	97.4	64.7	35.2	7.0	6.9	51.7	326.2

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p. SAT 1-48)

MESSENGER Life Cycle Cost Data:

	Prior	FY 01	FY 02	FY 03	FY 04	FY 05	FY 06	FY 07	BTC	Total
Pre-Development	11.1	51.8	94.3	68.0	39.1	7.1	7.5	8.7	42.2	330.0
Development		25.9	72.8	46.0	19.1					163.8
Launch Services	0.2	5.6	21.5	22.0	15.6				19.5	64.9
Operations					2.9	4.1	4.2	4.2	22.7	34.9
Data Analysis					1.5	3.0	3.3	4.5		35.0

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-8)

Total budget authority represents the Life Cycle Cost (LCC).

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	Prior	FY02	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget	63.1	97.4	88.0	42.5	7.4	7.8	9.0	11.1	31.4	337.7	
Development	63.1	97.4	88.0							266.5	
Operations				3.0	4.3	4.4	4.4	5.5	14.2	35.9	
Data Analysis				1.5	3.1	3.4	4.6	5.6	17.2	35.3	
Changes since FY 03 PBS:	0.0	+3.1	+0.0	+3.4	+0.3	+0.3	+0.3	+1.1	+0.0	+18.5	Reason for Change:
Development		+3.1								+6.4	02 growth/full cost
Operations			+3.3		+0.1	+0.2	+0.2	+0.5		+6.3	Full cost
Data Analysis					+0.1	+0.1	+0.1	+5.6		+5.8	Full cost
FY 2003 President's Budget	63.1	94.3	88.0	39.1	7.1	7.5	8.7	0.0	42.2	330.0	
Development	63.1	94.3	88.0	34.7						260.1	
Operations				2.9	4.1	4.2	4.2		19.5	34.9	
Data Analysis				1.5	3.0	3.3	4.5		22.7	35.0	
Initial Baseline LCC	63.1	94.3	88.0	39.1	7.1	7.5	8.7	0.0	42.2	330.0	FY 2003 Pres. Budget
Development	63.1	94.3	88.0	34.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	260.1	
Operations				2.9	4.1	4.2	4.2	0.0	19.5	34.9	
Data Analysis				1.5	3.0	3.3	4.5	0.0	22.7	35.0	

Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit. FY 2002, FY 2003, Prior and BTC are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 2.7)

BUDGET/LIFE CYCLE COST

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	FY09	BTC	Total	Comments
FY2005 PRESBUD	160.4	86.7	42.3	7.7	8.2	9.4	11.5	16.3	15.8	358.3	--
Development	160.4	86.7	37.8							284.9	--
Operations			3.0							3.0	--
Mission Operations & Data Analysis			1.5	7.7	8.2	9.4	11.5	16.3	15.8	70.4	--
Changes since 2004 PRESBUD	-0.1	+18.7	-0.2	+0.3	+0.5	+0.4	+0.4	+16.3	-15.6	+20.6	--
Development	-0.1	+18.7	-0.2							+18.4	--
Operations				-4.3	-4.4	-4.4	-5.5			-14.2	-32.9 --
Mission Operations & Data Analysis			+1.5	+7.7	+8.2	+9.4	+11.5	+16.3	+15.8	+70.4	MO&DA combined
Data Analysis			-1.5	-3.1	-3.4	-4.6	-5.6			-17.2	-35.3 --
FY2004 PRESBUD	160.5	88.0	42.5	7.4	7.7	9.0	11.1			314	337.7 --
Development	160.5	88.0	38.0							266.5	--
Operations			3.0	4.3	4.4	4.4	5.5			14.2	35.9 --
Data Analysis			1.5	3.1	3.4	4.6	5.6			17.2	35.3 --
Initial Baseline	157.4	88.0	39.1	7.1	7.5	8.7				42.2	330.0 --
Development	157.4	88.0	34.7							260.1	--
Operations			2.9	4.1	4.2	4.2				19.5	34.9 --
Data Analysis			1.5	3.0	3.3	4.5				22.7	35.0 --

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

No details provided from NASA 2006 Budget Request to NASA 2012 Budget Request – included under “Other Missions and Data Analysis” – Discovery Programs, 2010 (p. SCI-105) as an example.

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-23)
MESSENGER - \$22.7 FY 2011 Actual

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-23)
MESSENGER - \$34.9 FY 2012 Actual

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-20)
MESSENGER - \$16.6 FY 2013 Actual

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-19)
MESSENGER - \$12.2 FY 2014 Actual

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-22)
MESSENGER - \$6.0 FY 2015 Actual

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-30)
MESSENGER - \$6.8 FY 2016 Actual

Messenger References

Krebs, Gunter D. *MESSENGER (Discovery 8)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/messenger.htm .

NASA. *MESSENGER*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2004-030A> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

NASA. (2014) *Messenger – NASA’s Mission to Mercury – Launch Press Kit*. Aug 2004. https://web.archive.org/web/20070824103010/http://www.nasa.gov/pdf/168019main_MESENGER_71504_PressKit.pdf , downloaded Mar 6, 2024.

Solomon, S.C., McNutt, R.L., Gold, R.E. et al. (2007) *MESSENGER Mission Overview*. Space Sci Rev 131, 3–39 Oct 5, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-007-9247-6> , downloaded Mar 6, 2024.

Ralph L. McNutt, Sean C. Solomon, Robert E. Gold, James C. Leary. (2006) *The MESSENGER mission to Mercury: Development history and early mission status*. Advances in Space Research, Volume 38, Issue 4, 2006, Pages 564-571, ISSN 0273-1177, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2005.05.044> , downloaded Mar 6, 2024.

Santo, Andrew G, et al. *The MESSENGER mission to Mercury: spacecraft and mission design*. Planetary and Space Science, Volume 49, Issues 14–15, 2001, Pages 1481-1500, ISSN 0032-0633, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-0633\(01\)00087-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-0633(01)00087-3), downloaded Apr 19, 2024.

Solomon, Sean C, et al. *The MESSENGER mission to Mercury: scientific objectives and implementation*. Planetary and Space Science, Volume 49, Issues 14–15, 2001, Pages 1445-1465, ISSN

0032-0633, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-0633\(01\)00085-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-0633(01)00085-X), downloaded Apr 19, 2024.

NEAR

Mission Attributes		Near	
Last Updated		9/17/2024	
Definition			
COSPAR	2011-070A		
Program	Flagship		
Destination	Mars		
Success	Operational		
Type	Rover		
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5		
Schedule			
Initial Design Duration (months)	46.0		
Realized Design Duration (months)	71.0		
Calculated Design Duration (months)	72.9		
Initial Mission Life (years)	2.5		
Realized Mission Life (years)	12.3		
Extended Mission Life (years)	9.7		
Phase A - Award	12/1/2005		
PDR	6/20/2006		
CDR	6/1/2007		
Launch	11/26/2011		
On Station	7/6/2012		
Extend Mission	7/10/2014		
End Mission	3/17/2024		
Cost			
Start	2002		
Launch	2011		
Budget \$	1068.5		
Realized \$	2337.1		
Budget Schedule	45		
Realized Schedule	70		
Then \$	\$ 3,046.00		
Development	\$ 2,142.40		
Launch	\$ 194.70		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 176.90		
Extended	\$ 532.00		
NSII 2023\$	\$ 4,197.70		
Development	\$ 3,068.50		
Launch	\$ 255.70		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 266.70		
Extended	\$ 606.80		
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 3,902.80		
Development	\$ 2,853.80		
Launch	\$ 244.10		
Operations	-		
Primary	\$ 215.10		
Extended	\$ 589.80		
Technical Scope			
Launch Mass	3839	Payload	
Fuel	539	Instruments	10
S/V Dry	3300	Mass (kg)	899
S/V Bus	3032	Power (W, ave)	125
S/V Payload	899	RTG or S/A	RTG
Probe/Rover	-	S/A Power	-
Cruise	536	BoL 1 Au	125
Lander	2016	Perihelion	125
Aeroshield +	480	Aphelion	-
Bus Volume (m³)	17.82	S/A Area (m²)	-
Objectives	8	S/A Type	-
Deployments	7	Blank	-

NEAR

- The initial Discovery mission program was approved as a fresh start in 1994.
- Target altered to asteroid 433 Eros in February 2000. Initially scheduled for rendezvous in 1999, the rendezvous was delayed due to a premature cut-off during the first orbit insertion engine firing in December 1998, as well as a corrected error.
- Mission life: 4-year cruise and 1-year prime orbit mission (Primary mission: 5 years)
- Extension: Extended 14 days to “touch-down” on the surface of the asteroid
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - NLR (5.0 kg, 16.5 W)
 - MAG (1.5kg, 1.5 W)
 - MSI (7.7 kg, 13.9 W)
 - NIS (15.15 kg, 15.1 W)
 - RS (- kg, - W)
 - XRS-GRS (26.9 kg, 24 W)
- Bus Volume: 1.2 x 1.2 x 1.7 m³ (inscribed octagon)
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 4 (fixed)
- Objectives:

- Determine bulk properties (size, shape, volume, mass, gravity field, and spin rate), (1)
- Evaluate surface properties (elemental and mineral composition, geology, morphology, and texture), (2) and
- Determine internal properties (mass distribution and magnetic field) (3)
- Manufacturer: Johns Hopkins University – Applied Physics Laboratory (JHU-APL)

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 818 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): 33 kg
 - Fuel: 318 kg (209 kg hydrazine, 109 kg NTO)
 - Space Vehicle: 487 kg
 - Payload: 56.25 kg
 - Bus: 430 kg
- S/A Area: 8.64 m²
- Power (1 Au): 1800 W
- Power (station): 400 W (2.2 AU)
- Science
 - NLR: NEAR Laser Rangefinder
 - MAG: Magnetometer
 - MSI: Multispectral Imager
 - NIS: Near-Infrared Spectrometer
 - RS: Radio Science and Gravimetry
 - XRS-GRS: X-Ray/Gamma-ray Spectrometer

NASA 1996 Budget Request (p. SI-20)

	PRIOR	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT		66.6	52.2	31.3						150.1
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS					3.3	5.4	6.8	22.3	7.8	47.6
LAUNCH SUPPORT		24.6	15.9	11.2						51.7
TOTAL		91.2	68.1	45.8	5.4	8.8	22.3	7.8		249.4

NASA 1997 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

	PRIOR	1996	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	66.6	50.0	8.3							124.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS			4.9	8.5	9.5	14.8	8.6			46.3
LAUNCH SUPPORT	24.6	15.9	7.2							47.7
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT		0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	1.6
TOTAL	91.2	66.0	20.6	8.7	9.7	15.0	8.8	0.2	0.3	220.5

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	Balance	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	116.6	8.3								124.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS		4.9	1.4	9.5	14.8	8.6				39.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT	40.0	3.5								43.5
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3		1.6
TOTAL	156.7	16.9	1.6	9.7	15.0	8.8	0.2	0.3		209.2

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-23)

	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	124.9									124.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS	4.9	3.1	11.0	14.4	8.6					42.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	43.5									43.5
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2					1.1
TOTAL	173.6	3.3	11.2	14.6	8.8					211.5

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

	PRIOR	1996	1996	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	124.9									124.9
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS	8.0	11.0	14.4	8.6						42.0
LAUNCH SUPPORT	43.5									43.5
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2					1.1
TOTAL	176.7	11.2	14.6	8.8	0.2					211.5

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

	PRIOR	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	124.9									124.9
LAUNCH SUPPORT	43.5									43.5
MISSION OPERATIONS	10.9	8.4	6.6	5.0						30.9
DATA ANALYSIS	8.1	5.9	6.4	3.0						23.4
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2						0.9
TOTAL	187.7	14.5	13.2	8.2						223.6

ESTIMATED CIVIL SERVICE PTEs (4) (4)
CIVIL SERVICE COMPENSATION ESTIMATE (\$M) 0.8 0.5

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
DEVELOPMENT	124.9									124.9
LAUNCH SUPPORT	43.5									43.5
MISSION OPERATIONS	19.3	6.6	5.0							30.9
DATA ANALYSIS	14.0	6.4	4.8	1.5	3.0	3.0	1.5			34.2
TRACKING & DATA SUPPORT	0.5	0.2	0.2							0.9
TOTAL	202.2	13.2	10.0	1.5	3.0	3.0	1.5			234.4

NEAR (Near Earth Asteroid Rendezvous) References

Krebs, Gunter D. *NEAR (Discovery 2, Shoemaker)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/near.htm.

NASA. *NEAR Shoemaker*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1996-008A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

New Horizons

Mission Attributes		New Horizons																																																	
Last Updated	9/13/2024																																																		
Definition	<table border="1"> <tr><td>COSPAR</td><td>2006-001A</td></tr> <tr><td>Program</td><td>New Frontiers 1</td></tr> <tr><td>Destination</td><td>Pluto</td></tr> <tr><td>Success</td><td>Operational</td></tr> <tr><td>Type</td><td>Flyby</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch Vehicle</td><td>Atlas 5</td></tr> </table>			COSPAR	2006-001A	Program	New Frontiers 1	Destination	Pluto	Success	Operational	Type	Flyby	Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5																																				
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Schedule	<table border="1"> <tr><td>Initial Design Duration (months)</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Realized Design Duration (months)</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Calculated Design Duration (months)</td><td>50.4</td></tr> <tr><td>Initial Mission Life (years)</td><td>15.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Realized Mission Life (years)</td><td>18.2</td></tr> <tr><td>Extended Mission Life (years)</td><td>7.0</td></tr> <tr><td>Phase A - Award</td><td>11/29/2001</td></tr> <tr><td>PDR</td><td>3/1/2003</td></tr> <tr><td>CDR</td><td>10/1/2003</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch</td><td>1/19/2006</td></tr> <tr><td>On Station</td><td>7/14/2015</td></tr> <tr><td>Extend Mission</td><td>3/1/2017</td></tr> <tr><td>End Mission</td><td>3/17/2024</td></tr> </table>			Initial Design Duration (months)		Realized Design Duration (months)		Calculated Design Duration (months)	50.4	Initial Mission Life (years)	15.0	Realized Mission Life (years)	18.2	Extended Mission Life (years)	7.0	Phase A - Award	11/29/2001	PDR	3/1/2003	CDR	10/1/2003	Launch	1/19/2006	On Station	7/14/2015	Extend Mission	3/1/2017	End Mission	3/17/2024																						
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Extend Mission	3/1/2017																																																		
End Mission	3/17/2024																																																		
Cost	<table border="1"> <tr><td>Start</td><td>2001</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch</td><td>2006</td></tr> <tr><td>Budget \$</td><td>594.9</td></tr> <tr><td>Realized \$</td><td>781.4</td></tr> <tr><td>Budget Schedule</td><td>44</td></tr> <tr><td>Realized Schedule</td><td>44</td></tr> <tr><td>Then \$</td><td>\$ 889.70</td></tr> <tr><td>Development</td><td>\$ 347.70</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch</td><td>\$ 218.00</td></tr> <tr><td>Operations</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Primary</td><td>\$ 215.70</td></tr> <tr><td>Extended</td><td>\$ 108.30</td></tr> <tr><td>NSII 2023\$</td><td>\$ 1,472.60</td></tr> <tr><td>Development</td><td>\$ 676.20</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch</td><td>\$ 416.80</td></tr> <tr><td>Operations</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Primary</td><td>\$ 241.70</td></tr> <tr><td>Extended</td><td>\$ 137.90</td></tr> <tr><td>PCEPI 2023\$</td><td>\$ 1,375.30</td></tr> <tr><td>Development</td><td>\$ 576.30</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch</td><td>\$ 357.10</td></tr> <tr><td>Operations</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Primary</td><td>\$ 309.80</td></tr> <tr><td>Extended</td><td>\$ 132.10</td></tr> </table>			Start	2001	Launch	2006	Budget \$	594.9	Realized \$	781.4	Budget Schedule	44	Realized Schedule	44	Then \$	\$ 889.70	Development	\$ 347.70	Launch	\$ 218.00	Operations	-	Primary	\$ 215.70	Extended	\$ 108.30	NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,472.60	Development	\$ 676.20	Launch	\$ 416.80	Operations	-	Primary	\$ 241.70	Extended	\$ 137.90	PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 1,375.30	Development	\$ 576.30	Launch	\$ 357.10	Operations	-	Primary	\$ 309.80	Extended	\$ 132.10
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Technical Scope	<table border="1"> <tr><td>Launch Mass</td><td>585</td><td>Payload</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Fuel</td><td>77</td><td>Instruments</td><td>7</td></tr> <tr><td>S/V Dry</td><td>508</td><td>Mass (kg)</td><td>30.4</td></tr> <tr><td>S/V Bus</td><td>478</td><td>Power (W, ave)</td><td>28.2</td></tr> <tr><td>S/V Payload</td><td>30</td><td>RTG or S/A</td><td>RTG</td></tr> <tr><td>Probe/Rover</td><td>-</td><td>S/A Power</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Cruise</td><td>-</td><td>BoL 1 Au</td><td>240</td></tr> <tr><td>Lander</td><td>-</td><td>Perihelion</td><td>200</td></tr> <tr><td>Aeroshield +</td><td>-</td><td>Aphelion</td><td>176</td></tr> <tr><td>Bus Volume (m³)</td><td>1.96</td><td>S/A Area (m²)</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Objectives</td><td>8</td><td>S/A Type</td><td>-</td></tr> <tr><td>Deployments</td><td>0</td><td>Blank</td><td>-</td></tr> </table>			Launch Mass	585	Payload		Fuel	77	Instruments	7	S/V Dry	508	Mass (kg)	30.4	S/V Bus	478	Power (W, ave)	28.2	S/V Payload	30	RTG or S/A	RTG	Probe/Rover	-	S/A Power	-	Cruise	-	BoL 1 Au	240	Lander	-	Perihelion	200	Aeroshield +	-	Aphelion	176	Bus Volume (m ³)	1.96	S/A Area (m ²)	-	Objectives	8	S/A Type	-	Deployments	0	Blank	-
Launch Mass	585	Payload																																																	
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Deployments	0	Blank	-																																																

New Horizons

- 1st New Frontiers program

- NASA 2005 Budget request, total budget \$619.2: CDR 10/03, launch 1/06, Pluto-Charon Encounter 7/15 (prime mission), End of Mission 1/20 (funding profile)
- Mission life: 1 year cruise and 3-year prime mission (Primary mission: 4 years)
- Extended mission: “transition to extended mission after the playback of all Pluto data” (flyby-PK), March 2017. “As part of the potential extended mission, it will delve deeper into the Kuiper Belt” (Pluto & Kuiper Belt PK)
- Status: Currently Operational
- Instruments
 - LORRI (8.8 kg, 5.8 W)
 - LEISA (11.2 kg, 19 W)
 - ALICE (4.5 kg, 4.4 W)
 - RALPH (10.3 kg, 6.3 W)
 - PAM: Plasma and High Energy Particle Spectrometer Suite
 - SWAP (3.3 kg, 2.3 W)
 - PEPSSI (1.5 kg, 2.5 W)
 - REX (0.1 kg, 2.1 W)
 - SDC (1.9 kg, 5 W)
- Bus Volume: 0.68 x 2.11 x 2.74m³ (irregular shape)
- Deployments: 0
- Objectives:
 - Probe atmospheric composition and surface structure, (1)
 - Obtain high-resolution color maps and surface composition maps, (2)
 - High resolution surface images, (3)
 - Measure solar wind charged particles in and around Pluto’s atmosphere, (4)
 - Measure masses of space-dust particles, (5) and
 - Examine the atmospheric structure, surface thermal properties, and the planet’s mass. (6)
 - Conduct a close flyby of at least one KBO. (+1 extended mission)
 - Survey the Kuiper Belt. (+2 extended mission)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

- RALPH: Multispectral Visible Imaging Camera
- PAM
 - SWAP: Solar Wind at Pluto
 - PEPSSI: Pluto Energetic Particle Spectrometer Science Investigation
- REX: Radio Science Experiment
- SDC: Student Dust Counter

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-21)

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY 2004 President's Budget	81.6	246.1	850.4	
ISP	19.0	62.5	75.0	
Project Prometheus		125.5	279.2	
JIMO			92.8	New Initiative - JIMO (part of Project Prometheus)
Nuclear Power	46.5	55.7		
Nuclear Propulsion	79.0	130.9		
Optical Communications			31.2	New Initiative - Optical Communications
X-2000	24.1	30.0	10.8	
Other SSE Tech	6.9			
Future Discovery	0.9	13.1	24.0	
New Frontiers		15.0	130.2	
New Horizons (PKB)		30.0		
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget	-9.4	-61.8	-88.6	Reason for Change:
ISP			+8.3	full cost
Project Prometheus			+54.7	
JIMO			+92.6	New Initiative - JIMO (part of Project Prometheus)
Nuclear Power			-32.5	-5.3 full cost; D4 deferral
Nuclear Propulsion			+32.5	-22.0 full cost; D4 deferral
Optical Communications			+31.2	New Initiative - Optical Communications
X-2000			-8.7	-16.7 redirected to other priorities
Other SSE Tech			+5.4	
Future Discovery			-9.1	-151.3 selected Dawn and Kepler
New Frontiers			-24.8	lower flight rate planned

Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
 Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
 FY 2002 and FY 2003 are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 2-14)

Budget Authority (\$ in millions)	Prior	FY03	FY04	FY05	FY06	FY07	FY08	FY09	BTC	Total	Comments
FY2005 PRESBD	30.7	123.6	116.8	115.8	84.4	19.0	8.4	5.9	114.6	619.2	
Development	30.7	123.6	116.8	115.8	84.4	19.0	8.4	5.9	114.6	619.2	
Changes since 2004 PRESBD	+30.7	+123.6	+116.8	+115.8	+84.4	+19.0	+8.4	+5.9	+114.6	+619.2	Moved from formulation into development
Development	+30.7	+123.6	+116.8	+115.8	+84.4	+19.0	+8.4	+5.9	+114.6	+619.2	
FY2004 PRESBD											

Indicates changes since the previous year's President's Budget Submit
 Indicates budget numbers in full cost.

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. Appendix – SAE 2-4)

Budget Detail/Life Cycle Cost (Dollars in Millions)

Budget Authority	Prior	FY2004	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2006 PRES BUD	154.3	140.1	103.0	87.7	16.1	9.5	5.7	6.1	72.4	594.9	
Changes	0.0	23.3	-12.8	3.3	-2.9	1.1	-0.2		-42.2	-24.3	
FY2006 President's Budget	154.3	116.8	115.8	84.4	19.0	8.4	5.9		114.6	619.2	

Additional funding to cover launch vehicle cost growth.

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p. SAE SMD 2-19)

Budget Detail/Life Cycle Cost (Dollars in Millions)

Budget Authority	Prior	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	FY2011	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2007 PRES BUD	294.4	193.5	83.3	18.6	10.2	5.8	6.1	6.6	78.4	696.9	
Changes	0.0	90.5	-4.4	2.5	0.7	0.1	0.1		6.0	95.4	
FY2006 President's Budget	294.4	103.0	87.7	16.1	9.5	5.7	6.1		72.4	594.9	

NASA 2008 Budget Request (p. SMD-168)

Other - \$77.8 FY 2006 (Actual)

NASA 2009 Budget Request (p. Sci-137)

Other Missions and Data Analysis - \$34.0 FY 2007 Actual

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p. SCI-117)

Other Missions and Data Analysis - \$23.9 FY 2008 Actual

From Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 585 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Fuel: 77 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 508 kg
 - Payload: 30 kg
 - Bus: 478 kg
- S/A Area: 0 m² (RTG)
- Power (1 Au): 240 W
- Power (station): 174 W (by 2016 – RTG degradation)
- Science
 - LORRI: Long Range Reconnaissance Imager
 - LEISA: Linear Etalon Imaging Spectral Array
 - ALICE: Ultraviolet Imaging Spectrometer

NASA 2011 Budget Request (p. PLANET - 35)
Other Missions and Data Analysis - \$19.0 FY 2009 Actual
NASA 2012 Budget Request (p. PS-39)
Other Missions and Data Analysis - \$22.4 FY 2010 (Actual)

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-35)
New Horizons - \$97 FY 2011 Actual

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-33)
New Horizons - \$26.5 FY 2012 Actual

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-34)
New Horizons - \$9.6 FY 2013 Actual

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-32)
New Horizons - \$12.9 FY 2014 Actual

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-35)
New Horizons - \$28.8 FY 2015 Actual

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-37)
New Horizons - \$21.5 FY 2016 Actual

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-54)
New Horizons - \$29.4 FY 2017 Actual

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-56)
New Horizons - \$12.0 FY 2018 Actual

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-62)
New Horizons - \$12.7 FY 2019 Actual

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-76)
New Horizons - \$17.3 FY 2020 Actual

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-87)
New Horizons - \$12.5 FY 2021 Actual
New Horizons - \$12.5 FY 2023 Request

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-83)
New Horizons - \$9.5 FY 2022 Actual
New Horizons - \$9.7 FY 2024 Request

New Horizons References

Krebs, Gunter D. *New Horizons (New Frontiers 1)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/new-horizons.htm.

NASA. *New Horizons Pluto Kuiper Belt Flyby*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2006-001A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

Osiris-Rex

Mission Attributes		Osiris-Rex	
Last Updated	9/13/2024	Cost	
Definition		Start	2011
COSPAR	2016-055A	Launch	2016
Program	New Frontiers 3	Budget \$	865.9
Destination	Asteroid	Realized \$	775.1
Success	Operational	Budget Schedule	52
Type	Sample Return	Realized Schedule	52
Launch Vehicle	Atlas 5	Then \$	\$ 1,125.30
Schedule		Development	\$ 591.60
Initial Design Duration (months)	52.0	Launch	\$ 183.50
Realized Design Duration (months)	52.0	Operations	-
Calculated Design Duration (months)	53.0	Primary	\$ 246.90
Initial Mission Life (years)	7.0	Extended	\$ 103.30
Realized Mission Life (years)	7.5	NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,350.70
Extended Mission Life (years)	0.5	Development	\$ 747.50
Phase A - Award	5/1/2012	Launch	\$ 224.50
PDR	3/1/2013	Operations	-
CDR	4/1/2014	Primary	\$ 275.40
Launch	9/8/2016	Extended	\$ 103.30
On Station	12/3/2018	PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 1,302.50
Extend Mission	9/24/2023	Development	\$ 712.20
End Mission	3/17/2024	Launch	\$ 217.60
Technical Scope		Operations	-
Launch Mass	1955	Primary	\$ 269.40
Fuel	1095	Extended	\$ 103.30
S/V Dry	860	Payload	
S/V Bus	750	Instruments	6
S/V Payload	110	Mass (kg)	110
Probe/Rover	-	Power (W, ave)	121.6
Cruise	-	RTG or S/A	S/A
Lander	-	S/A Power	-
Aeroshield +	-	BoL 1 Au	3000
Bus Volume (m ³)	26.112	Perihelion	1226
Objectives	5	Aphelion	-
Deployments	3	S/A Area (m ²)	8.5
		S/A Type	2 fixed
		Blank	-

Osiris-Rex

- Third New Frontiers program
- Travel to carbonaceous asteroid (101955) 1999 RQ36, study it, return a sample (>60 grams) with planned launch in September 2016
- Mission life: Asteroid encounter Aug 2018, Depart asteroid Mar 2021, Sample return to Earth Sept 2023
- Extension: Renamed Apophis Explorer extended April 22, 2023 (funded) / Sept 2023 (sample return) /or Sept 2025 (end of primary mission – sample analysis complete)
- Status: Currently Operational
- Instruments (reported 46 kg, 121.6 W: accounted 63.97 kg, 109.97 W)
 - OCAMS (27.9 kg, 32.2 W)
 - OLA (7.6 kg, 59 W)
 - OVIRS (17.8 kg, 8.8 W)
 - OTES (6.27 kg, 10.8 W)
 - REXIS (4.4 kg, 10.8 W)
 - RSS () – part of communications
 - TAGCAM – part of GN&C
 - Telcom – part of communications
- Bus Volume: 3.2 x 3.4 x 2.4 m³
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Robot arm x 1

- Objectives:
 - Return and analyze a sample (at least 60 g) of pristine regolith, (1)
 - Map the global properties, chemistry, and mineralogy, (2)
 - Document the textures, morphology, volatile chemistry, and spectral properties of the sample site, (3)
 - Measure the orbit deviation caused by non-gravitational forces (the Yablonsky effect), (4) and
 - Characterize the integrated global properties of the asteroid for comparison with ground-based observations. (5)
- Manufacturer: University of Arizona

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 725 kg (multiple sources: NSSDCA 1525 kg, NASA Explore 2110 kg, Spaceflight 101 1955 kg)
 - Fuel: 1095 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 860 kg
 - Payload: 46 kg, 121.6 W (63.97 kg, 109.97 W)
- S/A Area: 8.5 m²
- Power (1 Au): 3000 W
- Power (station): 1226 W (max distance from sun, initial asteroid encounter)
- Science
 - OCAMS: Osiris-Rex Camera Suite
 - OLA: Osiris-Rex Laser Altimeter
 - OVIRS: Osiris-Rex Visible and Infrared Spectrometer
 - OTES: Osiris-Rex Thermal Emission Spectrometer
 - REXIS: Regolith X-ray Imaging Spectrometer
 - RSS: Radio Science
 - TAGCAM: Two Navigation cameras and a “Stowcam”
 - Telcom

NASA 2013 Budget Request (p. PS-29)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual Estimate		Request					BIC	Total
		FY 2011	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017		
FY 2013 President's Budget Request	0.0	4.9	110.3	137.5	228.8	224.2	202.1	44.9	0.0	952.7
Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	27.2							
Percent Change From FY 2012 Estimate	--	--	24.7%							

NASA 2014 Budget Request (p. PS-28)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual		Notional				
	FY 2012	FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018
FY 2014 President's Budget Request	99.8	--	218.7	244.1	204.4	30.9	21.1
Change from FY 2012	--	--	118.9				
Percentage change from FY 2012	--	--	119.1%				

NASA 2015 Budget Request (p. PS-27)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual Enacted		Request					Notional			BIC	Total	
		FY 2013	FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022			
Formulation	108.1	36.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	144.3
Development/Implementation	0.0	89.3	207.3	224.8	187.0	13.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	721.7
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.7	30.7	26.1	43.1						198.3
2014 MPAR LCC Estimate	108.1	125.5	207.3	224.8	193.7	44.0	26.1	43.1						1064.2
Total Budget	108.1	125.5	218.7	224.8	193.7	44.0	26.1	43.1						1075.7
Change from FY 2014					6.1									
Percentage change from FY 2014					2.8%									

NASA 2016 Budget Request (p. PS-25)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual Enacted		Request					Notional			BIC	Total	
		FY 2014	FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022				
Formulation	144.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	144.3
Development/Implementation	89.3	207.3	216.8	183.0	13.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	709.7
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.7	30.7	38.1	43.1	27.7						210.3
2015 MPAR LCC Estimate	233.6	207.3	216.8	189.7	44.0	38.1	43.1	27.7						1064.3
Total Budget	233.6	207.3	216.8	189.7	44.0	38.1	43.1	27.7						1064.3
Change from FY 2015					-27.1									
Percentage change from FY 2015					-12.5%									

NASA 2017 Budget Request (p. PS-28)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Prior	Actual Enacted		Request					Notional			BIC	Total	
		FY 2015	FY 2016	FY 2017	FY 2018	FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022					
Formulation	144.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	144.3
Development/Implementation	296.6	209.8	180.7	13.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	700.4
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	9.0	30.7	38.1	43.1	27.7	16.5						212.6
2016 MPAR LCC Estimate	440.9	209.8	189.7	44.0	38.1	43.1	27.7	16.5						1067.3
Total Budget	440.9	209.8	189.7	44.0	38.1	43.1	27.7	16.5						1067.2
Change from FY 2016					-145.7									
Percentage change from FY 2016					-76.8%									

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-37)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2016	Enacted FY 2017	Request FY 2018	Notional			
				FY 2019	FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022
New Frontiers Future Missions	2.0	--	13.4	20.0	64.8	183.6	271.1
New Frontiers Research	0.0	--	5.4	9.4	12.4	13.1	13.7
Origins-Spectral Interpretation-Resource Identification-Security-Regolith Explorer (OSIRIS-REx)	124.7	--	36.8	55.3	50.7	21.6	22.2
New Horizons	21.5	--	12.0	12.0	16.5	9.5	0.0
Juno	45.8	--	14.5	25.0	25.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	194.0	--	82.1	121.7	169.4	227.8	307.0

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-54)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2017	Enacted FY 2018	Request FY 2019	Notional		
				FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022
New Frontiers Future Missions	1.5	--	30.8	64.1	183.3	271.0
New Frontiers Research	1.7	--	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.5
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	39.5	--	50.3	50.7	21.6	22.2
New Horizons	29.4	--	14.7	14.5	5.7	0.0
Juno	61.9	--	25.0	25.0	25.0	0.0
Total Budget	134.0	--	130.2	163.7	245.0	327.6

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-56)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2018	Enacted FY 2019	Request FY 2020	Notional		
				FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023
New Frontiers Future Missions	13.4	--	83.8	194.1	296.3	351.2
New Frontiers Research	2.1	--	6.0	7.0	9.4	9.5
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	42.8	--	50.3	21.6	17.2	26.6
New Horizons	12.0	--	18.3	9.5	0.0	0.0
Juno	17.8	--	32.0	29.0	19.0	0.0
Total Budget	88.1	--	190.4	261.2	341.9	387.3

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-62)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2019	Enacted FY 2020	Request FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025
New Frontiers Future Missions	2.3	--	9.7	70.6	6.0	19.9	46.8
New Frontiers Research	7.9	--	6.9	9.2	9.3	9.3	9.3
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	50.3	--	28.8	16.9	26.1	8.9	20.0
New Horizons	12.7	--	9.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Juno	11.8	--	28.4	18.9	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	85.0	--	83.2	115.5	41.4	38.2	76.1

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-76)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2020	Enacted FY 2021	Request FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026
New Frontiers Future Missions	1.7	4.3	1.5	2.4	11.9	90.8	60.3
New Frontiers Research	5.9	6.9	10.4	10.5	10.5	9.3	9.3
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	37.1	19.5	17.2	26.1	29.1	25.0	20.0
New Horizons	17.3	12.5	9.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Juno	33.8	30.9	32.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	13.0
Total Budget	95.8	74.0	70.6	76.5	89.0	162.6	115.1
Change from FY 2021			-3.4				
Percentage change from FY 2021			-4.6%				

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-87)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2021	Request FY 2022	Request FY 2023	FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	FY 2027
New Frontiers Future Missions	2.2	1.9	2.5	9.0	54.3	94.5	119.9
New Frontiers Research	4.9	10.4	10.5	10.5	9.3	9.3	9.5
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	10.4	11.1	32.1	36.8	25.4	20.0	32.4
New Horizons	12.5	9.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Juno	35.0	31.8	30.5	28.4	26.2	8.1	13.0
Total Budget	64.9	64.6	88.1	97.2	127.6	144.4	187.3
Change from FY 2022 Budget Request			23.5				
Percent change from FY 2022 Budget Request			36.4%				

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-83)

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan FY 2022	Enacted FY 2023	Request FY 2024	FY 2025	FY 2026	FY 2027	FY 2028
Apophis Explorer	0.0	--	14.5	15.8	19.9	22.1	31.0
New Frontiers Future Missions	0.5	--	0.0	35.6	74.0	128.0	272.0
New Frontiers Research	10.4	--	10.5	9.3	9.3	9.5	9.7
Origins Spectral Interpretation Resource	12.5	--	16.8	5.4	0.0	0.0	0.0
New Horizons	9.5	--	9.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Juno	31.8	--	28.4	26.2	8.1	0.0	0.0
Total Budget	64.6	--	79.9	92.3	111.3	159.6	312.7

Osiris-Rex References

Krebs, Gunter D. *OSIRIS-REx* → *OSIRIS-APEX (New Frontiers 3)*. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/osiris-rex.htm.

NASA. *OSIRIS-Rex*. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=2016-055A>, downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

Spaceflight101. (2024). *OSIRIS-REx Mission & Trajectory Design*. <https://spaceflight101.com/osiris-rex/osiris-rex-mission-profile/>. viewed Mar 14, 2024.

Spaceflight101. (2024). *OSIRIS-REx Spacecraft*. <https://spaceflight101.com/osiris-rex/osiris-rex-spacecraft-overview/>. viewed Mar 14, 2024.

Phoenix

Mission Attributes		Phoenix	
Last Updated	9/13/2024		
Definition		COSPASR 2007-034A	
Program	Scout 1		
Destination	Mars		
Success	Success		
Type	Lander		
Launch Vehicle	Delta 7925		
Schedule		Initial Design Duration (months) 43.0	
		Realized Design Duration (months) 43.0	
		Calculated Design Duration (months) 48.7	
		Initial Mission Life (years) 1.2	
		Realized Mission Life (years) 1.3	
		Extended Mission Life (years) 0.2	
		Phase A - Award 8/4/2003	
		PDR 2/1/2005	
		CDR 9/1/2005	
		Launch 8/4/2007	
		On Station 5/25/2008	
		Extend Mission 8/24/2008	
		End Mission 11/16/2008	
Technical Scope		Launch Mass 664	
		Fuel 67	
		S/V Dry	
		S/V Bus	
		S/V Payload 59	
		Probe/Rover -	
		Cruise -	
		Lander -	
		Aeroshield +	
		Bus Volume (m³) 1.75	
		Objectives 4	
		Deployments 3	
Payload		Instruments 6	
		Mass (kg) 59	
		Power (W, ave) 53	
		RTG or S/A S/A	
		S/A Power -	
		Bol. 1 Au 600	
		Perihelion 334	
		S/A Area (m2) 4.2	
		S/A Type 2 fixed	
		Blank -	
Cost		Start 2003	
		Launch 2007	
		Budget \$ 325	
		Realized \$ 412.8	
		Budget Schedule 41	
		Realized Schedule 41	
		Then \$ 417.00	
		Development \$ 318.20	
		Launch \$ 86.20	
		Operations -	
		Primary \$ 8.40	
		Extended \$ 4.20	
		NSII 2023S \$ 630.10	
		Development \$ 484.80	
		Launch \$ 127.70	
		Operations -	
		Primary \$ 11.80	
		Extended \$ 5.80	
		PCEPI 2023S \$ 576.40	
		Development \$ 442.80	
		Launch \$ 117.10	
		Operations -	
		Primary \$ 11.00	
		Extended \$ 5.50	

Phoenix

- The Phoenix lander was built and was in testing for application as the 2001 Mars Surveyor program. Mars Surveyor was cancelled after the Mars Polar Lander failed in December 1999.
- Lander sat in storage at Lockheed Martin Denver, managed by NASA's new Mars Exploration Program.
- Phoenix included improved versions of the University of Arizona panoramic camera and volatile-analysis instrument from MPL, and experiments built for the 2001 Mars Surveyor Program, including the JPL trench-digging robot arm and chemistry-microscopy instrument. Payload also includes a meteorological instrument suite provided by CSA (\$37M, not sure reference of \$)
- Mission life: 10-month cruise and 152 sols (Primary mission: 10 months + 156.2 days = 1.25 years)
- Extension: Extended 84 days (onset of Martian Winter, did not recover. Imagery suggests that solar arrays collapsed)
- Status: Success
- Instruments
 - MARDI (unknown)
 - SSI (unknown)
 - RA and RAC (unknown)

- TEGA (5.7 kg, 13 W)
- MECA (unknown)
- MET (7.5 kg, 40 W)
- Bus Volume: $0.75 \phi \times 1.0 m^3 = 1.75 m^3$
- Deployments: 3
 - Solar array x 2
 - Robot Arm x 1
- Objectives: (only stated 4 objectives in database: objectives 1 & 2 combine in literature sources)
 - Determine polar climate and weather, interaction with the surface, and composition of the lower atmosphere around 70 degrees north for at least 90 sols, (1)
 - Determine the atmospheric characteristics during descent through the atmosphere, (2)
 - Characterize the geomorphology and active processes shaping the northern plains and the physical properties of the near-surface regolith, focusing on the role of water, (3)
 - Determine the aqueous mineralogy and chemistry as well as the adsorbed gases and organic content of the regolith, (4) and
 - Characterize the history of water, ice, and polar climate and determine the past and present biological potential of the surface and subsurface environments. (5)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

Not included in Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 670 kg
 - Ballast: kg
 - Fuel: 67 kg
 - Space Vehicle: kg
 - Launder: 410 kg
 - Aeroshell: 172 kg
 - Heat shield: 62 kg.
 - Backshell: 110 kg
 - Cruise Stage: 82 kg
 - Instruments: 59 kg
- S/A Area: $4.16 m^2$ (Photovoltaics for Space: $7 m^2$)
- Power (1 Au): 600 W
- Power (station): 334 W (sol 1 – from locked presentation for Power Subsystem design – AIAA document that I do not have access to, chart of power versus sol as part of dust study ~330 W)
- Science
 - MARDI: Mars Descent Imager
 - SSI: Stereo Imager
 - RA and RAC: Robot Arm and Camera
 - TEGA: Thermal Evolved Gas Analyzer
 - MECA: Mars Environmental Compatibility Assessment
 - MET: Meteorology Suite

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-7)

Phoenix (Scout 07)	FY2004	FY2005	FY2006
FY 2006 PRES BUD	25.4	96.1	94.4
Changes from FY 2005 Request	-3.5	-6.7	

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p. SAE SMD 2-35)

President's FY 2007 Budget Request (Dollars in Millions)

Phoenix (Scouts 07) (Development)	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	FY2011
FY 2007 PRES BUD	108.9	125.6	90.5	28.6	1.0		
Changes from FY 2006 Request	12.8	31.3	-1.8	-5.3	-5.0		

(p SAE SMD 2-37)

Budget Detail/Life Cycle Cost (Dollars in Millions)

Budget Authority	Prior	FY2005	FY2006	FY2007	FY2008	FY2009	FY2010	FY2011	BTC	Total	Comments
FY 2007 PRES BUD	30.7	108.9	125.6	90.5	28.6	1.0				385.3	
Changes	0.1	12.8	31.3								
FY 2005 President's Budget	30.6	96.1	94.4								

Phoenix entered development in November 2005 at which time the LCC baseline commitment was established. Therefore, no LCC in FY 2006 budget.

Life Cycle Cost (LCC) elements:
 Spacecraft: \$154M
 Launch Vehicle: \$79M
 Instruments/Payloads: \$54M
 Other: \$98.3M

NASA 2008 Budget Request (p. SMD-146)

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	Prior	FY06	FY07	FY08	FY09	FY10	FY11	FY12	BTC	LCC TOTAL
FY 2008 President's Budget Request	146.5	141.5	99.8	11.4	1.2	-	-	-	-	400.4
Formulation	85.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Development	60.8	141.5	99.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Operations	-	-	-	11.4	1.2	-	-	-	-	-
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
FY 2007 President's Budget Request	139.6	125.6	90.5	28.6	1.0	-	-	-	-	385.3
Formulation	83.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Development	56.4	125.6	90.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Operations	-	-	-	28.6	1.0	-	-	-	-	-
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Changes	7.0	15.9	9.3	-17.2	0.2	-	-	-	-	15.1
Formulation	2.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.5
Development	4.4	15.9	9.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	28.6
Operations	-	-	-	-17.2	0.2	-	-	-	-	-17.0
Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

NASA 2009 Budget Request (p.)

No information.

NASA 2010 Budget Request (p.)

No information.

Phoenix References

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Psyche

Mission Attributes Psyche	
Last Updated	9/13/2024
Definition	
COSPAR	2023-157A
Program	Discovery 14
Destination	Asteroid Belt
Success	Operational
Type	Orbiter
Launch Vehicle	Falcon Heavy
Schedule	
Initial Design Duration (months)	48.0
Realized Design Duration (months)	61.0
Calculated Design Duration (months)	66.4
Initial Mission Life (years)	7.4
Realized Mission Life (years)	0.4
Extended Mission Life (years)	-7.2
Phase A - Award	5/1/2018
PDR	3/1/2019
CDR	4/20/2024
Launch	10/13/2023
On Station	8/1/2029
Extend Mission	6/1/2031
End Mission	3/17/2024
Technical Scope	
Launch Mass	2800
Fuel	1064
S/V Dry	1400
S/V Bus	1330
S/V Payload	70
Probe/Rover	-
Cruise	-
Lander	-
Aeroshield +	-
Bus Volume (m ³)	25.87
Objectives	5
Deployments	4
Cost	
Start	2016
Launch	2023
Budget \$	925
Realized \$	1108.1
Budget Schedule	48
Realized Schedule	61
Then \$	\$ 1,108.10
Development	\$ 844.50
Launch	\$ 112.70
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 150.90
Extended	-
NSII 2023\$	\$ 1,202.70
Development	\$ 935.90
Launch	\$ 115.90
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 150.90
Extended	-
PCEPI 2023\$	\$ 1,176.10
Development	\$ 912.50
Launch	\$ 112.70
Operations	-
Primary	\$ 150.90
Extended	-
Payload	
Instruments	3
Mass (kg)	70
Power (W, ave)	46.2
RTG or S/A	S/A
S/A Power	-
BoL 1 Au	19200
Perihelion	2400
Aphelion	-
S/A Area (m ²)	75.0
S/A Type	2 articulated
Blank	-

Psyche

- Initially planned as a 2023 launch, restructured for a 2022 launch
- 14th Discovery mission
- Mission life: 4-year cruise and 22-month prime mission (Primary mission: 5 years 10 months)
- Extension: currently on cruise
- Status: Currently Operational
- Instruments
 - MAG (4.4 kg, 4.2 W) – based on Messenger MAG
 - MastCam (4.0 kg, 17.4 W) – based on Mars Science Laboratory Cam
 - GRS&NS (18.7 kg, 24.6 W)
 - GRS (13.1 kg, 23.6 W) – based on Messenger GRS
 - NS (5.6 kg, 0.94 W) – based on Lunar Prospector NS
- Bus Volume: 4.9 x 2.2 x 2.4 m³
- Deployments: 4
 - Solar array x 2
 - HGA x 1
 - MAG x 1 (or 2)
- Objectives:
 - Determine whether Psyche is a core of if it is unmelted material, (1)
 - Determine the relative ages of regions of Psyche’s surface, (2)
 - Determine whether small metal bodies incorporate the same light elements as are in the Earth’s high-pressure core, (3)
 - Determine whether Psyche formed under conditions more oxidizing or more reducing than Earth’s core, (4) and
 - Characterize Psyche’s topography. (5)
- Manufacturer: Maxar Technologies (Loral)

Not included in Jane’s Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 2800 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 1064 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 1400 kg
 - Payload: 27.1 kg
- S/A Area: 75 m²
- Power (1 Au): 19,200 W
- Power (station): 2,400 W
- Science
 - MAG: Magnetometer
 - MastCam: Camera
 - GRS&NS: Gamma-Ray Spectrometer and Neutron Spectrometers (2)

NASA 2018 Budget Request (p. PS-25)

FY 2018 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2016	Enacted FY 2017	Request FY 2018	FY 2019	Notional FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022
Total Budget	0.0	--	25.0	160.4	210.0	169.2	181.0

NASA 2019 Budget Request (p. PS-43)

FY 2019 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2018	CR FY 2019	Request FY 2019	FY 2020	Notional FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023
Total Budget	54.5	--	153.3	209.8	154.7	56.4	16.5

NASA 2020 Budget Request (p. PS-43)

FY 2020 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Actual FY 2019	Enacted FY 2020	Request FY 2020	FY 2021	FY 2022	FY 2023	FY 2024
Total Budget	42.0	--	213.2	181.9	156.4	33.7	24.0

NASA 2021 Budget Request (p. PS-43)

FY 2021 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Request FY 2021	Request FY 2022	Request FY 2023	Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2019							
Formulation	92.3	51.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	143.7
Development/Implementation	0.0	122.8	219.3	187.4	152.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	681.9
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.7	29.0	32.0	81.1
2020 MPAR LCC Estimate	92.3	174.2	219.3	187.4	152.4	28.7	29.0	32.0	81.1
Total Budget	92.3	174.2	219.3	187.4	152.4	28.7	29.0	32.0	81.1
Change from FY 2020			-31.9						
Percentage change from FY 2020			-14.5%						

NASA 2022 Budget Request (p. PS-53)

FY 2022 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan			Request FY 2022	Request FY 2023	Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	Request FY 2026	BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2020	FY 2021							
Formulation	143.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	143.7
Development/Implementation	122.8	214.0	169.6	139.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	646.1
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.7	29.0	32.0	32.0	49.1
2021 MPAR LCC Estimate	266.5	214.0	169.6	139.7	28.7	29.0	32.0	32.0	49.1	960.6
Total Budget	266.5	214.0	169.6	139.7	28.7	29.0	32.0	32.0	49.1	960.6
Change from FY 2021				-29.9						
Percentage change from FY 2021				-17.6%						

NASA 2023 Budget Request (p. PS-50)

FY 2023 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Request FY 2023	Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	Request FY 2026	Request FY 2027	BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2021							
Formulation	143.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	143.7
Development/Implementation	336.8	175.6	138.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	651.1
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	38.8	29.0	32.0	32.0	35.4	13.7
2022 MPAR LCC Estimate	480.5	175.6	138.7	38.8	29.0	32.0	32.0	35.4	13.7
Total Budget	480.5	175.6	138.7	38.8	29.0	32.0	32.0	35.4	13.7
Change from FY 2022 Budget Request				-99.9					
Percent change from FY 2022 Budget Request				-72.0%					

NASA 2024 Budget Request (p. PS-53)

FY 2024 Budget

Budget Authority (in \$ millions)	Op Plan		Request FY 2024	Request FY 2025	Request FY 2026	Request FY 2027	Request FY 2028	BTC	Total
	Prior	FY 2022							
Formulation	143.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	143.7
Development/Implementation	512.4	163.8	109.3	28.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	813.8
Operations/Close-out	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.4	34.5	34.5	37.1	15.4	150.9
2023 MPAR LCC Estimate	656.1	163.8	109.3	57.7	34.5	34.5	37.1	15.4	0.6
Total Budget	656.1	163.8	109.3	57.7	34.5	34.5	37.1	15.4	0.6
Change from FY 2023 Enacted				-51.6					
Percent change from FY 2023 Enacted				-47.2%					

Psyche References

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Hart, William; Brown, G. Mark; Collins, Steven M.; De Soria-Satacruz, Maria; Fiesler, Paul; Goebel, Dan; Marsh, Danielle; Oh, David Y.; Snyder, Steve; Warner, Noah; Whiffen, Gregory; Elkins-Tanton, Linda T.; Bell III, James F.; Lawrence, David J.; Lord, Peter; Prikl, Zachary, 2018, *Overview of the Spacecraft Design for the Psyche Mission Concept*, <https://hdl.handle.net/2014/47495>, 2018 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, Montana, March 3-10, 2018, JPL Open Repository.

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Stardust		Mission Attributes																																																	
Stardust		Stardust																																																	
Last Updated		9/13/2024																																																	
Definition		<table border="1"> <tr><td>COSPAR</td><td>1999-003A</td></tr> <tr><td>Program</td><td>Discovery 4</td></tr> <tr><td>Destination</td><td>Comet</td></tr> <tr><td>Success</td><td>Success</td></tr> <tr><td>Type</td><td>Sample Return</td></tr> <tr><td>Launch Vehicle</td><td>Delta 7426</td></tr> </table>		COSPAR	1999-003A	Program	Discovery 4	Destination	Comet	Success	Success	Type	Sample Return	Launch Vehicle	Delta 7426																																				
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Blank	-																																																		

Stardust

- First US mission dedicated solely to the exploration of a comet.
- Mission life: 7-year cruise, sample, return (Primary mission: 7 years)
- Extension: Mission extended three times, 1/15/2006 through 2/14/2011
- Status: Successful
- Instruments
 - DFMI (1.76 kg, 1.8 W)
 - CIDA (10.4 kg, 15 W)
 - NC (12 kg, 18 W)
 - DS (bus components)
- Bus Volume: 1.6 x 0.66 x 0.66 m³
- Deployments: 5
 - Solar array x 2
 - Sample collector x 1
 - Sample separation x 1
 - Sample return x 1
- Objectives:
 - Collect coma sample material from Comet P/Wild 2, (1)
 - Collect interstellar dust grains during cruise to Comet P/Wild 2, (2) and
 - Return samples to Earth. (3)
- Manufacturer: Lockheed Martin

From Jane's Space Systems and Industry 2011-2012

- Control: 3-axis stabilized
- Launch mass: 385 kg (consistent with Delta II launch manifest)
 - Ballast (unaccounted mass): kg
 - Fuel: 85 kg
 - Space Vehicle: 254 kg
 - Payload: 24.16 kg
- S/A Area: 6.6 m²
- Power (1 Au): 800 W
- Power (station): 170 W
- Science
 - DFMI: Dust Flux Monitor Instrument
 - CIDA: Cometary and Interstellar Dust Analyzer
 - NC: Navigation Camera

NASA 1998 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

	PRIOR	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B		9.6								9.6
DEVELOPMENT		13.5	52.2	42.3	9.8					117.8
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				1.6	3.4	3.3	3.3	25.6		37.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT		4.6	10.5	13.9	12.5					41.5
TOTAL		27.7	62.7	56.2	25.9	3.4	3.3	3.3	25.6	206.1

NASA 1999 Budget Request (p. SI-24)

	PRIOR	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B		9.6								9.6
DEVELOPMENT		13.5	52.2	42.3	9.8					117.8
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				3.5	3.5	3.7	3.7	5	17.8	37.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT		7.5	11.5	13.9	12.5					45.4
TOTAL		30.6	63.7	56.2	25.8	3.5	3.7	3.7	5.0	210.0

NASA 2000 Budget Request (p. SI-26)

Stardust

The Stardust mission was selected as the fourth Discovery mission in November 1996, with mission management from the Jet Propulsion Laboratory. The mission team completed the Phase B analysis, and Stardust was approved for implementation in October 1996. The mission is designed to gather samples of dust from the comet Wild 2 and return the samples to Earth for detailed analysis. The mission will also gather and return samples of interstellar dust that the spacecraft encounters during its trip through the Solar System to fly by the comet. Stardust will use a new material called aerogel to capture the dust samples. In addition to the aerogel collectors, the spacecraft will carry three additional scientific instruments. An optical camera will return images of the comet; the Cometary and Interstellar Dust Analyzer (CIDA) is provided by Germany to perform basic compositional analysis of the samples while in flight; and a dust flux monitor will be used to sense particle impacts on the spacecraft. Stardust will be launched on the Med-Lite expendable launch vehicle in February 1999 with return of the samples to Earth in January 2006.

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B		9.6								9.6
DEVELOPMENT		65.7	42.3	9.8						117.8
MISSION OPS & DATA ANALYSIS				3.5	3.5	3.7	3.7	5.0	4.0	37.2
LAUNCH SUPPORT		19.0	13.9	12.5						45.4
TOTAL		94.3	56.2	25.8	3.5	3.7	3.7	5.0	4.0	210.0

NASA 2001 Budget Request (p. SI-25)

(Budget Authority in Millions of Dollars)

	PRIOR	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B		9.6								9.6
DEVELOPMENT		108.0	8.8							116.8
LAUNCH SUPPORT		28.3	12.5							40.8
MISSION OPERATIONS			1.0	1.0	1.0	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.0	8.7
DATA ANALYSIS			2.5	3.3	3.0	2.7	3.8	5.0	7.7	29.6
TOTAL		145.9	24.8	4.3	4.0	3.7	5.0	6.2	9.0	205.5

NASA 2002 Budget Request (p. SI-27)

	PRIOR	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	BTC	TOTAL
PHASE A/B		9.6								9.6
DEVELOPMENT		116.8								116.8
LAUNCH SUPPORT		40.8								40.8
MISSION OPERATIONS		1.0	1.0	3.8	3.6	4.7	5.2	4.6	5.7	29.6
DATA ANALYSIS		2.5	3.3	0.8	0.7	0.9	1.6	1.0	0.9	11.7
TOTAL		170.7	4.3	4.6	4.3	5.6	6.8	5.6	6.6	208.5

NASA 2003 Budget Request (p.) – nothing listed for 2001.

NASA 2004 Budget Request (p. SAE 2-16)

Budget Authority (\$M)	FY02	FY03	FY04	Comments
FY02 President's Budget	119.9	310.8	330.7	
Stardust	3.5	4.6	5.3	
Genesis	8.0	7.2	8.2	
Contour		2.4		
Galileo	1.5			
DS-1	0.3			
Messenger			3.0	
Deep Impact			6.9	
Dawn				
Cassini	30.7	31.5	30.3	
DSN expansion	22.0	15.3	0.7	
DSMS	55.9	249.6	255.5	
Changes since FY 03 Pres. Budget	+6.8	+0.0	-3.4	Reason for Change:
Stardust			+0.3	
Genesis			+2.0	growth
Contour			-2.0	spacecraft lost
Messenger			+0.1	full cost
Deep Impact			+0.1	full cost
Dawn			+1.0	new mission selection
Cassini			+1.0	full cost
DSN expansion			+7.0	
DSMS			-1.0	includes transfer to Optical Comm

Indicates budget numbers in full cost.
 Indicates changes since the FY 2003 President's Budget Submit.
 FY 2002 and FY 2003 are not in full cost.

NASA 2005 Budget Request (p. ESA 2-18)

BUDGET

Budget Authority (\$ millions)	FY 2003	FY 2004	FY 2005	Comments
FY2005 PRESBUD	298.0	308.2	277.0	
Stardust	4.7	5.3		
Genesis	8.1	8.2		
Messenger		3.0		
Deep Impact		6.9		
Cassini	31.3	30.1	16.3	
DSN expansion	15.2	0.7		
DSMS	239.6	254.0	260.7	
Changes since 2004 PRESBUD	-11.7	-1.7		MO&DA combined
Stardust		+0.1		
Genesis		+0.9		
Cassini		-0.2	-0.2	
DSN expansion		-0.1		
DSMS		-10.0	-1.5	
Contour		-2.4		

NASA 2006 Budget Request (p.) – no definition of Discovery mission operations cost

NASA 2007 Budget Request (p.) – no definition of Discovery mission operations cost

Stardust References

Krebs, Gunter D. ***Stardust (Discovery 4) / NExT***. Gunter's Space Page. Retrieved March 03, 2024, from https://space.skyrocket.de/doc_sdat/stardust.htm .

NASA. ***Stardust/NExT***. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1999-003A> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

NASA. ***Stardust Sample Return Capsule***. NASA Space Science Data Coordinated Achievements. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/nmc/spacecraft/display.action?id=1999-003D> , downloaded Mar 3, 2024.

Data Dictionary – NIM Database Table 2

The NIM database is organized and presented in Table 2 by data segment, consisting of programmatic, schedule, cost, and technical data. Cost is provided in three data formats: Then \$ is represented as the sum of incurred costs valued at the year of inception, NSII adjusted \$ is defined as the sum of adjusted incurred costs inflated from the value of the year of inception to 2022 \$ using the appropriate index multiplier, and PCEPI adjusted \$ represented as the sum of adjusted incurred costs inflated from the value of the year of inception to 2022 \$ using the appropriate index multiplier.

Unpopulated cells are designated with “na”. Cells containing a zero value represent a quantity of zero or a value of 0 and do not designate a blank entry.

Mission Definition

The mission definition provides the programmatic attributes of the mission elements. These variables are string-formatted data. This includes:

<i>Mission</i> –	Given the identification name of the NASA interplanetary mission/program
<i>COSPAR</i> –	International identifier assigned to artificial objects in space by the Committee on Space Research (COSPAR)
<i>Initiative</i> –	NASA program name or program directive of a class of missions
<i>Destination</i> –	Planet or celestial body identified as the primary science objective of the mission: lunar, LaGrange 1, Mercury, Venus, Mars, Saturn, Jupiter, comet, asteroid, asteroid belt.
<i>Success</i> –	The operational status of the mission: Success, Failure, or Operational. Failure is defined as the inability to achieve the primary science objective.
<i>Type</i> –	Primary science function class of the mission: flyby, impact, lander, orbiter, rendezvous, rover, or sample return
<i>Launch Vehicle</i> –	Expendable or reusable launch platform used to achieve Earth-based transfer orbit status

Schedule

The schedule definition provides the initial budget schedule attributes of the mission elements. Month and year time durations are real-number data. Dates are presented in the format mm/dd/yyyy. This includes:

<i>Proposed Design Schedule (PDS)</i> –	Initial schedule budget for development activities defined as initiation (contract award or funding announcement) to launch. (months)
<i>Proposed Mission</i>	

Schedule (PMS) – Proposed or initial schedule budget for the operations life defined as launch to end of mission disposal (years)

Realized Design

Schedule (RDS) – The reported development schedule is stated as the period between initiation (contract award or funding announcement) and launch. (months)

Calculated Design

Schedule (CDS) – Calculated as the [number of days/30] from the funding announcement to the manifest launch date, actual time realized. (months)

Realized Mission

Schedule (RMS) – The reported primary operations schedule stated as launch to current status. The current status is either the end of the mission (for both successful and failed missions) or March 17, 2024 (the date establishing Version 1.0). This data should be updated for consistency as operational missions transition to extended missions or reach the end of mission status. (years)

Calculated Mission

Schedule (CMS) – Calculated as the [number of days/365] from the operational schedule reported from the launch date to the end of the mission date, actual time realized. (years)

Feasibility – The document's feasibility date indicates when the proposed mission was considered viable for concept development, feasibility analysis, or consideration. (date)

Funding – The document date for the selection or award indicates the initiation of the mission, which is typically identified by the award date, funding date, and budget request initiation date, as acknowledged in a NASA announcement. (date)

PDR – The document/report date for the completion of the mission, Preliminary Design Review (PDR) associated with the spacecraft bus PDR. Instrument and Launch Vehicle PDRs are completed before the spacecraft bus/mission PDR. (date)

CDR – The documented/report date for the completion of the mission Critical Design Review (CDR) associated with the spacecraft bus CDR. Instrument and Launch Vehicle CDRs are completed before the spacecraft bus/mission CDR. (date)

Launch – The document/manifest date recording the mission launch. (date)

On-station – The document date recording the arrival of the mission at the primary destination is described as the initiation of orbit acquisition, spacecraft

	initiation, or initial instrument operation/ check-out. (date)
<i>Science</i> –	The document/announcement date signifying the initiation of primary science operations. (date)
<i>Mission Extension (Extend)</i> –	The document/announcement date signifying the end of primary operations, initiation of extended mission operation scope, or extension of operation funding. (date)
<i>End of Mission (EoM)</i> –	The document/announcement date indicates the end of the mission, either as loss of communication, loss of science function, loss of tracking contact, or disposal. (date)
<i>StartY</i> –	The Year the mission was identified as a line item in the NASA budget requests. (yyyy format)
<i>LaunchY</i> –	The Year the mission was reported launched in the NASA budget requests. (yyyy format)

Cost

The cost attributes are organized into four parts: cost and schedule planning and performance, cost accounting in Then Year \$, cost accounting adjusted for inflation using the NSII index, and cost accounting adjusted for inflation using the PCEPI index. Headings use a WXYZ format for identification:

- W represents the cost context: P – proposed, F – final, and T – total reported
- X represents the program phase: M – mission (full program duration), D – development, L – launch, O – primary operations, E – extended operations
- Y represents the system component: C – cost
- Z represents the accounting format: T – Then-Year (reported) dollars, N – NSII adjusted dollars, P – PCEPI adjusted dollars. All dollars are reported in millions (\$M)

The Part 1 cost attributes provide the initial budget cost and schedule attributes of the original mission planning.

The Part 2 cost attributes provide the cost summation by mission cost attributes (development, launch, primary operations, and extended operations) for the mission. Lumped costs are distributed over a time duration consistent with other detailed cost profiles. This was common with launch vehicle cost accounting, which was reported as a single cost budget item. When required, the launch cost was distributed over a 2 or 3-year period of performance, including the launch year and preceding years.

The Part 3 cost attributes provide the cost summation by mission cost attribute (development, launch, primary operations, and extended operations) for the mission adjusted for inflation using the NSII index. The NSII index adjusts cost elements to 2022 \$ based on the NSII index multiplier and the year of cost incurred. Cost

attributes represent the accumulation of expenses over successive years, with each year assigned an independent multiplier based on the NSII index. Expenses incurred in 2023 and 2024 were assigned a multiplier of 1.00.

The Part 4 cost attributes provide the cost summation by mission cost attribute (development, launch, primary operations, and extended operations) for the mission adjusted for inflation using the PCEPI index. The PCEPI index adjusts cost elements to 2022 \$ based on the PCEPI index multiplier and the year of cost incurred. Cost attributes are the accumulation of expenses over successive years, with each year assigned an independent multiplier based on the PCEPI index. Expenses incurred in 2023 and 2024 were assigned a multiplier of 1.00.

Cost values are listed in millions of dollars (\$M). This includes:

<i>PMCT</i> –	Proposed Mission Cost Total represents the total mission cost proposed in the initial NASA budget request or amount allocated by NASA before the mission award.
<i>CMCT</i> –	Calculated Mission Cost Total represents the current/final realized mission cost reported in the NASA budget requests.
<i>TMCT</i> –	Total Mission Cost in Then-\$ represents the total mission cost summed for all years of program reporting, as actual costs reported in the NASA budget requests. These values are not adjusted.
<i>TDCT</i> –	Total Development Cost in Then-\$ represents the total development cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests. These values are not adjusted.
<i>TLCT</i> –	Total Launch Cost in Then-\$ represents the total launch cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests. These values are not adjusted.
<i>TOCT</i> –	Total Operations Cost in Then-\$ represents the total planned operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests. These values are not adjusted.
<i>TECT</i> –	Total Extension Cost in Then-\$ represents the total extended operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests. These values are not adjusted.
<i>TMCN</i> –	Total Mission Cost in NSII-\$ represents the total mission cost summed for all years of the program reported as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the NSII index.

<i>TDCN</i> –	Total Development Cost in NSII-\$ represents the total development cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the NSII index.	<i>(LM)</i> –	The manifested launch mass of the spacecraft. (kgs)
<i>TLCN</i> –	Total Launch Cost in NSII-\$ represents the total launch cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the NSII index.	<i>Fuel</i> –	The spacecraft fuel load. In most cases, the fuel load is the difference between the launch mass and the spacecraft's dry mass. Where documented, this is confirmed by fuel budgets. Fuel includes propellant and oxidizer. (kgs)
<i>TOCN</i> –	Total Operations Cost in NSII-\$ represents the total planned operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the NSII index.	<i>AKM</i> –	AKM is the mass of the apogee kick motor (AKM) used for orbit circularization or transfer boost integrated within the spacecraft. (kgs)
<i>TECN</i> –	Total Extension Cost in NSII-\$ represents the total extended operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the NSII index.	<i>Ballast and Adapter (Ball)</i> –	The ballast and adapter account for any non-space vehicle accommodations, including the launch vehicle adapter and/or ballast that is not included in the SCdry mass but contributes to the total launch mass of the spacecraft, independent of fuel. (kgs)
<i>TMCP</i> –	Total Mission Cost in PCEPI-\$ represents the total mission cost summed for all years of the program reported as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the PCEPI index.	<i>SCdry</i> –	SCdry is the total spacecraft dry mass ready for launch before launch site fueling. (kgs)
<i>TDCP</i> –	Total Development Cost in PCEPI-\$ represents the total development cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the PCEPI index.	<i>SVbus</i> –	SVbus is the space vehicle bus mass, less payload and fuel integration. (kgs)
<i>TLCP</i> –	Total Development Cost in PCEPI-\$ represents the total development cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the PCEPI index.	<i>SVpayload (SVpay)</i> –	SVpayload is the total, or calculated from the instruments, space vehicle payload mass ready for integration with the space vehicle bus. (kgs)
<i>TOCP</i> –	Total Operations Cost in PCEPI-\$ represents the total planned operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the PCEPI index.	<i>Probe</i> –	The probe mass accounts for secondary payload elements that are deployed from the primary spacecraft, such as probes, and are not integral to the spacecraft science operations. (kgs)
<i>TECP</i> –	Total Extension Cost in PCEPI-\$ represents the total extended operations cost summed for all years of program reporting as actual cost reported in the NASA budget requests and adjusted to Year 2022-\$ using the PCEPI index.	<i>Cruise</i> –	The Cruise mass is associated with cruise phase elements of the space vehicle. In the case of a cruise phase, the spacecraft consists of the science payload-carrying vehicle, and the Cruise segment transfers the spacecraft from an Earth orbit to a destination, either with or without orbit capture. (kgs)
		<i>Lander</i> –	The lander mass is associated with the landing and deployment phase elements of the space vehicle. In the case of a landing phase, the lander includes both the science payload and a carrying and support landing vehicle. (kgs)
		<i>Aeroshield (Aero)</i> –	The aeroshield mass is associated with re-entry shield elements of the space vehicle. In the case of a re-entry phase, the spacecraft consists of a science payload-carrying and support vehicle. (kgs)
		<i>Obj</i> –	The number of objectives quantifies the published scientific objectives of the mission. A standard for space mission objectives does not exist. The values reported represent an estimate of the scientific and functional objectives of the mission. Delivery of

Technical

The technical definition provides the design attributes of the mission elements. This includes:

Launch mass

	secondary payloads and continuation of service as a communication relay are examples of additional objectives attributed to the mission objective quantity. (quantity)	<i>BoMPwr</i> –	The reported solar array power capability at destination orbit at perihelion as determined at the beginning of the mission (BoM). (Watts)
<i>Ins</i> –	The number of science instruments manifested with the mission, including radio science (+1). Instruments are defined as science-gathering devices and exclude power and data electronics that directly support one or more instruments. In their presence, the mass and power associated with support electronics are included in the individual instrument properties. In the case of multiple or redundant units, the science is counted as a particular quantity. For example, a mission may include multiple magnetometer units that are considered a single magnetometer experiment due to redundancy or cross-correlation. (quantity)	<i>BoSPwr</i> –	The reported solar array power capability at destination orbit at perihelion as determined at the beginning of science (BoS), where there is an extended non-science operation phase of the mission. (Watts)
		<i>Solar Array Area (SAA)</i> –	The documented or calculated from spacecraft geometry, the total area of the spacecraft's solar array(s). When calculated, a packing factor of 0.90 or 0.95 is used. (meters ²)
		<i>Solar Array Type (SAT)</i> –	The type of solar array included in the spacecraft design, including mount and articulation employed. (2-axis gimbal, roll out, body mount, wing, articulated, fixed)
<i>InsMass</i> –	The reported mass of all payload instruments is recorded as the sum of the payload components or a combination of components, including power and data units that directly support individual or multiple payload instruments. (kgs)		
<i>InsPwr</i> –	The reported instrument power orbit average power of the payload components as determined by allocation, the sum of payload instruments, or a combination that includes the power associated with power and data units that directly support individual or multiple payload instruments. (Watts)		
<i>Deployments (Deploy)</i> –	The number of unique mission deployments, excluding separation from the launch vehicle adapter. Solar array deployment constitutes a single deployment independent of the number of wings or staged to deploy the solar array(s) fully. The number of deployments is a measure of the complexity and risk associated with spacecraft and operations. (quantity)		
<i>Bus Volume (BV)</i> –	Where documented or calculated from spacecraft dimensions, the value represents the volume of the spacecraft core structure in launch configuration. (meters ³)		
<i>SA</i> –	Indicates the primary source of spacecraft power, including solar arrays (SA) or Radioactive Thermal Generator (RTG). (RTG or SA)		
<i>BoLP</i> –	The reported solar array power capability at 1 AU beginning of life (BoL) for a fully deployed solar array complement. (Watts)		